

It's Not All About Song and Dance: How the *Natyashastra* Informs
Contemporary Bollywood

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To my BFFs:

I am better because of you.

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ABSTRACT

The increasing popularity of Bollywood cinema and Indian culture is undeniable. However, despite its popularity, Bollywood cinema has not received much rigorous academic attention. This study intends to go some way to filling this research gap. First, a historical overview of Bollywood cinema is provided, followed by a description of the methodology (critical analysis) of this study, and a description of the findings in this exploratory qualitative study using the ancient Sanskrit treatise – the *Natyashastra*. Three films are used in the study, which seeks to examine whether popular Bollywood cinema continues to follow the dramaturgical tradition described in the *Natyashastra*. The conclusions are based on a critical analysis of the *Natyashastra* and the films used. This study is the first of its kind in how it relates the *Natyashastra* with Bollywood cinema and leads to interesting possibilities for the development of an indigenous theory to understand and analyze film in the future.

Keywords: Bollywood, *Natyashastra*, critical analysis, Indian cinema

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Cue: Emotional music. A field of golden yellow flowers. A boy clad in a leather jacket stands with a guitar, and a girl in a skirt and blouse runs to him. He enfolds her in his arms. Cut.

Two brothers face each other shouting at each other, "Mere paas Maa hai!" (I have our mother) Cut.

Cue: Music. (Black and White) A couple under an umbrella in the rain, soaked to the skin. Cut.

"But this is a different universe," said an American film scholar after watching his first Hindi film ([Lutgendorf, 2006](#)), adding that of all the various cinemas with which he was familiar and had studied, it is Bollywood cinema (or Indian popular cinema) that defies all aesthetic and dramatic rules. In the eyes of the Western scholar, Bollywood cinema defies classification. One reason for this may be that any attempt to classify and interpret Bollywood film requires understanding of the phenomenon of Bollywood. Because, Bollywood is not simply about film, it is part of the Indian cultural identity: the big noisy colorful weddings, the large dramatic families, and the bursting into song and dance every few minutes. In some ways, Bollywood serves as a mirror to Indian societal development and history.

The name "Bollywood" derives from "Tollywood," a name given to Bengali language cinema, named after the physical address of the film industry in Calcutta — a place called "Tollygunge" ([Prasad, 2003](#)). Film industry lore says that in 1932, an American engineer, writing in *American Cinematographer*, received a telegram upon his return from India (where he worked on some of the earliest films produced in India) saying: "*Tollywood sends best wishes happy new year to Lubill film doing wonderful records broken*" ([Prasad, 2003](#)). The origins of the

telegram are lost to obscurity, but the name stuck, and newspapers such as the *Junior Statesman* in West Bengal ([Sarkar, 2008](#)) used it. Today, Tollywood also refers to the Telugu and Tamil film industries from the Indian states of Tamil Nadu, Telangana and Andhra Pradesh (It's actually just the Bengali and Telugu film industries that are referred to as Tollywood). But the term "Bollywood" is contentious, and disliked by some who feel that it implies that the Indian film industry is merely a second class derivative of Hollywood. Largely understood to be a combination of the words "Bombay" (now Mumbai) and "Hollywood," the term Bollywood did not actually emerge from these two words ([Bose, 2006](#)). Instead, the modern use of the term Bollywood, may be credited to filmmaker and Indian film scholar Amit Khanna and journalist Bevinda Collaco ([Sarkar, 2008](#)); and refers to the Hindi film industry that remains established in Mumbai, India. The term Bollywood these days is used simultaneously as an affectionate moniker for the Hindi film industry that both mocks the thing it names and celebrates its difference at the same time ([Prasad, 2008](#); [Waugh, 2001](#)); and as subversive and pejorative ([Gopal & Moorti, 2008](#)).

For the Bollywood uninitiated, all Indian cinema is classified under the broad title of "Bollywood." However, the discerning Indian film consumer knows that there are four types of Bollywood films: Popular Indian/Hindi Cinema, Regional Language Indian Cinema, Art or Parallel Cinema from India in Hindi or other Indian languages, and films produced by the Indian diaspora ([Stafford, 2004](#)). Prasad ([2008](#)) has contended that the notion of "Bollywood" is a strategy used by the Indian film industry for marketing its essential, eternal difference, and also a term used by journalists and scholars to reinforce the difference that Indian cinema represents within a clearly defined model of global hegemony and resistance. And while the

discussion on this moniker persists, this researcher sits firmly on the fence on the issue and uses the term “Bollywood” to refer to popular Indian cinema in Hindi.

According to Gary Harmon ([2006](#)), “popular culture” consists of the arts, rituals and events, myths and beliefs, and artifacts commonly shared by a significant part of a population at a specific time. Indian popular culture remains largely influenced by Bollywood cinema, which has pervaded the graphic arts, language, fashion, music, and day-to-day communication. Indians frequently use “*filmy*” dialogue to express themselves and to communicate with their peers, while film music is the soundtrack of choice at religious festivals, weddings and other celebratory occasions. Outside Indian borders, there is a growing fascination with many things Indian, including the colors of India (the now ubiquitous “Color Runs” in many US cities and around the world are inspired by the Indian spring/summer festival of colors: Holi), its people, its food, its belief systems and its popular culture, all of which are evident in a spate of recent Hollywood films including *Eat Pray Love* ([2010](#)), *The Life of Pi* ([2012](#)), *Slumdog Millionaire* ([2008](#)) and *The Best Exotic Marigold Hotel* ([2011](#)) and its sequel released in 2015 ([Madden, 2015](#)), among others.

With the world’s largest democracy (perhaps) poised at the verge of becoming a world superpower ([Sanghoee, 2015](#)), it stands to reason that there is a need to understand modern India and Indians, specifically sensibilities and culture. It is contended that a study of its films provides some insight in this area. Despite its worldwide popularity however, Bollywood cinema continues to remain an under-studied subject of academic research. Researchers have attempted to trace the historical origins and development of Bollywood ([Bose, 2006](#)) and have looked at themes in Bollywood ([Mishra, 1996](#)), the music and dance within it ([Gopal & Moorti,](#)

[2008](#)), Bollywood's place and relevance in Indian society ([Kavoori & Punathambekar, 2008](#)) and within the digital communication age ([Basu, 2010](#)). But little, if any comprehensive literature exists on Bollywood's ties with the Indian cultural heritage, which remains firmly rooted in its indigenous performance arts tradition. If Bollywood cinema is incomprehensible to a non-Indian, with its large-scale focus on song, dance and cinematic spectacle, it is due to the influence of an indigenous performance arts tradition, which is not always readily apparent to outsiders. The examination of the literary tradition is of great relevance to any in-depth study of Bollywood cinema, and to understand the perceptions of Indian audiences.

Bollywood Cinema, or film, has been seen as primarily a text, product, public resource, archive, social history, or myth ([K. J. Kumar, 2011](#)). Bhaumik ([2004](#)) states that Indian cinema fits into a tradition where narrative complexity is low, but audience absorption into the film narrative is high. This leads to a performance immediacy that includes a complex layering of sound, visual effects, dialogue, and dance that resists literary analysis but is key to understanding why and how contemporary Indians and the Indian diaspora continue to be profoundly affected by Indian cinema ([Bhaumik, 2004](#)). Curiously, Bollywood films as a whole, remain resistant to ideological readings, genre analysis, or deconstructive analysis, all of which fail to clearly reveal the relationship between Indian cinema and Indian society ([Bhaumik, 2004](#)). One reason for this may be the tendency of researchers to examine Indian cinema through a post-colonial lens, keeping in mind that film is a relatively new medium that began its journey in India as a byproduct of colonial wealth and influence (for instance, [Bose, 2006](#)). It is also equally possible (if not even more so) that formal education in India is inherently post-

colonial, or even colonial in many aspects, and has largely ignored the study of Indian narrative traditions and works that existed prior to the days of the British Raj.

Discourses and practices of the performing arts tradition in India may be traced back to several traditions and influences. However, one ancient Indian text: The *Natyashastra*; came before them all. The *Natyashastra* (composed in approximately the 3rd century AD) is a treatise on classical Sanskrit drama, dealing with poetic discourse, dramaturgical and aesthetic approaches and experience ([Misra, 2004](#)). This study grounds contemporary Bollywood cinema in the performance tradition, as laid down in the *Natyashastra*, using the critical analysis method.

The Importance of this Study

“It was the first of books; it was as if an empire spake to us, nothing small or unworthy, but large, serene, consistent, the voice of an old intelligence which in another age and climate had pondered and thus disposed of the same questions which exercise us.” (Emerson, 1831 in [Sealts Jr \(1974\)](#))

There is perhaps no other place on earth with a cultural continuity as long as that of India, as other civilizations have risen to greatness, then fallen and been forgotten, only to be remembered through archeological excavations ([Basham, 1975](#)). Indian culture is in a constant state of flux from its beginnings in North India with the Harappans, and with the early Dravidians in the South. “Indian-ness” however, remains an intangible concept, in some ways, easy to culturally appropriate like henna tattoos, bindis, and Yoga.

Relatively small in geographical area, India is positioned to be the most populous nation in the world by 2020, and these numbers do not include the Indian diaspora – which forms a consumptive audience for all things Indian. The Indian government estimates that over 15 million people form the Indian diaspora ([India, 2016](#)). In the USA alone, while Indian-Americans make up only approximately 1 percent of the US population according to 2010 USA Census data, with figures between 2.81 million (sole Indian ancestry) and 3.18 million (mixed ancestry) ([Pew Research Center's & Demographic Trends, 2012](#)), they still form the country's third-largest self-reported Asian-American group, after Chinese-Americans and Filipino-Americans ([Pew Research Center's & Demographic Trends, 2012](#)). There are records of Indians coming to America in the 1800s, and an exhibit at the Natural History Museum, Washington, D.C., (sponsored by the Smithsonian Asian-Pacific Center) in 2014 traced the journey of Indian-Americans in the United States ([Jain, 2016](#)). While Indian-Americans have largely integrated within the American population, they maintain their unique cultural traditions. Consuming Indian media exports like film is one of the ways reported by the Indian diaspora to remain in touch with its cultural origins and developments ([Punathambekar, 2005](#)).

The “Indian” impact is not limited to geographical India or its diaspora, and Indian culture has been “translated” and adapted worldwide. Yoga, for instance, the best example of an Indian cultural export, is a multi-million-dollar industry ([D. G. White, 2011](#)). If Yoga appeals to Americans' minds, Indian food appeals to their taste buds. An article on Salon.com predicts that Indian food is poised to become the next trendy ethnic food in the 2010s ([Rogers, 2010](#)). Ethnic and spicy cuisines have become increasingly popular in America, and after a survey, some researchers found that there are a number of reasons that Indian food is increasingly

popular, including the variety of vegetarian options available, and the value for money ([Josiam & Monteiro, 2004](#)). A more intense fondness for Indian food exists in the UK, where it is considered as British as the British, and the reasons for this are the familiarity with Indian food, its value for money and its intense flavor ([H. White, 2004](#)).

Indian culture, such as it is seen today, is a composite, amalgamated culture ([Keay, 2010](#)). The modern Indian may be considered similarly composite, with a worldview that is individual, yet reflecting the traditional value systems of a society. Indian cultural symbols like food, clothing, and belief systems reinforce identity and race perceptions among the largest known diaspora in the world. Performance-based Indian media add to this cultural reinforcement, allowing second-generation Indian-Americans for instance to bridge the black-white dichotomy that exists within the larger American identity ([Maira, 2012](#)). Indian-American youth reproduce Indian-film tableaux at social and public events as a means of reinforcing and distinguishing their cultural identity, usually transforming such performances to blend in with their birth-identities ([Maira, 2012](#)).

One of India's major cultural exports is its media of film and music. Once dismissed as ridiculous, over-the-top musicals ([R. Dudrah & Rai, 2005](#)), Bollywood can no longer be ignored in the global film arena for one main reason: the numbers. In 2014, a *Forbes* data journalist examined the numbers for Bollywood cinema and found that while Bollywood films made a relatively small \$1.6 billion in box office revenue, compared to Hollywood films at \$10.8 billion; it was other figures that made it clear that Bollywood cinema was here to stay ([McCarthy, 2015](#)). Bollywood produced 1,602 films in 2014, as compared to Hollywood at 476; and sold a whopping 2.6 billion cinema tickets, as compared to Hollywood at 1.3 billion ([McCarthy, 2015](#)).

And while Jerry Seinfeld was estimated as being the world's wealthiest actor, with an estimated worth of \$820 million, India's superstar Shahrukh Khan, came in second, with an estimated personal wealth of \$600 million, with 90s heartthrob Tom Cruise coming in at \$480 million ([McCarthy, 2015](#)). Bollywood is a large part of the process that has changed the image of India in the global arena: from developing country to an emerging superpower ([Ganti, 2012](#)).

Bollywood has transcended boundaries to influence global culture in many ways. It has become a symbol of non-monolithic cultural globalization and has even begun to influence western film processes ([Matusitz & Payano, 2012](#)). The worldwide pervasion of Bollywood culture also demonstrates that globalization does not equal westernization ([Matusitz & Payano, 2012](#)). Bollywood films have a reach that extends beyond India's borders. Bollywood films are exported to countries in South Asia, Africa, South America, as well as countries belonging to the former Soviet Union ([Kasbekar, 1996](#)). Bollywood films have become something of an international obsession or phenomenon; and in 2014, the International Indian Film Awards (IIFA) were held in Florida, USA. The televised awards had an estimated viewership of 800 million. Bollywood film actors too have their place in expanding geographical reach, with the likes of Raj Kapoor being seen as an ambassador of Indian culture in the past ([Bose, 2006](#)), and Shah Rukh Khan being given the Knight of the Legion of Honor by the French Government in 2014 (the highest civilian order bestowed by the French government) ([Joshi, 2014](#)).

The inspiration for this study was provided by innumerable Hindi movies watched and experienced, but it is more influenced by the increasing evidence of all things Indian in daily life. In India, Bollywood and other regional-language cinema form the backdrop for life: at weddings, evenings at home, and celebrations at home and school. Music from the films blares

from loudspeakers mounted on poles at religious festivals, at weddings, and even during moments of distress. Dialogue from the movies is as much a part of speech within India as slang is in pragmatic American English. And today, American television pop culture includes more aspects than ever before that are part of Bollywood culture.

The increasing ubiquity of Bollywood in many aspects of popular culture and everyday life is undeniable, but the origins of the narrative and art-form traditions that inform contemporary and past Indian cinema are shrouded in mystery, and blurry. The identification and study of the literary traditions of Bollywood could provide clues to understanding the formation of identity, cohesion, social stratifications and mores within contemporary Indian society.

The *Natyashastra* has been chosen for an exploratory study of Bollywood cinema. There are several reasons for this choice as the critical basis for understanding Bollywood cinema. The *Natyashastra* is an ancient, but comprehensive treatise on performance. It has never been examined in any systematic comprehensive fashion. As a researcher, the opportunity to examine something that is essentially virgin territory is exciting as well as intimidating. This study also seeks to establish a case for the foundation for a critical metatheory specific to examining Bollywood cinema, while hoping to debunk the notion of Bollywood as fluffy, non-serious cinema and instead to be viewed as a cultural artefact. As globalization and the diaspora become more key to understanding the modern Indian, the subject of this study is more relevant than ever before and has revealed influences and directions taken by contemporary mass media even as global and new media influences emerge, develop and transform.

Foundations of this Study

The term culture is difficult to describe and to define; there are over 164 documented definitions of culture ([Sriramesh & Verčič, 2012](#)). One of the earliest definitions of culture is, “The complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, art, morals, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society” ([Tylor, 1871, p. 1](#)). Culture also has been defined as the entire way of life of a community of people, including their technology and material artifacts, and as knowledge required for being a functioning member of society ([Geertz & Marić, 1972](#)). A later definition of culture states it is a shared system of publicly available symbolic forms through which people experience and express meaning ([Keesing, 1974](#)). Still others see culture as a reservoir of symbols, stories, rituals and language, which people may use to their advantage to solve problems, thus making culture an impetus for community action ([Hannerz, 1990](#)). But perhaps one of the most pertinent definitions for this study, is the idea that culture is made up of symbolic systems ([Cassirer, 1957](#)). In this study, the term culture refers to that ephemeral *mélange* that is part of the larger context of a society, contributing to the community’s unique identity. Culture is that complex whole that defines society through its historical, sociological and anthropological developments.

This study focuses on Bollywood, the Hindi-language film industry, because Hindi is the national language of India, and Hindi films are ubiquitously watched all over India and abroad by the Indian diaspora ([Trivedi, 2008](#)). It is an attempt at understanding just how much of one distinctive part of Indian popular culture — Bollywood — remains in keeping with India’s literary tradition. The Indian literary tradition, like Indian culture, is also amalgamated and complex.

A literary tradition is meant to be a temporal map, a means of negotiating the centuries and connections between writers and stories ([McEwan, 2006](#)). A literary tradition implies an active historical sense of the past, living in and shaping the present ([McEwan, 2006](#)). Western literature is believed to have followed the literary practices of storytelling in the Greek tradition of drama and literature as laid down by Aristotle's fragmentary lecture notes, the *Poetics*, which have been followed by Stravinsky's *Poetics of Music*, Todorov's *Poetics of Prose*, a study of the poetics of architecture, and the Russian Formalists' *Poetics of the Cinema* ([Bordwell, 2008](#)).

The latter, the *Poetics of Cinema* may be most relevant to this study, as it is described as “a systematic enquiry into the presuppositions of artistic traditions,” of trying to ascertain the filmmaker’s secrets, even those of which they may not have been conscious ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). David Bordwell ([2008](#)) calls for historically-inflected *Poetics* in the field of film studies, one that takes into account the historical and anthropological development of society, which in turn influences cinema. This will alert researchers to changes and continuities in society and could help predict future trends. While this is common in mature disciplines, in film studies this idea is novel but will aid researchers in situating mass media such as film, within a historical context ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). Bordwell ([2008](#)) has also postulated that there is an institutional practice, patterns that are normative in the way films are made, and in their elements. Thus, literary traditions are not static and rigid realities but must instead be understood as fluid and heterogeneous.

No study about Bollywood can be carried out without some rudimentary understanding of Indian culture and history. Indian myths, folk tales, and traditions are passed on through the oral tradition, and are deeply enmeshed in everyday life, forming part of the day-to-day cultural

mores and belief systems. Many themes in Bollywood cinema are immediately recognizable to those familiar with the two main Indian Epics: *The Ramayana* and *The Mahabharata*. An understanding of the historical and cultural context is imperative to be able to draw any conclusions on the nature of Bollywood. This is in keeping with the ethnographic nature of the critical methodology used in this study.

Finally, as stated, the goal of this study is to establish the relevance of an ancient Hindu dramatic text (the *Natyashastra*) in a historically changed context, i.e. contemporary Bollywood cinema. The *Natyashastra* was chosen for this study to evaluate traditional influences in contemporary Bollywood cinema. The author of the *Natyashastra*, who is generically named “Bharata Muni” (translated to “the Sage Bharata”), is widely believed to be a composite of the many people who contributed to the treatise. The *Natyashastra* is concerned with movement, voice, emotional expression, and the stylization of the body with makeup and costume, all of which are considered essential — not merely important — to artistic performance ([Misra, 2004](#)). However, it is important to note that the *Natyashastra* is not only concerned with aesthetics but also the psychology of performance, and understanding the theory within the *Natyashastra* is fundamental to understanding Indian performance art and the artistic experience.

The *Natyashastra* differs fundamentally from the *Poetics* by Aristotle and is distinct in the way it approaches the art of performance. However, ancient Greek drama is said to be disconnected from modern western drama ([Gupt, 2006](#)), but Indian contemporary drama and other traditional forms of art (like music and dance) still adhere to (at least in some aspects) the “classical” Indian tradition. While both Greek and Indian traditions in theory and practice

subscribe to the theory of *heiropraxis* (the idea that drama is divinely inspired), where drama is concerned, Greek drama first emphasized semiotics and later emphasized the lexical, the Indian tradition did and continues to emphasize the semiotic aspect of performance ([Gupt, 2006](#)) and rarely the lexical. Indian performance arts instead prioritized aural and visual elements, including makeup, gesture, song, and dance to convey the essence and the message ([Gupt, 2006](#)).

This study is based on the assumption that film does not follow any predetermined path, but is instead shaped by people, who are in turn bound and shaped by historical events and current structures. The research approach and theoretical framework for this study is informed by Critical Theory, and thus this study includes the sometimes conflicting, differing interests of the stakeholders involved in the Bollywood film industry, including the audience, the producers and the actors.

Purpose of the Study

This study makes a two-fold contribution – practical and theoretical. Practically, it provides a new approach and focus for Bollywood film-study enthusiasts, in a way that other studies have not provided. The new approach will be centered in a uniquely Indian aesthetic tradition and context, unlike most previous studies which took a western-centric approach. The theoretical contribution includes its novel application of the critical analysis method to Bollywood film, using a classical Indian text, something that has hitherto not been attempted. This adds to the small, but growing body of academic literature available on Bollywood cinema.

Statement of the Problem

Clearly it is difficult to fit Indian cinema into any neat pigeonholes. This is due to a myriad of reasons, not the least of which is that while film is a relatively new medium, the themes depicted and other narrative devices used in the creation of film derive from ancient traditions like the *Natyashastra*. Despite the acknowledgement of traditional devices used in contemporary classical Indian dance and music, there have been no attempts in academia to ascertain how many of the literary devices specified in the *Natyashastra* continue to be used in Bollywood cinema. The author hopes to fill this knowledge-gap using the critical analysis method, which encourages questioning of surface meanings, assumptions and beliefs. This study is exploratory in nature, meaning that it did not begin with a well-defined hypothesis, but instead attempts to address the following broad research question:

- Does the *Natyashastra* continue to inform Bollywood film production?

The following literature review looks at Bollywood as an ecosystem, making it easier to understand all the interwoven histories, factors, and variables that may have affected Bollywood cinema over the decades. It also includes an overview of storytelling in India, and of the *Natyashastra*. This is followed by the section on the methodology, then a chapter detailing the aspects of the *Natyashastra* used in this study, and by three chapter case studies of three separate films.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Bollywood Information Ecology System

There is evidence to suggest that meaning in film may be conceptualized at multiple interwoven levels ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). This is because the production of film includes multiple stakeholders, contributors and factors. It therefore seems prudent to break this literature review down to understand the phenomenon that is Bollywood, by looking at the ecosystem that comprises the Indian film industry, including the communication traditions, its systems, and its theoretical traditions.

Nardi & O'Day ([1999](#)) describe an information ecology as a system of people, practices, values, and technologies in a particular local environment. While this definition was mainly relevant to local libraries, schools and other such institutions, there is emerging work examining information ecologies in the cases of virtual communities and other “imagined communities.” One of the aims of the Anthropology Department and Institute of Ecology at the University of Georgia, USA, (or H.E. Kuchka, as the group refers to itself) is to study how information systems are correlated to ecosystems of culture ([Kuchka, 2011](#)). As they have pointed out, anthropology as a discipline has long applied the science of ecology to human behavior and adaptation, and one of its primary concerns is to understand how culture brings meaning to human lives and guides behavior ([Kuchka, 2011](#)). Culture, and all its elements, including rituals, symbols, and the meaning they impart determine the way information is used ([Kuchka, 2011](#)).

In this study, the Indian Hindi film industry is treated as an information ecology, to break down and understand the factors involved in the system more efficiently. Any study of Indian

cinema — and Bollywood especially — is incomplete without at least some reference to the developments and changes within the Indian film industry. Bollywood provides a history of events in India, albeit a distorted version of reality, lived out by “others” who make the audience acknowledge them ([Nandy, 1998](#)). The study of Bollywood is challenging, because it is a business, a means of expression, an agent of social change, and a part of traditional and popular culture. A possible way to study Bollywood, is to separate its business aspects from its creative aspects ([Rajadhyaksha, 2003](#)), or using a journalistic analogy — to separate editorial from business. Here, it is Indian cinema that is under study and not the business of making films in India, but without one, there isn't the other. Without profit, there can be no industry, and without industry, there is no continued artistic expression. Making films is expensive.

The ecosystem approach also makes it easier to understand and pinpoint the different aspects that could be studied independently, or that could be understood as integral parts of a whole, without which an ecosystem would fall apart. In this study, the producers of media content, the audiences for the content, as well as the environment within which the content is produced, are all part of the larger ecosystem of Bollywood and must be examined if any kind of theory is to be developed, connecting the aesthetic traditions within India to the production and reception of Bollywood cinema.

The *Natyashastra*, the treatise to be used as the basis for this study, contains rules and standards for the production of the performance arts. The *Natyashastra* emphasizes that the culture and value systems surrounding the audience are a major part of the dramatic experience. It has been contended that audiences absorb most of their information unconsciously simply by being exposed to their environment ([Bates, 2002](#); [Williamson, 2005](#)). It

also has been suggested that it is difficult to isolate cultural and historical environmental influences from other macro-environmental influences ([Sekaran, 1983](#)). The unconscious influence of the environment is subtle, pervasive ([Dewey, 1916](#)), and almost impossible to study. It affects all aspects of human behavior, but specifically, it may be seen in the use of language, manner, and good taste and aesthetic appreciation ([Dewey, 1916](#)). The aesthetic eye is trained and becomes accustomed to a certain standard and forms ([Dewey, 1916](#)).

Williamson's Ecological Model of Information Behavior ([2005](#)) postulates that information behavior exists not in a vacuum, but within a context of other factors surrounding the content consumers. It is important to understand these factors to situate the system, the medium, and the content ([Williamson, 2005](#)) within the larger context. It is also essential to understand the factors affecting Bollywood, film in India in general, the content and form of film, as well as the audience behavior of those consuming Bollywood film.

Nardi and O'Day ([1999](#)) characterized information ecology with certain properties, which may be similarly used to study the Bollywood industry ecology. An information ecology consists of the system, which is the sum total of all the parts and relationships ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)). In this case, the Bollywood film industry is considered the system. An ecological system is constantly evolving, and diverse in its composition, where it is understood that societies and cultures are constantly changing ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)). Indian culture and society (which includes that of the diaspora) is similarly evolving. The diverse components of an ecosystem evolve, in a symbiotic fashion, where parts are understood to be co-dependent ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)).

There are also several keystone “species” that are vital to the successful working of the ecosystem, who may be skilled people necessary to support the effective use of the technology ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)). These “keystone species” are individuals who have changed or may change the course of history or development of the ecosystem. In the history of Bollywood, there are notable individuals who have affected, changed, and assisted in the development of Bollywood; including actors, directors, and technologists who have proved vital or significant in some way.

And lastly, information ecologies have a sense of “locality” ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)). This term, though problematic, is also at the heart of understanding Bollywood in its entirety. For instance, Bollywood is an indigenous film industry, based in Mumbai, India. However, its reach and impact are seen worldwide. Its target audience is mainly audiences within India and the Indian diaspora.

The above properties are used in this literature review to depict, better organize, and review material that is correlated.

Some Theoretical Foundations

This chapter presents some of the philosophical assumptions that were reviewed during this study. The theories reviewed here have influenced and informed the research effort and are thus an important part. They also serve as a point of reference for those judging and reviewing this study in the future. The theoretical perspectives mentioned herein also serve another purpose: they illustrate the difficulty in pigeonholing Bollywood cinema within a neat theoretical foundation.

Introduction to Critical Theory

In Critical Theory “the world and subjectivity in all its forms have developed with the life processes of society” ([Horkheimer, 1972, p. 246](#)). Critical Theory is not a scientific paradigm, but is instead a reflexive and politically-inspired mode of enquiry, sensitive to the vagaries of history ([Hope, 1996](#)). Critical Theory encompasses a collection of theories formulated by researchers with a common aim, who were followers of varying schools of thought and disciplines. The origins of Critical Theory lie within the objective idealist tradition, which finds the traditional theoretical tenet that the researcher needs to remain an uninvolved observer and produce work that is free of value judgement to be implausible ([Bohman, 2015](#)). Critical Theory also may be distinguished from traditional theory in that it was deemed “Critical” because its original purpose was to seek “human emancipation from slavery,” act as a liberating influence, and act as an equalizer ([Horkheimer, 1972](#)). It may be interpreted that Critical Theory provides a foundation aimed at decreasing domination of existing doctrines and increasing freedom of thought.

In addition, “Critical Theory is concerned with preventing the loss of truth that past knowledge has labored to attain” ([Marcuse, 1969](#)). Critical theorists have focused on the skewing of discourse due to a normalization of social order, universalization of managerial interests, domination of instrumental reasoning and the production of consent ([Alvesson & Deetz, 2006](#)). They sought to change the dialectic through a comprehension of social/historical/political constructionism, a broader conception of rationality, the inclusion of viewpoints from sections of society that were previously silenced, and by challenging structures that confine people ([Alvesson & Deetz, 2006](#)). Critical theorists conceptualize reality and events

using power relations. Critical Theory asks that historical and social contexts be taken into account in any research situation. In the context of this study, Critical Theory is useful to understand the idea of questioning established ways of thinking and perceiving Bollywood cinema. However, it fails to provide any kind of blanket perspective that could be used in this study. Film theory is examined next for its focused insights into film.

Film Theory and its (ir)Relevance

“Film needs theory like it needs a scratch on a negative.” ([Alan Parker in Lapsley & Westlake, 2006 Foreword p. vi](#))

There are those who believe film theory is unnecessary or dead ([Carroll, 1996](#)), or deliberately obtuse, and impractical ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). Whatever the case, film theory exists to make sense of the art of the production of the film, as well as to make attempts to understand spectatorship of film. But even those who reject theory as a detriment to the enjoyment of experiencing film are in fact simply unaware of the theories that they are using to have come to that conclusion ([Stam, 2000](#)).

Film theory is an international and multicultural field that often remains monolingual, provincial and sexist ([Stam, 2000](#)). It is a line of inquiry dedicated to generalizations about film, or devoted to isolating, tracking, and/or accounting for any mechanisms, devices, patterns, and regularities in the field of cinema ([Carroll, 1996](#)). Film theory broadly follows two traditions: realism and formalism. Some of the first films in existence, including the Lumière Brothers’ films, followed the realism tradition, in that they attempted as far as possible to depict the world as it actually is, within the framework of an artistic medium ([Stam, 2000](#)). Films following the realism tradition tend to emphasize reality more than style or narrative. Indian parallel

cinema¹ tends to follow this tradition, choosing to emphasize realism rather than form. Two prominent theorists following this tradition were Siegfried Kracauer ([1960](#)) and Andre Bazin ([2004](#)), who viewed contemporary cinema as an evolution of the photographic medium.

Kracauer ([1960](#)) even went so far as to suggest that films have built their aesthetic validity from their base properties by recording and revealing physical reality. But while Kracauer ([1960](#)) and Bazin's ([2004](#)) works has many redeeming qualities, their work is rejected for one main reason, in that they speak only about the depiction of reality and do not emphasize the creative art form that cinema can be. Popular Bollywood cinema has largely disregarded the realism tradition, with most films melding social realism with melodrama in a far cry from parallel cinema ([Bhaumik, 2004](#)).

Formalist film theorists believe that cinema is possible mainly because it makes the depiction of the unreal – real, and that the real world is primarily a storehouse of raw material to be drawn and reshaped into art ([Giannetti & Leach, 1999](#)). The Formalist approach to filmmaking emphasizes form, style or aestheticism over reality. The main proponents of formalism are considered to be Georges Melie, Sergei Eisenstein, and Rudolph Arnheim ([Giannetti & Leach, 1999](#)). However, formalism is a fragmented school of thought where all the proponents of formalism agree that a filmmaker should indeed manipulate reality to express himself on film, but how this is done, differs. The Formalist school of thought is more in keeping with Bollywood cinema, which largely draws on “real world” scenarios as raw material for the

¹ Parallel cinema or Art Cinema in the Indian context are those films that do not follow the popular Bollywood formulae, (no or few song-and-dance sequences). This is further explained later and in more depth within Appendix 1.

creation of art, but blends this with melodrama and other stylistic elements drawing from Indian dramatic traditions ([Bhaumik, 2004](#)).

Bollywood films also may be perceived as cultural artifacts. Cape ([2003](#)) says that it is useful to think of films in general as a “cultural reservoir,” reflecting what is largely taken for granted or implicit in a society. Perhaps in no other film industry is this more famously apparent than Bollywood cinema ([Cape, 2003](#)). Kaur ([2002](#)) says that popular cinema does not exist for the purpose of self-gratification, or for fulfilling specific objectives, adding that popular cinema deals with narratives that have their origins in sociopolitical transformations in society, including the commercial factors that influence their shape and existence. Society thus provides the raw material to influence cinema but is also influenced by it in turn. The relationship, she states, is one of symbiosis, a give and take. The history, beliefs, and values of a society find their way into the narratives of popular cinema ([Kaur, 2002](#)), emerging in their ideal forms, and attempt to transform society into the ideals the medium depicts.

Communication of meaning in a film may be seen as being of four types: referential, explicit, explicative, and symptomatic ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). Symptomatic meaning refers to the manifestation within the viewer of a meaning that is determined by social cultural forces or otherwise unconscious psychological forces in the viewer’s ecological environment ([Bordwell, 2008](#)). This is perhaps immediately evident in indigenous cinema like Bollywood, which bears indelible stamps of the culture within which it is produced.

Formalist art critic and art philosopher Clive Bell ([1914](#)) advocated for an approach to visual art focusing on aesthetic emotion. His approach emphasized the existence of an emotion that is evoked by aesthetic qualities within the form of the artistic object. In the visual arts

(specifically painting and sculpture), these qualities are embodied in the forms and relations of forms which Bell termed “significant form” in totality. Bell’s view is that “significant form” evokes a response that is dissimilar to other emotional responses – one that is only evoked in experiencing art ([Bell, 1914](#)). In this aspect, Bell’s approach ([1914](#)) has strong associations to Kantian philosophy, which similarly disassociates aesthetic appreciation from other emotions. Aesthetic appreciation in this vein evokes an emotion most closely reminiscent perhaps of a religious experience.

However, there are problems with Bell’s views, as there are no clear assertions on the standards that govern “forms and relations of forms” ([McLaughlin, 1977](#)). Bell has also been criticized for emphasis on subjectivity in art appreciation ([McLaughlin, 1977](#)). In the context of this study however, Bell’s work seems applicable as the *Natyashastra* explicitly states that aesthetic emotion is evoked in the process of experiencing dramatic arts forms. As opposed to Bell’s approach however, it clearly delineates the conditions and “rules” involved in the creation of this dramatic experience. Bell’s emphasis was that the aesthetic emotional response was the primary criterion in judging or experiencing any work of art and not in what the art work is trying to represent or express. In his words, “the starting point for all systems of aesthetics must be the personal experience of a peculiar emotion” ([Bell, 1914, p. 3](#)).

In an earlier time, Plato believed that only paradigms could explain our worlds, illustrating this with the concept that justice and beauty do not exist in the “real” world, but as abstract concepts. Yet they are understood. This means that we somehow supply the missing meanings of those words, thereby creating new ways of thinking about the world. The sentiments in this are reframed by Deleuze ([Kennedy, 2000](#)), who states that what

differentiates cinema from other art forms is that it allows the audience to imagine and reflect (perhaps even recreate) time and movement. The Indian narrative tradition articulated in the *Natyashastra* explicitly states that art must be experienced, must be transcendental and must inform and educate, making it somewhat similar to the handful of Western theorists who have advocated for emphasis on artistic experience.

Other researchers have asserted the dearth of consideration of studies and theory on film aesthetics. Galt ([2009](#)) insists that the rhetoric of film theory has consistently denigrated “prettiness” in film. The idea that aesthetically appealing films can be “good” films is seen as problematic. Meanwhile, critical and cultural theorists, have omitted or sidelined the study of the “aesthetics of sensation,” a term coined by Barbara Kennedy ([2000](#)), to explain how what is visually perceived is intrinsically bound with what is felt emotionally. Mishra ([2009](#)) has talked about the experience of watching Bollywood film in a similar vein; of the difficulty of remaining detached from the experience of film during the writing of his book on Bollywood cinema.

The Auteur theory from the 1960s emphasized the personal style of film aesthetics, and work analyzed in this vein generally examined a body of work specific to a single producer or a group of like-minded people ([Bordwell & Carroll, 2012](#)). While the body of work produced in Bollywood comprises several notable people who brought their own indomitable style with them, their work still bears the hallmark of “*masala*” or popular cinema. Since it attempts to define elements of Bollywood cinema vis-à-vis the *Natyashastra*, this study was not based on the auteur theory.

There are also critics who advocate for the inclusion of ethnographic vision to cinema, focusing on the audience tastes for “images of people of color,” contending that there is a tendency for cinematic producers to construct and regard any focus on “spectacle” as colonial aesthetic ([Rony, 1996](#)). In “The Third Eye,” Rony ([1996](#)) examines representations of non-western people in film and determines that there is a definite creation of the “other” in cinema. This in turn spills into the study of film, in which the depiction of the exotic is generally viewed as “wrong,” or is trivialized ([Rony, 1996](#)). Using a variety of films to illustrate her points, she reveals how constructions within the Western perspective of race, gender, nation and empire are skewed ([Rony, 1996](#)). This concept may be illustrated using the instance of the film *Hero* by Zhang Yimou ([Zhang, 2002](#)), which features a richly toned mise-en-scene, which has been reviewed by critics as veiling a lack of meaningful depth, a refusal of political speech, and even as an endorsement of authoritarianism ([Chan, 2004](#); [Galt, 2009](#); [Harrison, 2006](#)). This provides certain explanations of why Bollywood cinema is portrayed and understood by outsiders as somehow inferior to Western cinema, exposes the hegemony of western modes of thought in film criticism of Bollywood cinema, and also makes a case for having an Indian ethnographic understanding of Bollywood film.

In order to achieve this, it becomes necessary to adopt the middle-level approach of analyzing film; which is to reject the notion of an overarching theory that can help elucidate the elements within Bollywood cinema. Bordwell ([2012](#)) advocates a middle-level approach to research in film, stating “Big Theory” should not get in the way of interesting research. Carroll ([1996](#)) has advocated for a “piece-meal” approach to the formation of film theory, asserting that mini-theories that apply to some aspect of film, or certain genres, etc. are more relevant

than trying to formulate broad overarching theories about film in general. This study uses the *Natyashastra* as the primary lens to understand Bollywood elements and style, but it by no means denies other influences in Bollywood cinema, including individual styles, and other socio-cultural elements.

Mass Media Theory and Film

The main distinction between interpersonal communication and mass communication in any western theory is that the former operates at a one-to-one level and the other at a one-to-many level ([O'Sullivan, Dutton, & and Rayne, 2003](#)). Traditional mass media had four characteristics in common: distance (between the sender of the message and the receiver); technology (a mode of transmission); scale (involving simultaneous communication to large-scale audiences), and commodification (all mass media came with a financial cost) ([O'Sullivan et al., 2003](#)). Other traditional mass media have conformed to the new media characteristics of technology (they need technology), personalization (they can be personalized), and collective control (each audience member has the ability to shape, share and change the content) ([Crosbie, 2002](#)). Following this definition, film is one of the last surviving true mass media, and movie theatres are places of mass media spectatorship.

However, it is surprising to note that contemporary mass media theorists have largely remained silent on the interpretation of film and have been ignored as film theorists. Research into Bollywood cinema may be seen from two points of view, that of the audience (media effects theories), and that of the creator ([Rai, 2009](#)). Creator intent theories or auteur intent theories have been covered mainly by literary theorists from several perspectives, including those from the Schools of thought of New Criticism, Psychoanalysis, Marxist Criticism, Post-

Structuralism, Reader Response, and more recently from Intentionalism ([Burke, 1998](#)). In the traditional theories centered on auteur intent, the sender of messages may presume knowledge of a shared code, as well as assume an understanding of the receiver. Bollywood's stylistic tendencies such as "epic dispersion, cyclicity, artifice, and irony" are perhaps successful among Indian audiences because of this shared code ([M. Sen & Basu, 2013](#)).

This shared code is markedly important to note and understand within this study. It is the basis of a multi-million-dollar industry; Bollywood is now an ecosystem that includes a "range of entities and activities intent on producing, consolidating and promoting a remarkably plastic—at once flexible and resilient, dynamic and distinctive, specific and universal—brand into a planetary force" ([Sarkar, 2013, p. 236](#)). Bollywood has of late has not only been studied using the industrial/institutional studies approach ([Sarkar, 2013](#)) but has also been studied using the media effects perspective, where it has been thought of as an agent of performing identity ([Alessandrini, 2001](#); [Bandyopadhyay, 2008](#); [Bhattachariya, 2009](#); [Dawson, 2005](#); [Rajinder Kumar Dudrah, 2002](#); [Harper, 2013](#); [Sarrazin, 2008](#)), in terms of media messages ([Rajendar Kumar Dudrah, 2006](#)), and has been studied for its the affective style of filmmaking ([Neumann, 2014](#)).

Media effects theories have originated within theories of the mass media, and it is these theories that seem most relevant to film studies and more specifically to understand how audiences are affected by what is on screen. The *Natyashastra* similarly advocates a two-way communication model in which a certain code, known to both audience and creator, leads to shared understanding and effective communication. This research study, as stated before,

evaluates just how much of this shared code, as laid down in the *Natyashastra*, remains relevant in contemporary Indian cinema and society.

And, in order to do this, it becomes necessary to have some understanding of the film industry in India, which is a part of the larger context of this study. From the advent of film in India before independence to today, audiences in India have become increasingly fragmented, and Bollywood film producers are scrambling to produce films with mass appeal. What would then seem logical (as in the case of western cinema) is the creation of films specifically targeted at niche audiences. Instead, the fragmentation of Bollywood film audiences has resulted in films targeted at two categories of audiences: the masses and the classes ([Ganti, 2012](#)). The Indian Bollywood film audience exists within hierarchies, (which may be examined as a spectatorship theory or a theory of mass audiences, or a theory that binds acceptance with commercial success) ([Ganti, 2012](#)). This has given rise to some researchers who have studied Bollywood audiences using spectatorship theory. Ganti ([2012](#)) for instance, looks at Bollywood audience spectatorship from a perspective that focuses on economics, and argues against a culturalist perspective, arguing that a box office “hit” film is perceived as having universal appeal (within India), which most producers indicates that they have found a “formula” that appeals across borders of caste, class and other social divisions ([Ganti, 2012](#)).

The *Natyashastra* details factors that drive the success of performances. It is incredibly detailed in its rules and standards for the performance of the dramatic arts. A dramatic act is credited as being successful if “*Rasa*” is created. And the creation of *Rasa* (meaning “essence” or to the sensation of enjoyable taste) is dependent on many factors, including aesthetic techniques, rules for drama, music, dance, and makeup. Bollywood cinema has long been

accused of being formulaic ([Kaur, 2002](#); [Matusitz & Payano, 2012](#)), but if track records are anything to consider, then the Bollywood formula has succeeded in creating a multi-billion-dollar industry. This study aims at gauging whether any of that formula derives from the *Natyashastra*.

Bollywood is India

An understanding and awareness of the context within which Bollywood cinema has developed and now exists, is emphasized time and again in this study. The researcher takes such understanding and awareness for granted, being born and raised in India, surrounded by the background noise of Bollywood music, dance and storytelling. However, as this dissertation may be read by an audience without this background and awareness, a short historical overview of Bollywood cinema is included in the [Appendix](#). The overview is intended to be a starting point for further reading in the area and is by no means comprehensive.

Narrative and the Bollywood Style

In comparison to the classic Hollywood style of narrative, the Bollywood film has much more to offer, including an aesthetic mode of production that emphasizes multiple cinematic elements over the flat narrative ([Bharucha, 1998](#); [Gopal & Moorti, 2008](#); [Gopalan, 2002](#); [Prasad, 2003](#)). Lalitha Gopalan ([2002](#)) calls the Bollywood style of filmmaking the “cinema of interruptions,” with its sudden forays into song-and-dance sequences, half-time intervals, and heavy-handed censorship. These interruptions, she contends, produce what one researcher has termed “interrupted pleasures” ([Gopalan, 2002](#)). Using various Bollywood action films as case studies, Gopalan ([2002](#)) contends that these interruptions have more of a pattern than is given

credit for, and assist in the construction of a distinct visual and narrative time-space continuum, providing the filmmaker with opportunity for creativity in narration and personal expression.

One of the problems encountered while discussing the idea of classical narrative styles in the context or ecology of Indian cinema is the meaning of classical. While in the Western context, classical denotes the idea of system, order, discipline, theory, and antiquity of national origin ([Bakhle, 2004](#)), in the Indian context, it has been contended that the word “classical” has no direct or literal synonym, which does not mean that there is no equivalent ([Shah, 2002](#)).

What this instead implies is that the Sanskrit word that comes the closest in meaning:

“*Shastriya*” does not mean classical, but “textual” or coming from the texts or the *Shastras*

([Shah, 2002](#)). Thus, Indian art forms may be considered to be based on the texts, but their

meaning comes from their practice, or their expression ([Prasad, 2008](#)). Another way to look at

the idea of “*Shastriya*” may be to think of it as an external validating force that is established,

and therefore authoritative, and some scholars have pointed out that the *Natyashastra*

specifies this need for “regulation” and authority when it comes to the human creative act

([Prasad, 2008](#)).

There are two modes of narration in Bollywood films: one is the commercial “masala”

film, and the other is the middle or new Indian cinema or “art films” ([Tieber, 2012](#)). The two

modes differ significantly in the way the films are produced, their narratives, and the way the

audience is addressed. It is easy to differentiate between the two modes, and the difference in

the audiences was often the best indicator of the difference in modes ([Tieber, 2012](#)). “*Masala*”

films target mass audiences in India and abroad, whereas parallel or “art films” are usually

showcased at international film festivals in India and abroad ([Tieber, 2012](#)). However, in recent

years, these lines have been blurred, and films that could previously be seen as “art cinema” are now increasingly part of the mainstream. This is evident in films like *Love, Sex aur Dhoka* (2010), *Wake up Sid* (2009), *PK* (2014), *The Lunchbox* (2013), etc. A third category that is less often referred to, would be films made by filmmakers from the Indian diaspora like Gurinder Chadha with *Bend it like Beckham* (2002).

Movies of the silent era in Bollywood could be obviously perceived as directly drawing from the Hindu aesthetic tradition, but the “Talkies” allowed for storytelling techniques from the Islamic, Perso-Arabic tradition and Parsi theatre’s melodrama, turning Bollywood into a truly syncretic mass medium (A. G. Roy, 2010). If the visual medium drew from the visual aesthetic of *Darshana* (divine viewing), and the representation of the mythological narratives of the Hindu epics and stories, the aural aspect of cinema broke through the purely Hindu visual aesthetic to add the Perso-Arabic narrative tradition of *dastan* (part of the oral storytelling literary tradition, a *dastan* is a long narrative, usually in verse or prose, but sometimes involving *sangeet*, or music) or *qissa* (the shorter version of *dastan*; it may be termed a short story in the same tradition), which is an integral part of the romantic tones of popular Hindi film (A. G. Roy, 2010).

The idea of *Darshana* is considered unique to Hinduism. It is a part of the temple experience, an active positive mental and visual engagement with the Divine, in a way that one sees and experiences the Divine (Elgood, 2009). The eye is seen as an active agent, involved in the communication between man and the Divine or the idol (in the temple), and just the act of gazing or “seeing” imparts a part of the Divine to the gazer (Elgood, 2009). *Darshana* is a word from Sanskrit, and literally translates to the “being in the presence (of the Divine).” The idea is

important in all visual arts, as art is divine in the Indian culture, and the eye is the first sense to perceive. In a sense, the idea of *Darshana* merges the physical eye and the inner eye, making the act of “seeing” into something more approaching “perceiving” or “understanding.” While *Darshana* has traditionally been studied in the context of folk theatre, cinema is the ideal medium for *Darshana*, involving seeing as experiencing and understanding. However, Indian cinema, as stated, also borrows from the Perso-Arabic narrative tradition, one that involves *dastan*, or *qissa*, both of which are part not of a visual storytelling tradition, but an oral one ([Elgood, 2009](#)).

The idea of “*Dharma*” is central to understanding storytelling in the Indian context because it is the point where Indian traditions of storytelling combine. “*Dharma*” is an inherent liberal trait in Hinduism, encompassing duty and free will. This is most applicable to the “Hero” in a story, and often sets the direction for the decisions taken by him. “*Dharma*” is a concept in Hinduism that is hard to translate or explain in English, but refers to the idea of a cosmic order that must exist for human development. Kshitij Mohan Sen ([2005](#)) points out that a difference of metaphysical doctrine does not need to prevent the development of an accepted basic code of conduct. “The most important thing about a man is his *Dharma*” (personal ethical code), “not necessarily his religion” ([K. M. Sen, 1961](#)). This ethical code quite often sets the direction for the storyline, as it leads the characters to make choices.

The *Natyashastra* elucidates the various beliefs and traditions associated with the performance arts, which includes drama, music and dance. In this study, drama is examined in some depth in the context of Bollywood film, while music and dance are examined in lesser depth. “Spectacle,” or the aesthetic aspects of drama are also an area of some focus in this

study. For this, it is necessary to know the *Natyashastra*. The following section of the literature review will examine aspects of the *Natyashastra*.

The *Natyashastra* and What It Stands For

The *Vedas* represent sacred knowledge and are the oldest existing texts of India and contain religious and ritual poetry, ritual formulae, some early philosophy, and the explanatory prose interpreting the texts ([Witzel, 2003](#)). The four *Vedas* together (*Rig Veda*, *Sama Veda*, *Yajur Veda* and *Atharva Veda*), are called *Shruthi* (which may be translated as something revealed to or heard by the primordial sages) ([Witzel, 2003](#)). This background is crucial to understanding the context in which the *Natyashastra* comes into existence, for the *Natyashastra* is often considered to be the fifth *Veda* ([Massey, 1992](#)). The text itself states this in no uncertain words, proclaiming itself the *Veda* that is accessible to all, irrespective of social boundaries such as caste or class ([Gupt, 2006](#)).

Among Hindu philosophical schools of thought, the Vedanta school is considered the most popular, and derives its teaching points from three sources or three points of reference, known as a *Prasthanatrayi* (the three starting points): the *Upanishads*, the *Bhagvada Gita*, and the *Brahma Sutras*. The *Upanishads* traditionally include conversations between sages and their students, generally clarifying and interpreting the teachings of the *Vedas* ([Witzel, 2003](#)). In the *Vedanta* tradition, the *Upanishads* are known as the *Shruti Prasthanana* (*shruti*- heard from the Gods). The *Bhagwat Gita*, which needs little introduction, is considered a guide to living, and is known as a *Smriti* text (*smriti* – not of the Gods) ([Witzel, 2003](#)). The *Bhagwat Gita* is a guide to *Dharma*, which is essentially considered the guide to living life. And lastly, the *Brahma Sutras* or the *Vedanta Sutras* are the summaries or attempts to combine the words or the doctrines laid

down in the *Upanishads* and the *Bhagwat Gita*. The word “*sutra*” derives from the Sanskrit word for “thread” and thus the *Brahma Sutras* are attempts to tie the teachings of the *Upanishads* and the *Bhagwat Gita* into doctrines or interpretations that could more easily be taught ([Witzel, 2003](#)).

A claim in the *Natyashastra* states that it borrows from the other *Vedas*: the spoken word (*paatya*) from the *Rig Veda*; the rituals and body-language (*abhinaya*) from the *Yajur Veda*; musical sound and the notes composing music come from the *Sama Veda*; and *Sattvika* (an understanding of the relationship between mind and body-expressions) – for conveying the various *Bhāvas* through expressions exuding grace and charm – from *Atharva Veda* ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). In the first chapter of the text, the unknown author answers the questions of what led to the creation of the fifth *Veda* and for whom was it created. The answer states clearly that the objective of drama or performance is for audiences to realize and understand the goals of human existence: *Dharma* (Duty), *Artha* (Meaning), *Kāma* (Love and carnal pleasures), and *Moksha* (Salvation). This has led to the *Natyashastra* being termed the Fifth *Veda*.

One of the most important parts of the *Natyashastra*, is its description of an aesthetic tradition that may be termed the “*Rasa*” theory ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). This forms the core of the Sanskrit *Natya* (performance) theory. “*Rasa*” which also means “essence” refers to the effect of the performing art on audiences ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Thus, under the Indian aesthetic tradition, every dramatic presentation is aimed at evoking a particular kind of aesthetic experience in the audience. This aesthetic experience is termed as “*Rasa*.” This researcher contends that “*Rasa*” is a combination of both affective and cognitive effects within the audience, from a close reading of translations of the *Natyashastra*.

The *Natyashastra* is considered the oldest and best treatise on Indian dramaturgy ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). And while the authorship of the work has been ascribed to *Bharata Muni* (or the sage *Bharata*), it has been contended by many that “*Bharata*” was simply a name given to an anonymous series of authors of the work ([Gupt, 2006](#); [Massey, 1992](#); [Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The name “*Bharata*” has been said to mean dancer-actor, and the title or name of the *Muni* could simply incorporate the fact that this is a treatise directed at the Dancer-Actor, or the performer ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). It is also generally accepted that there are several versions of the treatise and that it has been revised several times over the centuries since it was first published ([De, 1976](#); [Ghosh, 1967](#); [Gupt, 2006](#)). An examination of the *Natyashastra* has revealed four different styles in which it has been written, showing further evidence of multiple authorship and revision ([De, 1976](#)). The last chapter of the text contains a kind of description of “*Bharata*,” as a maestro or conductor who leads a performance, playing several roles, several instruments and who orchestrates a performance ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). This implies that “*Bharata*” may refer to the producer or director or writer of the play or the performance.

The *Natyashastra* is a comprehensive treatise on theater (*Natya*), which encompasses all forms of performing arts. In the context of Indian performing arts, there remains no clear distinction between the various forms of art, as dance, painting, drama, gesture, and appearance were all forms of creative expression contributing to creating “*Rasa*.” Thus, it is a treatise on poetry, dance, music, and drama, but also includes some tenets for painting, sculpture, and architecture. The one that is considered most comprehensive however, is drama, and the objective of drama is to inform and educate the common man on how to live and become a better person in the way of the Gods ([Gupt, 2006](#)).

The *Natyashastra* takes the form of elaborate dialogues between the unknown author and a group of sages, who seek to understand the *Natya-Veda*. The author then proceeds to present the various facets of drama including its nature, origins, theories, description of the theater, and elements of drama including speech, body-language, gestures, costumes, décor, the state of mind of the performers, and the religious rituals that were incorporated into performance arts. The text in its entirety comprises 5,569 *sutras* or verses spread over thirty-six chapters ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

There has been some debate on the age of the *Natyashastra*. Based on some text analysis, involving meter, vocabulary, and terminology, scholars have ascertained its origins to lie in a period between the fifth century BC and the fourth century BC ([Ghosh, 1967](#); [Gupt, 2006](#); [Rangacharya, 2014](#); [Tarn, 2010](#)). Gupt has pointed that dating the *Natyashastra* or indeed any work on Indian antiquity is virtually impossible to do accurately, given that most written works are mere records of oral histories ([Gupt, 2006](#)). It must always be kept in mind that while these dates may be ascribed to the written version of the *Natyashastra*, there is evidence to suggest that there was an oral version of the treatise in existence before this time ([Kāne, 1971](#)). While the historical dating of the *Natyashastra* is important in its own way, what is more important is perhaps to situate it in context alongside the other aesthetic tradition to which it has been compared: *The Poetics* by Aristotle ([Gupt, 2006](#)). This however is outside the scope of this study.

The version of the *Natyashastra* that is currently accepted and widely read today is a version that derives from its many interpretations and is one ascribed to the scholar *Abhinavagupta* in the 11th century. It is this version that is used in this study. The

Abhinavabharata as it is called, is an “annotated” version of the *Natyashastra*. However, the commentary or the interpretation is provided with the original text, and the commentary or interpretation may be considered a companion volume, to the *Natyashastra*. *Abhinavagupta* interprets the text of the *Natyashastra* on a variety of levels, including conceptual, structural and technical. It is also the only commentary of its kind that has survived and is considered a unified version of previous versions of the treatise ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Ghosh ([1967](#)) also provides an excellent narrative overview of the *Natyashastra* in the 20th century, pointing out how the text has largely remained ignored by the West in terms of study, while still being acknowledged as a comprehensive treatise on drama and the performance arts within India ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

The text in use today is divided into 36 chapters. The first part of the treatise deals with the origins of the *Natya-Veda* (the science of dramatic performance), and the concept of *Anukaran* (imitation of life). Indian theorists have been known to view drama as poetry that can be seen by the eyes ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). The *Natyashastra* clearly demarcates between realism (*Lokadharmi*) and the conventional (*Natyadharmi*). Other researchers state that the *Natyashastra* provides guidelines to freeing realism from the shackles of time and space, representing it on a stage by simplifying or universalizing reality (*Sadharanikaran*), with the aim of creating “oneness” or commonality or unity among the members of the audience present ([Sreenath Nair, 2015](#)). This has led to the communication theory of *Sadharanikaran* ([Adhikary, 2009](#)), which looks at communication between parties as a way to achieve commonality or oneness ([Adhikary, 2009](#)). This idea of the dramatic performance helping to create a feeling of unification in the audience is unique to the *Natyashastra* and bears more scrutiny. Movie theatres, as mentioned before, are areas of communal gatherings to watch films, and it has

been observed that audiences are united in their experience as they consume the medium of film. This has especially been seen in screenings of the cult movie classic, *The Rocky Horror Picture Show* ([1975](#)).

The text begins with a description of the *Natya Veda* (the science of dramatic performance), and the concept of *anukarana* (imitation) of life for dramatic presentation, followed by precise instructions for the construction of the three kinds of theatre buildings and their ritual consecration by a sponsor or a member of royalty ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). The text then moves to techniques of the *Tāṇḍava* dance; instructions for nineteen pre-performance rituals (*Purvaranga*) to invoke the gods, and to please and educate the audience at the same time; the theory of *Rasa*; the definition of *bhāva*; facial expression; hand gestures (single, combined, dance); details of limb movement, including feet; basic steps, standing postures, and positions with weapons; the combination of steps and movement; types of scenic gaits; stage zones and conventions, local theatrical customs; the theory of prosody, Sanskrit recitation, and metrical patterns; examples of metrical patterns; attributes of poetry and figures of speech; *Prākṛit* recitation; modes of addressing and enunciation; ten kinds of plays; the structure of a plot; basic models of scenic representation; stage properties, costumes, and make-up; the role of women in the theater; description of women of easy virtue and amorous men; various representations; elements of the success of the drama; a general description of *Gāndharva* music; types of basic melody and music parts of *pūrvarāṅga*; hollow instruments; the unity of time, stage songs, and their application in female performance; *dhruvā* songs; covered instruments (drums); types of characters; the distribution of roles among actors, and the ideal drama troupe; and the role of drama in society ([Ghosh, 1967](#); [Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Natyashastra* uniquely emphasizes the role of the human body in communication and drama. During a performance, the body is involved in the creation of knowledge, consciousness, and emotion. However, this knowledge transcends the physical, and is a transitory experience, involved in the production of art and cultural artifacts ([Bourdieu, 1984](#)). The *Natyashastra* is about using the body in a transitory experience from the actor in character, using gesture, music, dance, and speech, to a communal performative experience for the audience, from cultural artifacts to a sensory experience. The interpretation of the *Natyashastra* by *Abhinavagupta* states that *Rasa* is the purpose and product of *Natya* (drama), and that *Rasa* is “the beginning and the end, the object and the result, the medium and method, and the discourse and practice of performance” ([Sreenath Nair, 2015](#)). Indian performance studies therefore are attempts to understand, explain and practice the transitive nature of the body in performance using the theory of *Rasa* ([Sreenath Nair, 2015](#)).

Each of the chapters in the *Natyashastra* yields avenues to explore for the examination of film and other performance arts, and this study primarily focuses on establishing a relationship between the *Natyashastra* and contemporary Bollywood cinema. But, it limits itself to only considering some aspects of the *Natyashastra*, Bollywood film, and the entire context within which they function. The aspects of the *Natyashastra* under consideration are described in more detail in Chapter 4, after an explanation of the methodology and reasoning behind this critical analysis.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

The Research Gap

Researchers have found Western theories to be inadequate for examination of Bollywood and have called for a more Indian perspective ([K. J. Kumar, 2011](#)). The *Natyashastra*, an ancient Indian treatise on performance arts and drama, provides some guidelines which may be used to study Indian cinema in a way better suited to understand it within its cultural context. The review of literature on Bollywood reveals that most studies negotiate cultural identity, film and the diaspora through a post-colonial lens. The chosen research method in this study critically analyzes contemporary Bollywood cinema using the *Natyashastra*, and some of the theoretical foundations outlined previously. The review of literature also indicates that there has been no previous work examining the relevance of the Indian aesthetic tradition in the *Natyashastra* to contemporary Bollywood cinema. This work fills this gap using three box-office hit Hindi films as case studies, taking the first steps to developing a critical foundation for examining Indian cinema using a non-western lens.

The Research Paradigm

The creation of the methodology requires identification of a research paradigm. A paradigm may be characterized as an “integrated cluster of substantive concepts, variables and problems attached with corresponding methodological approaches and tools” ([Kuhn, 2012, pp. 32-33](#)) or as a “basic belief system or world view that guides the investigation” ([Lincoln & Guba, 1985, p. 105](#)). A theoretical paradigm also has been defined as a “loose collection of logically held-together assumptions, concepts, and propositions that orient thinking and research”

[\(Bogdan & Biklen, 1998, p. 30\)](#). In simpler terms, a researcher needs to identify the larger purpose of his/her research representing the epistemological, conceptual, and methodological foundations. A research paradigm may be also understood as a framework of beliefs, values and methods within which research takes place. The following section contains explanations of the theoretical and methodological approaches that collectively define the paradigms of this research work.

Qualitative research is generally concerned with understanding and explaining social phenomena, focusing on human behavior, experiences, opinions, and attitudes ([Hancock, Ockleford, & Windridge, 1998](#)). Qualitative research allows for exploring new areas of research that have not yet been completely understood or identified, and for identifying links and patterns between human beings, culture, and other social contexts ([Hancock et al., 1998](#)).

Qualitative research is perfect for exploratory research, to discover new ideas and insights and even to generate new theories and models ([Croker, 2009](#)). Qualitative research methodologies have their roots in multiple disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and philosophy ([Croker, 2009](#)). Qualitative researchers are the primary instruments for data collection and analysis; where data is mediated through the human instrument, rather than through inventories and questionnaires ([Sharan B. Merriam, 1988](#)). They are concerned primarily with process, rather than outcomes or products; they are interested in meaning, and how people make sense of their lives, experiences, and the way they interpret the world; and this means that qualitative research may involve fieldwork and that “meaning is socially constructed by individuals in interaction with their world” ([Sharan B. Merriam, 1988](#); [Sharran B. Merriam & Associates, 2002](#)). “Meaning” thus, is not universal, but changes based on context,

person and time ([Croker, 2009](#)). This form of research is inductive in that the researcher builds abstractions, concepts, hypotheses, and theories from details ([Sharan B. Merriam, 1988](#)). The main difference between qualitative and quantitative research is philosophical, not methodological ([Krauss, 2005](#)).

It may be said that all research directly or indirectly involves participant observation in the selection of a topic, method of study, data collection, analysis and interpretation ([Altheide, 1987](#); [Altheide & Johnson, 1994, 2011](#); [Altheide & Schneider, 2012](#); [Cicourel, 1964](#); [Hammersley & Atkinson, 2007](#); [Johnson, 1975](#)). Qualitative research relies heavily on the researcher's intuition and understanding to identify links and patterns in the data, and on the expression of the particular and essential elements of the setting and the participants, in order to build on themes and to formulate theories ([Croker, 2009](#)). It is also reliant on rigorous observation and the interpretation of the elements detected through observation. This dissertation is qualitative and interpretivist. The interpretative research paradigm or methodology in turn is rooted in hermeneutics and phenomenology, as it takes into account the prior experience and background of the researcher in the field being studied ([Denzin & Lincoln, 2011](#)) but attempts to go beyond mere interpretation to include other underlying structures like social systems and historical backgrounds. The arguments for the use of interpretivism in research have been reiterated by many prior researchers ([Fitzgerald & Howcroft, 1998](#); [A. S. Lee & Liebenau, 1997](#); [Lincoln & Guba, 1985](#); [Walsham, 2006](#)). In the interpretive research paradigm, the researcher joins the participant to create a social reality, to establish knowledge, and to generate rich descriptions ([Jacobson, Gewurtz, & Haydon, 2007](#)). The interpretivist paradigm may be credited to Schutz ([1967](#)), Cicourel and Garfinkel ([2005](#)) (phenomenology/sociology), and the "Chicago

School of Sociology" (sociology), and Boas and Malinowski (anthropology) and developed as a critique of positivism in the social sciences ([Bulmer, 1986](#); [Cicourel, 1964](#); [Garfinkel, 2005](#); [Schutz, 1967](#)). In general, interpretivists share the following beliefs about the nature of knowledge and reality: relativist ontology, which assumes that reality as we know it is constructed inter-subjectively through the meanings and understandings developed socially and experientially; and, transactional or subjectivist epistemology, which assumes that we cannot separate ourselves from what we know.

Lutgendorf ([2006](#)) has classified the study of film into four kinds of approaches: cultural–historical, technological, psychological-mythic and political-economic. This study uses the cultural-historical perspective as one of the approaches to studying Bollywood cinema. This is a paradigm that traces the features of Indian film to older oral and theatrical traditions, which may or may not have survived into modern times. This includes tracing themes and stories within Indian cinema to stories and themes within the Indian epics: namely, the *Ramayana* and the *Mahabharata*.

The myriad perspectives used in the study of film, leave the researcher with a vast repository from which to choose. This study uses a variety of perspectives and approaches in critically viewing Bollywood film. The critical approach was chosen as one of the theoretical approaches after some evaluation of other alternatives. The use of multiple theoretical approaches offers multiple insights that are complementary (though not always). This is particularly true of those based on similar ontological approaches.

In summation, the research paradigm for this study is grounded in interpretivism, and the qualitative method used is a combination of the critical analysis method and the multiple case

study method. The justification for the combination of the use of these two methods lies in their capacity for breadth as well as some depth across the parameters of time and depth. The choice of three films spaced approximately 20 years apart provides for some examination based on historical and social development, and the use of the critical analysis means the application of a variety of lenses in the interpretation of the *Natyashastra* and how it remains relevant to contemporary Bollywood cinema. The choice of research method is justified in the following section, along with a broad overview of the way this study is carried out.

The Research Design

Critical analysis promotes a certain mode of thought and studying of phenomena, based on questioning overt meanings, assumptions and beliefs. Critical analysis is a research methodology where a point of view is presented, along with its advantages, disadvantages and evidence of support ([Knowles & McGloin, 2007](#)). A good critical analysis is able to distinguish between the important and unimportant aspects of the material under study, and to make connections between the materials and the outside world ([Gopee, 2002](#)). The exploratory nature and the research methodology chosen for this study require that it be presented through a variety of theoretical perspectives.

As this study involves some examination of the contents of film, it would perhaps be logical to term this a content analysis. Content analysis entails a systematic reading of a body of texts, images, and symbolic matter, not necessarily from an author's or user's perspective ([Krippendorff, 2012](#)). It is a method used by social scientists to examine human artifacts like newspapers, videos, books, magazines, music, fine art, etc. Content analysis is a flexible method for analyzing textual and visual data, ranging from impressionistic, intuitive, interpretive

analyses to systematic, strict textual analyses ([Rosengren, 1981](#)). However, it has largely been viewed and used as a quantitative method, or a statistical exercise involving categorizations or an analysis of behavior through examining instances of that behavior within the media content under study; this, coupled with its lack of firm definition and procedures has limited its use as a method ([Tesch, 1990](#)). As this study is qualitative and includes more than the content of the film and the *Natyashastra*, the content analysis method was not deemed suitable and was widened to be termed a “critical analysis.”

Critical analysis is a method which involves the close examination of a text. Similar to the method followed in the writing of a literature review, a work is identified, and then critiqued for its relevance or irrelevance, based on specific instances and interpretations. The critical analysis method does not shy away from personal opinion or interpretation. Similarly, this study includes the subjective interpretation of the *Natyashastra* along with a variety of interpretations of its contents through a variety of perspectives, to determine the continued relevance of the ancient text to contemporary Bollywood film. Critical analysis promotes a certain mode of thought and studying of phenomena, based on questioning overt meanings, assumptions and beliefs. Critical analysis is a research methodology where a point of view is presented, along with its advantages, disadvantages and evidence of support ([Knowles & McGloin, 2007](#)). The critical analysis, it must be made clear, has very little to do with the Critical Theory School of Thought that was examined earlier. Instead, it includes an over-arching attitude of critical thinking self-examination with a view to clarify hidden philosophical assumptions, and exploring several creative approaches to fruitful social scientific enquiry ([Yanchar, Gantt, & Clay, 2005](#)). This method of enquiry has much in common with the critical

methodology advocated by Yanchar et al. ([Yanchar et al., 2005](#)), which calls for flexibility of prevailing social scientific methods in a way as to facilitate scientific progress. The flexibility allows for the inclusion of context, intelligent and logical argument construction, critical thought and philosophical analysis, and rhetoric ([Yanchar et al., 2005](#)).

A researcher is able to use a critical analysis to be able to distinguish between the important and unimportant aspects of the material under study, and to make connections between the materials and the outside world ([Gopee, 2002](#)). In a critical analysis, the researcher uses a variety of sources to evaluate and identify relevant information and patterns within the data ([Knowles & McGloin, 2007](#)). Critical analysis requires knowledge of the subject matter, comprehension, application, analysis, and synthesis of the findings ([Knowles & McGloin, 2007](#)).

The case study is a tool that may be combined with another method to understand a system, the boundaries of which are unclear, and are determined by the researcher's interests ([Hood, 2009](#)). The case study has been categorized as being of various types, including, intrinsic, instrumental, and the multiple case study ([Stake, 2005](#)). This work uses the multiple case study method, which involves the study of one issue among several cases, in order for greater understanding and more effective theorizing ([Stake, 2005](#)). While a case may be made that three films make up a very small sample, the method used here does not preclude the use of examples from other films as required, to support the case made. The case study method is most suited to this study as the case study has been defined as an intensive study of a single unit for the purpose of understanding a larger class of (similar) units ([Gerring, 2004](#)). The fewer the cases used in the study, the more data can be gathered from each one. The case study

method allows the researcher to closely examine the data within a specific context ([Zainal, 2007](#)). The multiple case study is conducive to the investigation of contemporary real-life phenomenon through detailed contextual analysis of a limited number of events or conditions, and their relationships ([Campbell, 1979](#); [Zainal, 2007](#)).

Yin ([2013](#)) has noted three categories of case studies: exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory. This is an exploratory study, and exploratory case studies are aimed at exploring phenomena in the data that interest the researcher and consist of general questions that are meant to open the door for further investigation into the phenomena observed ([Zainal, 2007](#)). The case study approach is advantageous in terms of its intrinsic, instrumental, and collective approaches, which allow for qualitative analyses of the data. Case studies also help to explore or describe the data in a real-life environment and to explain the complexities of real-life situations that may not be captured through experimental or survey research ([Zainal, 2007](#)).

Research Question(s)

The purpose of this study is to assess whether the *Natyashastra* remains relevant to Bollywood cinema. This study fulfils this goal through a close critical reading of the *Natyashastra*, examining those parts that are relevant, in context of three Bollywood films. The overarching broad research question is:

Q1. Does the *Natyashastra* continue to inform Bollywood film production?

Sampling

Analyzing media using qualitative critical analysis means that the study examines the relationship between the text and its audience. Media texts are polysemic, or in other words, open to different interpretations ([Carragee, 1990](#)). Critical analysis is a process that is time-

consuming and rigorous, which is why many of the studies done this way have small samples that are largely representative. This researcher has picked the three films for the case studies based on their mass appeal and box office earnings; under the assumption that mass appeal and box office earnings represent that these films are viewed by audiences as exemplary of Bollywood film in general, making them thus most useful as studies for generalization pertaining to Bollywood film more broadly.

The first of the films included in this study is the Hindi film *Sholay* ([1975](#)). *Sholay* is one of Bollywood's most iconic films. It was honored at the 50th Indian Filmfare Awards (in 2005), and termed as India's "biggest entertainer." Even though box office earnings cannot be deemed accurate for a film from 1975, *Sholay* was considered to be India's biggest box office hit until 1995 and ran for many years at a Mumbai movie theatre. The second film use is *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* ([1995](#)). After *Sholay*, this has been considered the longest-running film in theatres. Box office earnings for this film also may not be accurate, and its cult status may be determined mainly using its long run in theatres (1009 weeks at Maratha Mandir in Mumbai) and its passage into popular culture in India ([Goyal, 2015](#)). The other film I include is *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* ([2013](#)). This film has broken all previous box office records (until 2013) and is one of the current highest international grossing Indian films in the last 20 years ([Koimoi.com, 2013](#)). The three films are not alike in theme and story, but they are exemplary in that they are landmark films in terms of their earning potential. But more pertinent to this study is the fact that they are representative of Bollywood films in their era.

Reliability and Validity

Reliable data is data that remains constant throughout variations in the measuring process ([Krippendorff, 2012](#)). As this study is subjective, and is the interpretation of the researcher, it is difficult to address issues of validity and reliability.

Validity concerns truths ([Krippendorff, 2012](#)). Validity tests pit the results of a researcher's claims against evidence obtained independent of that effort ([Krippendorff, 2012](#)). There are several types of validity including face validity, criterion-related validity, construct validity, and content validity ([Krippendorff, 2012](#)). Construct validity refers to how much a test, theory or experiment holds up to its claims. It acknowledges that there are certain concepts within the social sciences that may not be observed directly. In these cases, construct validity is used where the concepts under study are defined by the researcher or are a human-defined construct. This study is stronger on construct validity than any other kind of validity.

As the sample size of this study only includes three films, it may be criticized for not being generalizable. However, this is an exploratory study, and if consistent results are found, further studies including other films replicating this study design could be indicators of generalizability. Attempts will be made to follow this exploratory study with empirical testing that could form the foundations for theory, identifying the parameters for reliability and validity to a much greater extent.

Research Process, Expected Results and Data Analysis

The writing of film theory is generally carried out by exploring abstract questions about the nature of cinema ([Kydd, 2011](#)). The critical analysis method used in this study provides

opportunity to expand the text-based understanding of a film into an interpretation that takes into consideration the ideologies and contexts at work within a film ([Kydd, 2011](#)).

The method of critical analysis has often been pictorially depicted as follows:

The Critical Analysis Process

Figure 1: Graphic Credit: "Critical Analysis Process," (2013) ("Critical Analysis Process," 2013)

The process of critical analysis for this study is to re-read the complete *Natyashastra*. The researcher then describes the chosen chapters in greater depth. This provides context and a basis for evaluation for the content in the films. These notes form the basis for critical analysis by the researcher. A primary element of critical analysis and the case study method is description. Detailed description provides context for the material under review for the reader, helps clarify the writer's understanding, allows the writer to make connections between the

materials being evaluated, and finally, guides the reader through the material under review ([Kydd, 2011](#)). Description, it must be made clear, does not equate solely with summarization. While providing summaries is necessary for this study and others like it, analyses must also include interpretation.

The second step in the analysis is to record detailed summaries and descriptions of the films. The description of the films is detailed enough to provide a basis for evaluation and comparison between the tenets laid down by the *Natyashastra* and the content and presentation of the film. The films are summarized on two levels: the stylistic elements and the content within the film. The third step is to study the notes from the *Natyashastra* alongside the notes and observations from the films. This step serves as the point of data analysis in terms of a study using critical analysis as the method. Putting together the materials and observations from the two earlier steps is perhaps the most exhaustive part of this method. Bollywood films, as mentioned, vary in style within each film, and across films. There is certain to be a lot of material under study.

Each of the films is evaluated as an individual case study. This allows for greater depth of comparison within each film and the tenets in the *Natyashastra*. Having three films also permits an overview evaluation between the three films on one side, and the *Natyashastra* on the other. The evaluation of the three films is presented as three separate critical reflections or case studies: one for each film. These form chapters 4, 5, and 6 respectively. Chapter 7 is a summative conclusion that takes the form of an overview of the earlier critical reflections and presents any findings common to all the films. Conclusions based on the critical analyses are also presented and summarized in this chapter.

This study could be regarded as an exploratory study to evaluate Indian cinema using an Indian text and theory as its base. It is not exhaustive, and it is not a large enough sample to be generalizable, but it is adequate to serve as justification for the foundation of a new theory, which establishes a testable perspective on the relationship between Bollywood film and the *Natyashastra*. More research is necessary in the different aspects covered under the *Natyashastra*, along with larger sample sizes and quantitative approaches, for more conclusive and generalizable results, based upon the theory build by this exploratory study.

Pitfalls, Strengths and Weaknesses of the Research Design

One of the main flaws that could be pointed out in this study is its film sample size. The choice of three films as a research sample actually helps in establishing some kind of standards for reliability. And while the sample size used within this study is small and by no means completely representative of the sheer numbers or variety of Bollywood cinema that is produced, the sample size is common for qualitative research which utilizes the case study method. The films themselves may be considered exemplars and are thus representative of their time, and of Bollywood film in general. Finally, while quantitative research may have some superiority for deductive testing of hypotheses drawn from established theory, qualitative research is superior for initial theory building and provides the necessary flexibility.

While a concern of qualitative research has been the biases of the researcher, which may affect the conclusions of a study, there are some researchers who have argued that the interpretation of the idiosyncrasies of human behavior and societies is strengthened by subjectivity involved in qualitative research ([Peshkin, 1988](#)). This researcher also accepts that there are certain things within this study that may be common knowledge to those within the

Indian culture, but that are exotic to those external to this society. This approach allows this researcher to use insider knowledge of Indian culture and film to bring value to this research study, given that the biases are outlined and acknowledged prior to beginning data collection.

The choice of critical analysis as a method for this study may seem strange to some, and the lack of empirical data may be regarded as a disability in establishing a new theoretical foundation for the interpretation of Bollywood film. However, the method provides the flexibility to draw on multiple critical theories and schools of thought, as well as allowing for personal interpretation. The current research design therefore allows for greater depth of analysis and increases the reliability of the study.

This study and others like it are important for many reasons, most of which were discussed earlier in this dissertation. Indian culture and practices, not to mention the media, are increasingly becoming a part of mainstream global culture, and in the process have become big business. The Indian diaspora has spread to every corner of the planet, and it is valuable to understand a mass medium that has the ability to bring about a sense of community within this diaspora. All of this indicates some need to understand the reason for this popularity and for this mass appeal. This study is intended to be the beginning of something that aids the understanding of a rich and largely under-studied cultural artefact.

CHAPTER 4

A CLOSE READING OF THE NATYASHASTRA

“In it (Natya) there is no exclusive representation of you or of the Gods; for drama is a representation of the state (Bhaavaanikiirtana) of the three worlds.

In it sometimes there is a reference to duty, sometimes to game, sometimes to money, sometimes to peace, and sometimes laughter is found in it, sometimes fight, sometimes love-making and sometimes killing of people.

This teaches duty to those bent on doing their duty, love to those eager for its fulfilment and it chastises those who are ill-bred or unruly, promotes self-restraint, in those who are disciplined, gives courage to cowards, energy to heroic persons, enlightens men of poor intellect and gives wisdom to the learned.

This gives diversions to kings, and firmness (of mind) to persons afflicted with sorrow, and (hints of acquiring) money to those who are for earning it, and it brings composure to persons agitated in mind.

The drama as I have devised it, is a mimicry of actions and conducts of people, which is rich in various emotions, and which depicts different situations. This will relate to actions of men good, bad and indifferent, and will give courage, amusement and happiness as well as counsel to them all.

The drama will thus be instructive to all, through actions and States (Bhāva) depicted in it, and through Sentiments arising out of it.

It will give relief to unlucky persons who are afflicted with sorrow and grief or over work, and will be conducive to observance of duty (dharma) as well as to fame, long life, intellect and general good, and will educate people.

There is no wise maxim, no learning, no art or craft, no device, no action that is not found in the drama (Natya).

Hence I have devised the drama in which meet all the departments of knowledge, different arts and various actions. So, (O daityas) you should not have any anger towards the Gods; for a mimicry of the world with its Seven Divisions (Sapta Dvīpa) has been made a rule of, in the drama.

Stories taken out of Vedic works as well as semi historical tales (Itihāsa) so embellished that they are, capable of giving pleasure, is called drama (Natya).

A mimicry of the exploits of Gods, Asuras, kings as well as house-holders in this world, is called drama.

And when human nature with its joys and sorrows, is depicted by means of Representation through Gestures, and the like (Words, Costume and Temperament) it is called Drama.” ([Ghosh, 1967, pp. 13-14](#))

Drama in the *Natyashastra*

The definition of drama encompasses the representation of the three worlds, the world of the gods, the world of humans, and the world of *asuras* (demons). Drama has purpose; it diverts the mind, provides entertainment, and educates the masses. Storytelling is a big part of drama, and the stories are those of gods, *asuras*, kings and common people. Finally, drama tells these stories using gesture, words, costume and the emotions of people (both performers and spectators). In a nutshell, drama tells the stories of life and all that it has to offer, for the betterment of society and its members. The purpose of art, according to the *Natyashastra* is to educate, to enlighten, and to entertain. Art therefore is a form of mimesis, imitating the actions and emotions of common people, but showing the common person how to aspire to a higher level of existence. The text defines drama as the "mimicry of actions and conduct of people" depicting different situations and rich in emotions ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 15](#)). This is distinct from Aristotle's notion of drama as "imitation of an action," as the Indian perspective is that of an imitation of a situation, making the Indian idea of mimesis more passive. Bharata Muni claims that his guide to drama is based on the practical experience he gained through the direction of *Apsaras* (divine muses), in plays for the entertainment of Gods. In this way, it is conveyed that drama has divine origins ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

If the *Natyashastra* defines drama in India, it is important to know and note that its roots lie deep within Hinduism. Indian traditions, practices, and belief systems all emerge from an ancient foundation of Hinduism, and despite the existence and proliferation of other belief systems and religions in contemporary India, the old foundation may still be seen in contemporary practices. Hinduism is the framework within which *Natyashastra* draws the lines for drama. The researcher is Hindu, and it therefore becomes vital to assume some basic tenets of the researcher's knowledge and understanding of Indian Hinduism practices and beliefs:

1. Hinduism is not strictly prescriptive, and there is no single authoritative text or source on which its practices are based, and this has led to much confusion and flexibility in the way it is practiced and understood ([Leonard, 2013](#)). In this way, it is much a living religion.
2. It consists of an interconnected system of beliefs and practices that permeate most aspects of life in India including politics, law, and social life ([Leonard, 2013](#)). This is known as *parampara* (tradition).

Hinduism is a pervasive collective influence on India and Indians. However, the flexibility it offers to interpretation leaves very little room for the formation of absolutes. With the *Natyashastra* being deeply grounded in Hinduism, it must be understood that the same tenets above hold true to the contents of the *Natyashastra* as well. Bharata, the author, states this explicitly in the text as he says that the rules of drama may change according to the needs of time (*kaala*) and place (*desh*) — leaving room for change and flexibility in interpretation.

Much creative literature from the period c. AD 300-700, became the source of studies of dramaturgy, poetry, and literary theory in the subsequent period ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Some have dated the famous *Natyashastra* by Bharata – the foundational treatise on dance, drama and poetry – to that earlier time, suggesting its catalytic role ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). In fact, a close reading of the *Abhinavbharata* (the surviving annotated text of the *Natyashastra*) reveals it to be perhaps one of the earliest forms of literary criticism in India, exploring the interface between sound and meaning, mood and evocation, some of which are seminal to the discussion on the theory of *Rasa*, where one of the arguments was that the quality of creativity can be related to the manner in which it evokes a reaction ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

In the early days of Hinduism, in the period when the *Natyashastra* is believed to have originated, poetry and prose in Sanskrit were understood to be largely the literature of the elite, the court, the aristocracy, the urban rich, and those associated with such circles. It was the time of Kalidasa – an extraordinary poet and dramatist – whose work augments the prestige of the language and was echoed in many later poetic forms. His play *Abhijnana-shakuntala*, is still regarded as an exemplar in Sanskrit drama by literary critics and has been also widely discussed both in Sanskrit literary theory, and later throughout Europe, for its impact on German Romanticism ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). There was a blaze of creative literature in Sanskrit following Kalidasa, drawing on epic themes or familiar mythical narratives and subject to the religious virtuosity that is characteristic of Indian drama. Plays continued to be romantic comedies in the main, tragic themes being avoided, since the purpose of the theatre was to entertain. The *Mrichchha-katika* (The Little Clay Cart) by Shudraka provides glimpses of urban life. Vishakhadatta chose to dramatize past political events in his *Mudrarakshasha*, a play on

the Mauryan overthrow of the Nanda King, and in *Devi-chandra-gupta*, on the bid for power by Chandragupta II ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The hegemony of Sanskrit was political and cultural and enjoyed the patronage of the elite. But local languages and cultures were not abandoned for the language of the elite. The *Natyashastra* lists a number of languages and dialects, even including some spoken by the members of the lower castes ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Poetry and prose romances were often embellishments of themes familiar from epic and *Purana* legends, and the narrative aspect could be subordinated to the linguistic. Prosody and the technicalities of composition were studied in some detail. Anandavardhana and Abhinavagupta explored some of the ideas first mooted in Bharata's *Natyashastra*, such as the suggestive meaning and sound of words, and the place of poetry in drama ([Thapar, 1990](#)).

One of the texts used for this study is an early translation of the *Natyashastra* based on the *Abhinavabharata*, by Manmohan Ghosh ([1967](#)). Compared to a later translation by Adya Rangacharya ([2014](#)), this text is eminently readable — if a little on the verbose side. It is a detailed instruction manual for the performing arts and for their successful production, including rules for dance, music, and acting. The original *Natyashastra* is in archaic Sanskrit and is divided into 36 chapters, which consists of 5,569 *sutras* or *shlokas*. The text is in the form of elaborate dialogue between “the Sage Bharata” and some *munis* (junior sages). The *munis* ask Bharata questions about *Natya-Veda*, and in response Bharata provides a detailed description of the various facets of drama, including its origins and techniques.

The text begins with a description of the *Natya Veda* (the science of dramatic performance), and the concept of *anukarana* (imitation) of life for dramatic presentation, followed by precise instructions for the construction of the three kinds of theatre buildings and their ritual consecration by a sponsor or a member of royalty ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). The text then moves to techniques of the *Tāṇḍava* dance; instructions for nineteen pre-performance rituals (*Purvaranga*) to invoke the gods, and to please and educate the audience at the same time ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)); the theory of *Rasa*; the definition of *bhāva*; facial expressions; hand gestures (single, combined, dance); details of limb movement, including feet; basic steps, standing postures, and positions with weapons; the combination of steps and movement; types of scenic gaits; stage zones and conventions, local theatrical customs; the theory of prosody, Sanskrit recitation, and metrical patterns; examples of metrical patterns; attributes of poetry and figures of speech; *Prākṛit* recitation; modes of addressing and enunciation; ten kinds of plays; the structure of a plot; basic models of scenic representation; stage properties, costumes, and make-up; the role of women in the theater; description of women of easy virtue and amorous men; various representations; elements of success for drama; a general description of *Gāndharva* music; types of basic melody and music parts of *pūrvaraṅga*; hollow instruments; the unity of time, stage songs, and their application in female performance; *dhruvā* songs; covered instruments (drums); types of characters; the distribution of roles among actors, and the ideal drama troupe; and the role of drama in society ([Ghosh, 1967](#); [Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Natyashastra* uniquely emphasizes the role of the human body in communication and drama. During a performance, the body is involved in the creation of knowledge,

consciousness and emotion. However, this knowledge transcends the physical, and is a transitory experience, involved in the production of art, and cultural artifacts ([Bourdieu, 1984](#)). The *Natyashastra* is about using the body in a transitory experience from the actor in character, using gesture, music, dance and speech; to a communal performative experience for the audience, from cultural artifacts to a sensory experience. The interpretation of the *Natyashastra* by Abhinavagupta states that *Rasa* is the purpose and product of *Natya* (drama), and that *Rasa* is “the beginning and the end, the object and the result, the medium and method, and the discourse and practice of performance” ([Sreenath Nair, 2015, p. 2](#)). Indian performance studies therefore are attempts to understand, explain, and practice the transitive nature of the body in performance through the theory of *Rasa* ([Sreenath Nair, 2015](#)).

The *Natyashastra* uses the metaphor of the seed (*bija*) and the tree as a running motif. This embodies the idea of a multiplicity stemming from a unified entity – a concept that is prominent in Hinduism (e.g. a deity may have many avatars). Bharata describes the universe as a single organism or a primordial source (*bija*) in which there are a multitude of elements that are interrelated (like tree branches, leaves, flowers and fruit) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Similarly, a text is also a composite structure, with each part of the text being a distinct branch, inspired by a single unified source. The *Natyashastra*, congruently elucidates the relationship between the structure of drama, the plot, *Bhāva* and *Rasa*, using the same tree-and-seed motif. “*Just as a tree grows from a seed and flowers and fruits... So the Sentiments (Rasa) are the source (root) of all the states (bhāva), and likewise the states exist (as the source of all the Sentiments)*” ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 107](#)). Bharata appears to suggest theatre is a living organism, more than human, as a tribute and an understanding of the divine.

The idea of “*Natya*” or drama in the Indian context goes beyond drama, dance, or even performance in the Indian context. Instead as the *Natyashastra* states, “A mimicry of the exploits of Gods, the Asuras, kings, as well as of householders in this world, is called drama” ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 16](#)). Drama then, appears to be the narration of stories using different media: music, dance, aesthetics, and speech. The characters of the stories are from divinity, royalty and average people. The stories are those of the people, made by them, performed by them and for an audience of people. Indian drama seems more escapist than western drama; less concerned with realism. Both audience and actor are conscious of this idea of escaping from real life. Drama thus tells “real” stories in a “theatrical” way.

The *Natyashastra* clearly demarcates between realism (*Lokadharmi*) and the conventional (*Natyadharmi*). Other researchers have termed that the *Natyashastra* provides guidelines to freeing realism from the shackles of time and space, representing it on a stage by simplifying or universalizing reality (*Sadharanikaran*), with the aim of creating “oneness” or commonality or unity among the members of the audience present ([Sreenath Nair, 2015](#)). This has led to the communication theory of *Sadharanikaran*, which looks at communication between parties as a way to achieve commonality or oneness ([Adhikary, 2009](#)).

Bharata’s words provide the main function of drama within Indian society: to instruct. While entertainment and diversion are considered other functions of drama, these are clearly indicated to be inferior to instruction. Drama has a social purpose in society. It provides a communal experience wherein there is instruction through entertainment. Similar to the McLuhan’s idea stating the medium is the message ([McLuhan, 1994](#)), drama may be said to be

the medium through which the message is conveyed. So, are the message and drama (as defined in the *Natyashastra*) linked? Yes. Are they inseparable? Yes, or at least according to Bharata it gives every appearance of being a composite thing.

Drama in the Indian tradition is a phenomenon designed to be watched and experienced. It was not about listening. An indicator of this is the use of the word “*preksaka*” in the *Natyashastra*, which means “spectators” or “observers” instead of audience member. According to Ghosh (1967), this indicates the importance of the spectacle for the Indian audience, rather than the importance of the rhetoric. In the context of this study, this becomes important to understand and support. And indeed, it is supported, as often the dialogue and the songs are unintelligible to many, for the simple reason that not everyone is proficient in the language used in the film, but everyone can still watch and experience the moods of the film. And while drama is heavily dependent on dance, song, and instrumental music, all of these are part of influencing the mood (*Rasa*) (Ghosh, 1967). Ghosh (1967) indicates that the emphasis on spectacle in Indian drama may be attributed to how actors improvised lines in performances rather than being dependent on a written script.

Dramatic Success

The theory of *Rasa* is unique to the *Natyashastra* and elucidates how aesthetic enjoyment is evoked within the spectator. This aesthetic enjoyment is ephemeral and transcendental, transporting the spectator into a new state of being, and if the dramatic performance manages to achieve this state within the spectator, it may be considered successful. However, *Rasa* is a hard thing to quantify and qualify, and it appears that the

mysterious author Bharata felt the same. For it is reiterated within the text that *Natya* connects with the spectator to create *Rasa*, using *abhinaya* – or a combination of the body, speech, mind and scene – in four styles, and some regional variations. These are accompanied by dance, song and instrumental music, in a playhouse (specifically designed for dramatic performances to be most effective). And it is the combination of all of these that make up a successful production (or achieve *siddhi*).

While *Rasa* has been studied in some detail by other researchers, the very specific combination of *abhinaya* designed to achieve *siddhi* or success has never been studied – at least never in terms of Bollywood film. The success of drama depended on the way the producers meld together its various aspects, tailored to the audience that was watching it ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Success of drama depended on it appealing to as many people as possible, and can be categorized as being of two kinds: divine (*daivikī*) and mortal (*mānusi*) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Of these, the divine appears to be placed in higher regard and appears to relate to the deeper aspects of dramatic structure and to those spectators from a higher order, i.e. those who were educated and considered cultured ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Meanwhile, the mortal success of drama was more concerned with the superficial aspects of drama, and more “average joe” type spectators. Another interpretation of divine (*daivikī*) and mortal (*mānusi*) success is in the reflection of mortal success in direct audience response, which is seen in the physical and emotional responses of the spectators, for instance, laughter, spending and throwing of money, etc. Divine success is seen as the intervention of fate. If the fates intervene and there is for instance, an event caused by the forces of nature, like an earthquake or flood, or another calamity during the performance, it may be considered divinely cursed.

The notion that a play or a dramatic piece could have mass appeal in the time of the *Natyashastra* is certainly unique. The idea of a mass medium itself was unthinkable given the rudimentary state of technology at the time, as well as the geographical state of India (it wasn't even a united country; it was a collection of disparate kingdoms). Kalidasa is believed to have explained that one of the functions of drama was to appeal to as many people as possible, even though they may all have had differing tastes ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). But it is the *Natyashastra* which explicitly states how this is made possible. This theory of success forms the basis of the notion of “*Rasa*” in Indian drama.

Another factor in success or *siddhi* is *Pravritti*, an aspect of drama that takes into account that audiences differ based on regional differences. The *Natyashastra* categorizes these regional dramatic styles as *Avanti* (North), *DaksiNatya* (South), *Pancali* (West) and *Odhrmagadhi* (East) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Today these styles are most notably seen and studied in terms of Indian dance. There is *Kathak* from the North, *Kuchipudi* and *BharatNatyam* from the South, and *Odissi* from the East. While they all are remarkably similar in themes covered, stories and gestures; regional differences have rendered the interpretations in art to be different. Local costumes and styles are also used in each one. And each region prioritizes a different aspect of drama, including *Bharati* (language), *Sattvati* (emotions), *Kaisiki* (soft tender qualities and gestures) and *Arabhati* (bold and aggressive qualities or gestures) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The latter two may be understood to emphasize either male or female aspects. *Kaisiki* represents female aspects, where *Arabhati* refers to male qualities. Bharata, also says that an actor must be able to know and express these variations according to the region of his audience. This is considered an important factor for success.

Bharata specifies that no formula is ever foolproof enough to guarantee success. The success of drama is dependent on the average spectator. No critic or scholar can possibly predict success based on the edicts in the *Natyashastra* with absolute certainty, but Bharata, in Chapter 27, states that success may be evaluated by making note of the “mistakes” and successes during the performance and within its production ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Given the parameters of success in the *Natyashastra*, could a Bollywood film be successful if it satisfies the requirements? Can success be the result of a formula? The three films in this dissertation will be evaluated based on the parameters for success mentioned in the *Natyashastra*.

The Theory of *Rasa*

Rasa is central to the success of Indian drama. In “*The Sanskrit Drama*,” *Rasa* is described as “a single, ineffable, transcendental joy, but it can be subdivided, not according to its own nature, but according to the [eight] emotions (*Bhāvas*) which evoke it” ([Keith, 1992](#)). Another Indian scholar describes *Rasa* as one of those quintessential words in Sanskrit that sums up a whole philosophy or civilization ([Gokak, 1975](#)). *Rasa* seems to cover a gamut of emotions, and therefore is subject to a variety of interpretation and expression ([Goswamy, 1986](#)). This makes its study especially confusing, as the same word can have multiple meanings, under different contexts. The theory of *Rasa* is contained in the sixth and seventh chapters of the *Natyashastra* (and the *Abhinavabharati*), which are known as the *Rasadhyaya* and *Bhāvaadhyaya* respectively. They provide an overview of the idea of *Rasa* and how it works in drama.

Any discussion of the *Natyashastra* and Indian drama is incomplete without the discussion of *Rasa*. The word “*Rasa*” itself derives from “*rasa*,” meaning sap or juice, or flavor ([Gupt, 2006](#)). Bharata states that *Natya* (or performance) is the imitation of life, wherein the various human emotions have to be dramatically emphasized in such a way that the spectator is able to flavor the portrayed pleasure and pain ([Gupt, 2006](#)). The juice of the fruit is considered to embody its flavor, and it is this flavor that plays on the senses, and it is this flavor that is the word “*Rasa*.” In the *Natyashastra*, this is captured in the phrase, “*vibhāva anubhāva vyabhichari sanyogat Rasanishpattih*” ([Rangacharya, 2014, pp. 54-55](#)). This phrase essentially states that *Rasa*, or aesthetic relish, is produced as a result of the combination of determinants (*vibhāva*), consequents (*anubhāva*), and transitory emotions (*vyabhicharibhāva*) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Thus, *Rasa*, like the taste of food, comes from a combination of a variety of ingredients. Indeed, just as a connoisseur enjoys good food, so also does a person of refinement revel in the well-defined dominant mood (*sthayibhāva*) created by the other *Bhāvas* and *abhinaya* ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The *Natyashastra* states that drama should evoke a “dispassionate delight” in the audience as they watch the depiction of reality on stage through the dramatist’s writing, the actor’s portrayal, and the use of the eight major emotions in a “harmonious spectrum” ([Gupt, 2006](#)).

Rasa is evoked when an emotion is awakened in the audience’s minds in a purposeful manner, and is experienced while the individual is in an detached, but contemplative mood ([Chaudhury, 1965](#)). Emotional reactions are evoked in the audience through representations in performance art, in the form of situation and action, through the use of words in poetry, and words and physical presentation in drama ([Chaudhury, 1965](#)). However, it is assumed that the

audience always understands that the situations, actions, and characters on stage are but mere representations of reality, and thus can be actively enjoyed by the audience, a notion comparable to “the willing suspension of disbelief” in Western theatre ([Chaudhury, 1965](#)). The *Natyashastra* states that the sentiments (*Rasas*) are created through a combination of the psychological states (*Bhāvas*), the histrionic/physical representation, the practices (*Dharmi*), the styles (*Vritti*), local usage (*Pravritti*), success (*Siddhi*), the musical notes (*Swara*), instrumental music (*Ātodya*), songs, and the stage ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

There are eight *Rasas* (*AshtaRasa*): *śṛiṅgāra* (meaning “romance” or “passion”); *hāsyā*, (meaning “comedy” or “laughter”); *karuṇā* (meaning “compassion”); *raudra* (meaning “fury”); *vīra* (meaning “heroism”); *bhayānaka* (meaning “horror”); *bībhatsā* (meaning “revulsion”); and *adbhūta* (meaning “amazement”). These *Rasa* are not mere emotions felt by the audience but are instead states of being evoked by the emotions portrayed in the performance ([Buchta & Schweig, 2010](#)). This would imply that *Rasa* is an emotional response inspired by the *Bhāvas* conveyed to the spectator (the *rasika*) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The word “*bhāva*” on the other hand derives from the Sanskrit word, “*bhu-bhāvati*” which means “to become,” or “to come into existence.” In the words of the *Natyashastra*, “*bhāva*” has a causal quality, and it is both an existential and mental state; loosely translated in English as state of mind, emotional state, or psychological state. This researcher contends it is something more than simply a state of mind, it is more of an experiential state, or a transcendental experience. *Bhāva* can also simply be the emotions presented on stage by the actors. There are three types of *bhāvas*: *sthāyibhāvas* (durable psychological states or stable

emotions); *vyabhicāribhāvas* (transient emotions); and the sāttvika *bhāvas* (the temperamental or psychological state) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

There are eight *sthāyibhāvas*: *rati* (love); *hāsa* (joy); *śoka* (sorrow); *krodha* (anger); *utsāha*, (confidence); *bhaya* (fear); *vismaya* (astonishment) and, *jugupsā* (disgust) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). There are 33 transient emotions or *vyabhicāribhāvas*: *nirveda* (discouragement), *glāni* (weakness), *śāṅkā* (apprehension), *śrama* (weariness), *dainya* (depression), *augrya/ugratā* (cruelty), *cintā* (worry), *trāsa* (fright), *īrṣyā* (jealousy), *asūyā* (envy), *amarṣa* (indignation), *garva* (arrogance), *smṛti* (recollection), *maraṇa* (death), *mada* (intoxication), *supta* (dream state), *nidrā* (sleep), *vibodha* (arousal), *vṛīḍā* (shame), *apasmāra* (fits), *moha* (affection), *mati* (assurance), *alāsātā* (laziness), *ālasya* (indolence), *āvega* (agitation), *tarka* (deliberation), *avahitthā* (dissimulation), *vyādhi* (sickness), *unmāda* (insanity), *viṣāda* (despair), *utsuka* (restlessness/anxiety), *autsukya* (impatience), and *capala* (nervousness) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The eight Sāttvika states are *sthamba* (stasis), *sveda* (discomfort due to heat), *romanča* (thrills), *svarabheda* (change in voice timbre), *kampa* (trembling), *vaivarnya* (facial color change), *asru* (tears), and *pralaya* (fainting) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Of these, the first, the *sthāyibhāvas* may be understood as the general mood of the scene. This mood is created through a combination of the *anubhāvas* (determinants); *vibhāvas*, “catalysts of emotion” (consequents) and the *vyabhicārbhāvas* (complementary psychological states) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

Vibhāvas are the cause (*Karana*) of action, with one *vibhāva* being termed the main cause (*alambana vibhāva*), while the other lesser external *vibhāva* are termed *uddipana vibhāva* ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The emotional reaction caused by the *vibhāvas* is known as the

anubhāva ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). And finally the thirty-three *vyabhicāribhāvas*, are transient emotions that all contribute to creating *sthāyibhāvas*, and ultimately *Rasa* ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). *Sāttvika bhāvas* are the physical manifestation of intense emotion and may be used as *anubhāvas* or *vibhāvas*.

Rasa	Deity/ Colors	Sthayi Bhava	Vibhāva (Determinants)	Anubhāva (Representations)	Vyabhicāri bhāva
<i>Śṛṅgāra</i> (Love)	<i>Vishnu</i> / Light Green	<i>Rati</i> (Affection)	The seasons, garlands, ornaments, enjoyment of the company of beloved ones, music and poetry, and going to the garden and roaming there, etc.	Composure of the eyes and the face, sweet and smiling words, satisfaction and delight, and graceful movements of limbs.	Everything except fright, indolence, cruelty and disgust.
<i>Hāsyā</i> (Joy)	<i>Pramathas</i> / White	<i>Hāsa</i> (Mirth)	Showing unseemly dress or ornament, impudence, greediness, quarrel, defective limb, use of irrelevant words, mentioning of different faults, and similar other things etc.	Throbbing of the lips, the nose and the cheek, opening the eyes wide or contracting them, perspiration, color of the face, and taking hold of the sides. The six types of <i>hasya anubhava</i> are: " <i>smita</i> " (slight smile): slightly blown cheeks, elegant glances, teeth not visible; " <i>hasita</i> " (smile): wide eyes, face and cheeks, teeth slightly visible; " <i>vihasita</i> " (gentle laughter) – laughter suitable to the occasion; slight sweet sound, face	Indolence, dissimulation, drowsiness, sleep, dreaming, insomnia, envy, etc.

				joyful, eyes and cheeks contracted; " <i>upahasita</i> " (laugher of ridicule): expanded nostrils, squinting eyes, shoulder and head bent; " <i>apahasita</i> " (vulgar laugher) – laugher on unsuitable occasion: tears in eyes, shoulders and the head violently shaking; " <i>atihāsita</i> " (excessive laugher) – eyes expanded and tearful, loud and excessive sound, sides covered by hands.	
<i>Karuna</i> (Pathos)	<i>Yama</i> / Grey	<i>Sokā</i> (Sorrow)	Affliction under a curse, separation from dear ones, loss of wealth, death, captivity, flight accidents or any other misfortune, etc.	Shedding tears, lamentation, dryness of the mouth, change of color, drooping limbs, being out of breath, loss of memory etc.	Indifference, laziness, anxiety, yearning, excitement delusion, fainting, sadness, dejection, illness, inactivity, insanity, epilepsy, fear, indolence, death, paralysis, tremor, change of color, weeping, loss of voice, etc.
<i>Raudra</i> (Anger)	<i>Rudra</i> / Red	<i>Krodha</i> (Wrath)	Anger, rape, abuse, insult, untrue allegation, exorcizing, threatening, revengefulness, jealousy etc.	Red eyes, knitting of eyebrows, defiance, biting of the lips, movement of the cheeks, pressing one hand with the other, etc.	Presence of mind, determination, energy, indignation, restlessness, fury, perspiration, trembling, horripilation, choking voice, etc.
<i>Vira</i> (Heroism)	<i>Indra</i> / Yellowish	Utsāha (Vigor)	Presence of mind, perseverance, diplomacy, discipline,	Firmness, patience, heroism, charity, diplomacy, etc.	Contentment, judgement, pride, agitation, energy, determination, indignation,

			military strength, aggressiveness, reputation of might, influence, etc.		remembrance, horripilation, etc.
<i>Bhayānaka</i> (Horror)	<i>Shiva</i> / Blue	<i>Bhaya</i> (Fear)	Hideous noises, sight of ghosts, panic and anxiety due to the cry of] jackals and owls, staying in an empty house or forest, sight of death or captivity of dear ones, or news of it, or discussion about it, etc.	Trembling of the hands and the feet, horripilation, change of color and loss of voice, etc.	Paralysis, perspiration, choking voice, horripilation, trembling, loss of voice, change of color, fear, stupefaction, dejection, agitation, restlessness, inactivity, fear, epilepsy and death.
<i>Bībhatsā</i> (Revulsion)	<i>Kala</i> / Black	<i>Jugupsā</i> (Disgust)	Hearing of unpleasant, offensive, impure and harmful things or seeing them or discussing them, etc.	Stopping movement of all the limbs, narrowing down of the mouth, vomiting, spitting, shaking the limbs [in disgust], etc.	epileptic fit, delusion, agitation, fainting, sickness, death, etc.
<i>Adbutā</i> (Wonder)	<i>Brahma</i> / Yellow	<i>Vismaya</i> (Astonishment)	Sight of heavenly beings or events, attainment of desired objects, entry into a superior mansion, temple, audience hall (<i>sabhā</i>), and seven-storied palace and [seeing] illusory and magical acts etc.	Wide opening of eyes, looking with fixed gaze, horripilation, tears [of joy], perspiration, joy, uttering words of approbation, making gifts, Exclaiming, waving the end of <i>dhoti</i> or <i>sārī</i> , and movement of fingers, etc.	Weeping, paralysis, perspiration choking voice, horripilation, agitation, hurry, inactivity, death

Figure 2 Representation of Rasa

Rasa is only possible through mental perception or imagination, and so all the *vibhāva*, *anubhāva*, and *vyabhicharibhāva*, refer to stage representations of reality, and not reality itself. The *Natyashastra* is quick to note that *Rasa* emerges from art, and not from reality, thereby demarcating reality from mimetic reality ([Gupt, 2006](#)). Thus, the audience could experience the emotions portrayed by the actor on stage, but both actor and spectator remain aware that these emotions are caused by *Natya*. Some theorists have pointed at this as an example of a kind of catharsis, similar to Aristotle's notion of catharsis for the release of emotions in a safe environment ([Gupt, 2006](#)).

The *Abhinavabharata* offers two interpretations of *Rasa*: the first is as a dramatic structural element, and presents the techniques to achieve this; and the second characterizes the impact of *Rasa* on the spectator, and delineates the vital features of this impact ([N. R. Lidova, 2013](#)). In the first, *Rasa* emerges as the natural result of the various production techniques, coming close to the true essence of *bhāva* ([N. R. Lidova, 2013](#)).

Figure 3 The Process of Rasa

The emotions conveyed by the actors that contribute to *Rasa*, include physical expressions or histrionic expression in the form of gestures (*āṅgika*), words (*vācika*), costume and make-up (*āhārya*) and the representation of the Sattva (*sāttvika*). Music (both instrumental and vocal), song, and the stage were also seen to contribute to the success of *Rasa* and as essential parts of *Natya* according to the commentary in Abhinavagupta's notation of the *Natyashastra* (Ghosh, 1967). Performances were either seen to be *lokadharmī* (realistic) or *nāṭyadharmī* (theatrical); and there were four styles of production: *Bhāratī* (verbal), *Sāttvatī*

(*Grand*), *Kaiśikī* (graceful) and *Ārabhaṭī* (energetic). Four distinct geographical/local production styles (*Pravritti*) were also identified: *Āvanti*, *Dākṣinātyā*, *Oḍramāgadhī* and *Pañcālamadhyamā* (Ghosh, 1967). The success of the performance was said to be either *Daivikī* (divine) or *Mānuṣī* (human).

In the preface to the Theory of *Rasa* in Sanskrit Drama, Ramprasad Kavīraj states that the objective of *Abhinaya* (dramatic representation) is *Rasa* (in Misra, 2004). Similarly, Ghosh states that there is no meaningful idea is conveyed if *Rasa* is not evoked in his translation of the *Natyashastra* (Ghosh, 1967). For the purposes of this study, in attempting to answer the broad question as to whether the *Natyashastra* continues to inform the production of contemporary Bollywood cinema, it becomes necessary to ascertain whether the production of *Rasa* is observable in the three films, and how.

Plot and the Structure of Drama

The Indian dramatic tradition is uniquely characterized in its dependence on dance (*nritya*), song (*gita*) and instrumental music (*vadya*). Most of these songs and dances borrowed heavily in terms of symbols from Hindu myths and legends, like the motif of Krishna with his *gopikas*. Films with a recurring tune/refrain may be seen to using the song as a *sutradar* (roughly translated as “indicator” or narrator, if this is a person) to set the tone of a scene. In *Karz* (1980) for instance, the constant use of the refrain of the song “*Ek Hasina Thi*” sets the tone of the scenes that flashback to an earlier time.

What’s equally important to note is how specific *Bhāvas* or emotions are perceived to be more attractive to certain kinds of people (Ghosh, 1967).

“Young people are pleased to see [the presentation of] love, the learned a reference to some [religious or philosophical] doctrine, the seekers after money topics of wealth, and the passionless in topics of liberation.

Heroic persons are always pleased in the Odious and the Terrible Sentiments, personal combats and battles, and the old people in Puranic legends, and tales of virtue. And common women, children and uncultured persons are always delighted with the comic sentiment and remarkable costumes and make-up.” ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 520](#))

Indian dramatists did not think about the unities of time and place in terms of linear movement. The Indian epics, much like many films and folk tales, meander through side stories and time and place, with scarce regard for linear notions of time and place. However, individual acts necessarily had to include incidents that could take place in a single day. The duration between acts however, could span a longer amount of time not to exceed a year. If the time did exceed a year, then a short explanatory scene had to be placed between the two acts ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

Bharata has called plot the “body” of drama ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Indian drama comprises a main plot (*aadhikarika*) and the sub-plot (*prasangika*) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). The *aadhikarika* is concerned with the main hero, where the *prasangika* is concerned with the action of characters other than the hero ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). There are said to be three elements that characterize the movement of the plot: *beej* (seed), *bindu* (drop), *pataka* (action), *prakari* (episode) and *karya* (final action) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The seed is where the plot begins as an idea. It has been described as “that which planted in a small measure, expands in various ways and ends in

fruit ([Rangacharya, 2014, p. 158](#)).” The drop is what keeps the plot going, even when the purpose of the play has still not been disclosed to the audience. It helps in restoring the continuity whenever the hero faces obstacles in the realization of his objective. The episode is the “principal happening which helps the principal plot and is itself treated as a principal incident” ([Rangacharya, 2014, p. 159](#)). However, it does not stand in isolation, but should be linked with the main plot by one or more junctures. The episodic incident is that “the result of which only serves the purpose of the principal plot and which has no continuity of its own” ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The *prakari* deals with characters other than the hero but is vital in the realization of the main objective of the drama. The final action is that which “finally achieves the goal of the principal plot” ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

There are five stages (*Arasthas*) in the development of the plot: *Arambha* (beginning), *Prayatna* (effort), *Praptsambhāva* (prospect of success), *Niyataphalaprapti* (removal of obstacles to attain success) and *Phalaprapti* (attainment of the desired goal) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). While Greek drama began with an entrance by the chorus, Indian drama begins with *Purvaranga* (preliminaries). These are not considered part of drama. The *Purvaranga* is followed by the opening (*Mukha*), the progression (*pratimukha*), the development (*garbha*), the pause (*vinarsa*) and the conclusion (*nirvahana*). These are considered vital stages in the progression of the main plotline ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

However, there are other dramatic devices mentioned by the *Natyashastra* that help in the progression of the sub-plot or fulfill many of the same functions as the Greek chorus. Indian drama consists of anywhere between one and 10 acts, between which any amount of time may

have elapsed. Bharata specifies that the amount of time elapsed must be somehow conveyed to the audience to ensure their understanding and cooperation. This is done using *Arthopakshepakas*, or explanatory scenes ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). These explanatory scenes become necessary occasionally due to the restrictions of time and place in a performance. The five kinds of explanatory scenes are: The Interlude Scene (*praveśaka*), the Informational Speech (*cūlikā*), the Supporting Scene (*viṣkambhaka*), the Transitional Scene (*aṅkāvatāra*), and the Anticipatory Scene (*ānkāmukha*) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

Bharata specifies a number of situations that may not be presented on stage in a single act, specifically, representation of a battle, loss of a kingdom, death, and the siege of a city on stage. In addition, Bharata also forbids the killing of the hero, his flight or capture, or him making a treaty with the enemy. Anger or its pacification, grief, cursing, terrified flight of the hero, a marriage ceremony, and the occurrence of a miracle may also not be represented in a single act ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

The *Natyashastra* states that a *nataka* or drama necessitates both virtue and vice with a view to success. Bollywood cinema has always told stories that spoke to and for the current dominant generation. Plot construction within the *Natyashastra* is vague, at best, and scattered in addition. Thus, the question arises as to whether plot elements in the *Natyashastra* are clearly visible within the films under study.

The Typology of Drama

The typology of drama in the *Natyashastra* is incredibly complex, and in many cases, vague. The typologies overlap, and sometimes contradict. This may be another indication of the development of the text over the centuries and that Bharata is a composite author.

The *Natyashastra* indicates that there are two “natures” (*dharma*) of plays: *Lokadharmi* (realistic) and *Natyadharmi* (dramatic). *Lokadharmi* is a play featuring both men and women, displaying their “true nature,” and without any change (*avikrita*) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). *Natyadharmi* is a play in which speech is artificial and exaggerated, actions unusually emotional, gestures graceful, and the voice and costumes are not seen in everyday life ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). When a well-known theme is dramatized using characters portraying emotions in a dramatic exaggerated fashion, it becomes *Natyadharmi* ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Soliloquies for instance are a part of *Natyadharmi*. Drama, says the *Natyashastra*, must always be produced as *Natyadharmi*, because without bodily gestures there can be no drama.

Western dramatists would not recognize all the ten kinds of plays within the *Natyashastra* as drama. This is primarily due to their unique mode of production, which is based on the four primary styles given in the *Natyashastra* ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). These would consist of the Verbal (*Bharati*), the Grand (*Sattvati*), the Energetic (*Arabhati*), and the Graceful (*Kaisiki*) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Plays using the *Bharati* style use only male characters, are characterized by the preponderant use of speech, and attempt to evoke the *Karuna* and *Adbutā* sentiments ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Plays using the *Sattvika* or Grand style of production depend upon the use of grand gestures and speeches, as well as shows of strength, and the rise of spirits for their success.

They also attempt to evoke the *Vīra*, *Adbutā* and the furious sentiments ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

Performances following the *Arabhati* or Energetic style features a bold person making many exaggerated speeches about their deeds, and practicing deception, and perhaps magic. It is mainly concerned with the *Bībhatsā* and *Raudra* sentiments. The *Kaisiki* or the graceful style emphasizes the gentler emotions to do with *Śrīṅgāra*, *Hāsya*, *Karuna* and *Adbutā Rasas*. It is also more associated with the idea of the feminine.

There are ten main types of plays described in the *Natyashastra*, all of which are differentiated by the number of acts within them. An act in the context of Sanskrit drama cannot present more than a day's events, while a play in its entirety is not bound by such notions of time and place. An act may consist of loosely defined scenes that cannot be separated from one another, but are not entirely fluid ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). An act may also not feature feats of excessive anger, favor and gifts, pronouncing a curse, running away, marriage, a miracle, a battle, the loss of a kingdom, death, and the siege of a city and the like (Ghosh, 1967). It may also not feature the death of the Hero.

The different types of drama are named as follows: *Nataka*, *Samavakara*, *Prakarana*, *Ihamrga*, *Dima*, *Vyayoga*, *Anka*, *Prahasana*, *Bhana* and *Vithi*. In the chapters on gesture and character, Bharata indicates that depending on the construction (*yukti*) of the play, productions are of two types: *Sukumara* and *Aviddha* ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The plays of the *Aviddha* type feature violent movements, cutting, striking, fighting, and magical elements with all the characters in costumes. Most of the characters in the *Aviddha* plays are male but may occasionally be female. *Dima*, *Samavakara*, *Vyayoga* and *Ihamrga* are *Aviddha* plays

([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Gods, demons and *rakshasas* form the main characters in these plays with themes of bravery and violence. However, *Nataka*, *Bhana*, *Prakarana*, *Vithi* and *Anka* are *sukumara* (tender or sensitive) productions ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). In these, the characters are human beings.

Out of these, a *Nataka*, corresponds most closely with what Aristotle described as Tragedy. The *Nataka* features people from the nobility along with stories from mythology, similar to the hero of the Greek tragedy – with one noticeable difference. The stories are not about the fall of the hero. They all are to end with the triumph of the hero. The prime objective of the *Nataka* is to reiterate the divine roles of kings and the gods, and to reaffirm that a celestial order sustains a temporal order, that overall maintains a cosmic balance. Heroes of *Natakas* are uniquely tasked with the maintenance of this cosmic balance.

The *Nataka* has as its theme, a well-known familiar story of a royal sage and his family – with superhuman elements, glory, grandeur, and successful love affairs – with a similarly familiar hero ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). A *Nataka* or *prakarana* consists of between five to ten acts, with all characters leaving the stage at the end of each *Anka* (act) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Prakarana* is a play with between five and ten acts, and where the story, the plot and the hero are all original creations of the author ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). These feature characters who are not from nobility, but may be considered commoners with themes of money, legal issues, honor and love, and have plots with mistaken identities, revenge, theft, and politics ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). *Prakaranas* are almost always supposed to end happily, restoring the karmic (cosmic) order reaffirming the status of its middle-class characters ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

Prakaranas may feature a wide variety of subplots and *Bhāvas*, with interludes between acts whose only purpose is to link them ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Samavakara* is essentially a three-act or three-*Anka* play. However, unlike the idea of a traditional three-act play, the *Samavakara* may comprise three acts that are independent of each other, but bound by one single element, which could be the characters or the theme. The *Samavakara* is exclusively concerned with characters from the divinity or the Gods. The three acts of the play necessarily feature three kinds of deceit, three calamities or disasters and/or three types of *Sringara* (love), and twelve main characters. The *Samavakara* thus emphasizes the idea of a trinity in its aspects. Some researchers have speculated that this is akin to Hindu rituals and that the depiction of a trinity is specific for religious reasons ([N. Lidova, 1994](#)). The three kinds of calamities that may be included are battle or floods due to storm or fire (natural causes) or the siege of a city ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The three kinds of deceit that could lead to joy or sorrow would be a progression of events or fate or the machinations of an enemy ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The three kinds of love to be depicted would be *Dharma* (love arising from duty), *Artha* (love leading to material gain), and *Kāma* (love arising from passion) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Ihamrga* is also a play with less than five acts/*Ankas*, featuring divine characters, featuring the theme of a war that develops due to a woman (much like the *Odyssey*). The male characters must be strong characters, and the story develops as a result of her anger. The themes of the story must feature chaos, excitement, and conflict ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The *Dima* tells a familiar tale of a well-known heroic figure, and features six of the eight *Rasas* (all

except *Sringara* and *Hasya*) in four acts ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The *Vyayoga* features at least one well-known hero (who is a sage) and some other male and female characters, who are not royalty or divinity. There will be battles, fights, and conflicts, and the *Vyayoga* has only one act, which means all of the events featured take place over the period of 24 hours ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Anka* or the *Utsrstikanka* is a play featuring a well-known (non-divine) human being, predominantly featuring the *Karuna* (compassion) *Rasa*, and a lot of “female lamentation.” While the play is predominantly tragic in tone, it always features the rise and victory of the hero ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The *Prahasana* may be divided in two categories: *Suddha* (pure) and *Sankirna* (mixed). The *suddha* type is generally a satire on *gurus* (teachers), ascetics, Buddhist monks, and learned Brahmins; using actors clad in garb of “low” characters, wearing everyday dress and speaking in the language of the commoners. The speech and gestures are spontaneous and natural, if exaggerated ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The *sankirna prahasna* type of drama featuring courtesans, menial servants, eunuchs, rogues, and gallants appearing in immodest dress, who can be “obscene” ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). *Prahasana* uses news or popular scandal or gossip as the subject of its satire.

The *Bhana* is a solo single-act play. Perhaps the closest thing to this is stand-up comedy in the contemporary world, but this differs in the sense that the *Bhana* is supposed to use a lot of movement on stage. The material used comes from the actor’s own experience or that of

someone else. If it is about someone else's experiences, then the play must be in the form of a dialogue in which the actor plays both parts ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

Finally, the *Vithi* is also a one-act play featuring human characters of high, middle or low class and any or all the *Rasas*. A *Vithi* has 13 distinct features: *Udghatya* (when one character uses a difficult word and another person explains it); *Avalagita* (when a character's desire is fulfilled, but serves an entirely different purpose); *Avaspanidita* (a comment made has an intentional double meaning); *Asatpralapa* (when an irrelevant question receives an irrelevant response); *Prapanca* (when a snide remark is made under the guise of praise, causing laughter); *Nalika* (a riddle that incites laughter); *Vakkeli* (when witty repartee creates laughter); *Adhibala* (when a boast is called out as an exaggeration); *Chala* (when a compliment is actually snide); *Vyahara* (when an action is forced without giving rise to suspicion in the presence of the hero); *Mrdava* (when perceived faults are revealed to be virtues and vice versa); *Trigata* (when grandiose speech is actually comic and enjoyed by the other characters); and, *Ganda* (when a series of errors due to confusion, excitement, or misunderstanding lead to an unexpected situation) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

The typology for drama is detailed. Each of the types of plays features more than one style of drama (the Verbal, the Grand, the Energetic and the Graceful) and usually prioritizes one style over others, which in turn marks the play as being romantic, or violent or comic ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Thus, the typology of drama, the style used and emphasized, and *Rasa* are all closely connected. It does not seem to be a stretch to think that a single film can fit neatly into just one of these categories either, and in the course of the study, it is to be hoped that the

three films will have elements of one or more of these types. So, the question that arises here is: Can the typology of drama be seen within examples of Indian cinema?

Miscellaneous Elements

While the *Natyashastra* states that *Rasa* is achieved through the depiction of stable emotions, these emotions are expressed in *Natya* through *angika abhinaya* (bodily expression), *vacika abhinaya* (linguistic expression), *abarya abhinaya* (costumes of the characters and stage decoration), and *sattvika abhinaya* (voluntary changes expressed by the presence of tears, mark of excitement, change of facial color, trembling of lips, enhancing of nostrils) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

It has been reiterated there are certain elements of drama that remain unique to Indian drama. These are detailed in the *Natyashastra*.

Dance. The *Natyashastra* distinguishes between *Natya* (translated to drama), *nritta* and *nritya*. All three words find their roots in the Sanskrit word *nrt*, meaning “to dance.” *Nritta* is explained to be dance that does not convey emotion (or *bhāva*), but is instead just present for the purpose of creating beauty through the use of patterned delicate gestures ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). *Nritya* on the other hand refers to dance in which every gesture and movement has the intent to convey meaning and emotion ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). *Nritya* has two forms: *Desi* and *Marga*. *Desi* is the kind of dance performance that is presented for the entertainment of royalty, and *Marga* is the kind of dance performance accompanied by music.

However, in response to a question on the purpose of dance within drama, Bharata replies:

“It is not related to the meaning of a song nor does it convey the meaning of words. My reply to this, says Bharata, is as follows — true, nritta conveys no meaning, but it creates beauty (attraction) to the performance. It is also considered to be auspicious. It is also a diversion.” ([Rangacharya, 2014, p. 35](#))

All of this appears to point to the use of dance as something that serves the purpose of diversion within drama, but mainly to enhance the mood – even if the gestures and movements have no intended meaning. The only exception is if the dance is dedicated to a God (e.g. Tandava).

Purvaranga. These refer to the preliminaries that are meant to be placed before the enactment of any dramatic performance. Mainly, the preliminaries are intended to invoke the Gods for a successful performance. However, Bharata has provided detailed instructions on the 20 constituent parts of the *purvaranga*, of which the first nine are done backstage, while the other eleven are done on stage for the audience to behold ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

While instructions for the *purvaranga* are quite detailed, it is not a part of the play, and Bharata states explicitly that the dance, song and instrumental music in the introduction should not be too long or so elaborate that the audience loses patience and the performers lose their enthusiasm or feel anxious for the delay. Bharata also implies that a long and elaborate *purvaranga* would detract from the overall impact of the performance.

Thus, the *purvaranga* deals with the ceremonies and conventions that are performed prior to the staging of the play. Today, some or most Indian films still have some semblance of an invocation to the gods before the film.

This chapter has looked at the *Natyashastra* and how it may apply in the evaluation of Bollywood film. Elements within the *Natyashastra* have been identified and explained. The next part of this dissertation will entail looking for these elements within the films chosen and will attempt to answer the questions raised within this chapter.

CHAPTER 5

SHOLAY (1975)

Overview

“The greatest Hindi film of all time.” ([Dwyer, 2002, p. 218](#))

Director Shekhar Kapur perhaps expressed it best, “There has never been a more defining film on the Indian screen. Indian film history can be divided into *Sholay* BC and *Sholay* AD ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). *Sholay* is regarded as the greatest Hindi film of all time, the quintessential Bollywood film. It was also India’s first 70-mm format film with stereophonic sound ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). But, what is odd is, *Sholay* is not an original – neither in plot nor in story. Known now as a “curry western” because of its borrowing from the conventions of Hollywood Westerns and customized to appeal to the Indian palate, *Sholay* is a tenuous remake of Akira Kurosawa’s *Seven Samurai* ([1954](#)), a classic Japanese film ([Pandya, 2007](#)). But, *Sholay* is not a copy; it’s not even technically a remake, but in a broader sense it may be seen as intertextuality ([Chauhan, 2015](#)).

Sholay is a film that appeals to “everyone” and is a good choice to introduce someone to Bollywood film because it requires no cultural explanation ([Dwyer, 2002](#)). Perhaps true, perhaps not, the film does have something in it for everyone: action sequences, guns, picturesque locations, horses, romance, tragedy, and comedy. Its appeal cuts across barriers of geography, language, ideology, and class: an advertising guru in Mumbai will speak as enthusiastically and eloquently about the film as a rickshaw driver in Hyderabad ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). In the context of this study, *Sholay* appears to have uncovered the magic formula of success. The film appeals to Indian mass audiences, and those abroad, needs no

translation, and is quintessentially Indian. Chopra ([2000](#)) states that *Sholay* is “no longer just a film, but an event,” while commenting on the film’s cult status.

Sholay has no rivals at the box office, and certainly no other film in Indian cinema can claim its iconic status. The film collected approximately ₹350,000,000 in its first run in India, and to put things in perspective, the other top film released that same year *Jai Santoshi Ma* ([1975](#)), the religion-based cult classic of 1975, grossed approximately ₹60,000,000 ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). One hundred and ninety prints of *Sholay* were made in the first year, while Polydor Music sold over 500,000 records and cassettes, jacking up the ₹100,000,000 music market (at the time) by fifty percent on the dialogue sales alone ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). However, assessments of the size and worth of *Sholay*’s box office figures are difficult to quantify in today’s terms due to inflation, currency rates and conversion.

Mumbai’s iconic Minerva Cinema played the film for five consecutive years after the film was released in 1975. *Sholay* still tops fan and critics’ polls, and Filmfare magazine named it the “Best Film of the last 50 years” in 2005, and *TimeOut* magazine placed it at no. 1 in its 100 Best Bollywood Movies in 2015 ([Verma, 2015](#)). Nothing in Indian popular culture has ever matched its magic. Some critics have argued that *Mother India* ([1957](#)) or *Mughal-e-Azam* ([1960](#)) were better films, and others have pointed out that *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun* ([1994](#)) in 1994 broke *Sholay*’s box office records, but none of these films have matched *Sholay* in the scale and longevity of its success — *Sholay* was a landmark event ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)).

The film is ubiquitous in Indian popular culture. Kitschy Bollywood souvenirs often borrow from its dialogues and its characters, with the villain in the film Gabbar Singh being

termed “the most iconic film villain” ([Hashmi, 2013](#)). *Sholay* has also been remarked upon for a variety of reasons including its symbolism as a national allegory ([Dissanayake, 1993](#)), Indianisation of the Western ([Dissanayake & Sahai, 1992](#)), homoeroticism and friendship. *Sholay* is, as director Dharmesh Darshan says, ‘part of our heritage as Indians’ ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)).

So why is *Sholay* considered quintessentially Indian?

According to Dudrah, *Sholay* is the ultimate Bollywood film because it has all the spices necessary for a film, including drama, melodrama, romance, action, and family, in the perfect blend ([in Verma, 2015](#)). More importantly Dudrah sees the Indian Nation in the film, with its themes of law and order, all of which he says reflect the nation’s collective anxiety about one of the most controversial times in Indian history — the Emergency between 1975 and 1977. “The setting in the fictitious village of Ramgarh, referencing the lawless Wild West and paying homage to American and Italian westerns, is not by accident. Nor is the situation of the law enforcer who must step outside of the law to get justice,” explained Dudrah ([in Verma, 2015](#)).

The film has certainly aged well, blending traditional Indian motifs and modern elements. It has, as author Nasreen Munni Kabir said, “Differences in lifestyles which co-exist without appearing illogical” ([in Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). The steam engines, the horses, the guns, and the denim imbibe the film with an ageless quality — a feeling of several centuries juxtaposed on screen. The only things missing are computers and cellphones. Even the characters – Veeru, Jai, Gabbar, Thakur, Basanti, and Radha – are familiar in the way of

characters in the great epics of the *Mahabharata* and the *Ramayana*. The peripheral players Soorma Bhopali, the Jailer, Kaalia, and Sambha – are the stuff of folklore.

Mukherjee (2014) says that “curry westerns” such as *Sholay* underline the waves of political change, separating themselves from traditional westerns, in that they addressed the iconicity of the “barren landscape,” and despite displaying the same harshness, betrayal and a demonic villain as spaghetti westerns, included and emphasized codes of honor, kinship, friendship, and personal vendetta in a way that was uniquely Indian.

However, *Sholay* is not without its critics. Desai (2015) views *Sholay* as a film with:

“No grand theme running underneath the narrative, no archetypal conflict that satisfies deeper psychological needs, and little by way of any re-assertion of dearly held cultural truths that might be under attack. As compared to typical Hindi films, there are no family values that are sought to be upheld, no way of life to be defended, no societal order that needs to be restored. There is no ‘ma’ in the film- there is a ‘mausi’, of course, but she is used to contrive humour rather than pathos. At an unconscious level too, unlike the psychic underpinnings of the ‘lost-and-found’ films of the time or the embroiled emotional complexity of the ‘mother-son’ sagas, not very much happens.” (S. Desai, 2015, Para. 4)

He adds that while *Sholay* is a film with a lot of powerful emotion, none of it is tethered to the larger issues that Indian films have dealt with. Instead, *Sholay* depicts emotions at the individual level (*dosti*-friendship, *dushmani*-enmity, *badla*-revenge), rather than at the

collective conscious level (*izzat*-personal dignity/status, *sanskar* – traditional values, *mamta* – a mother's love) ([S. Desai, 2015](#)).

This researcher would not agree. Instead *Sholay* was in many ways an attempt to give power and inspire revolution among an audience that was increasingly feeling powerless and restless. The film dealt with the machinations of power and the effects of oppression and fear. And, it packaged all of this in an experimentally slick package. The saccharine romances of rich kids, and the family dramas being churned out had very little to do with their real lives. The prevailing mood in the 1970s was one of hopelessness and frustration, and the events of Indira Gandhi's trial and the subsequent Emergency led to anger, and a new morality was taking shape, typified by Jayaprakash Narayan's socialist movement. The Emergency even had its own direct influence on the film's release, as the Censor Board insisted the ending be changed because they were said to be worried about showing an already angry audience a positive consequence of taking the law into one's own hands ([Verma, 2015](#)). The film's intended ending was only released with the Director's cut in 1990.

***Sholay* Synopsis**

Former police sheriff Thakur Baldev Singh (Sanjeev Kumar) asks a former colleague to help him track down two petty criminals he had arrested previously, Veeru (Dharmendra) and Jai (Amitabh Bachchan) — who are also best friends — to help him avenge the death of his family. A flashback sequence shows first the encounter between the three on a train. Jai and Veeru had helped the sheriff defend the train against bandits who had attempted to attack the railway. The Thakur explains that the two men are ideal to help him in his vendetta against

Gabbar Singh (Amjad Khan) despite their criminal backgrounds, and mostly because of their inherent honorable natures.

Jai and Veeru come to Ramgarh, to be told by Thakur that in exchange for their help capturing Gabbar, they will receive ₹20,000 and get to collect the official bounty on Gabbar's head (₹50,000). The two agree to the terms. The following day some of Gabbar's goons arrive in the area to collect the villagers' "tribute" in exchange for "protection." Jai and Veeru intercede, and the goons leave empty-handed, but spewing threats.

The goons go back and are questioned about the incident. Gabbar engages in a game of Russian Roulette with the three men, and all the men survive. Gabbar begins to laugh psychotically, and so do the rest of his men. The three goons from the village laugh as well. Suddenly, Gabbar stops laughing and shoots and kills the three men. Gabbar voices his plan to attack the village again on Holi.

On Holi, the attack is more vicious, and Jai and Veeru are captured and left vulnerable. The Thakur appears to have the opportunity to throw them a gun but doesn't. Jai and Veeru escape with the help of some quick thinking, and Basanti, the chatterbox horse-taxi driver (Hema Malini). The dynamic duo declares their disgust with the Thakur's cowardice and states their intention to leave Ramgarh. Before they can leave, the Thakur tells them why he wants Gabbar brought to him, and why he couldn't throw them the gun.

A flashback shows how first the Thakur had captured and jailed Gabbar, who manages to get out on a technicality. When Gabbar is released, he kills the Thakur's entire family in cold blood, including Thakur's two sons, daughter, daughter-in-law and grandson. The only survivor

is the younger daughter-in-law, Radha (Jaya Bachchan). Thakur goes after Gabbar in a rage, but Gabbar overpowers him and tortures him. Gabbar then grabs two swords and approaches Thakur. The famous lines, "*Yeh Haath Mujhe de*" (Give me these hands/arms) are heard, and we see nothing more, but learn the Thakur has no arms. This is why he needs Jai and Veeru, and this is why he has not thrown them the gun during the attack that day.

A series of snippets from village life follow. Jai and Veeru get to know the villagers. Veeru falls in love with Basanti, the horse-cart taxi driver, who is outspoken and vivacious, but pure of heart, mind and body. Jai is subtly attracted to Radha, a sorrowful young widow, clad in all white. She is just as drawn to him. The audience learns of her past as a carefree young girl. The audience also learns that the Thakur has asked her father for permission for remarriage to Jai. The blind imam (Hangal) and his son Ahmed (Sachin), who finds a job in another city, also feature in the film.

Ahmed is finally convinced to take the job and sets off on his horse. His corpse returns to the village set atop the horse and is placed gently on the ground by Jai and Veeru. This is the catalyst for the climax of the film. Gabbar's message is a threat: Jai and Veeru or the same fate as Ahmed for the rest of the villagers. The villagers want to give in to Gabbar for fear of their children's lives, but the blind imam convinces them otherwise.

Jai and Veeru send a message back to Gabbar. For each dead villager, four of Gabbar's men will die. Gabbar is enraged. Basanti and Veeru are captured. Jai manages to get through Gabbar's defenses and helps save his friends. He insists Veeru and Basanti leave him to go for

help, while he holds the position. Jai is actually grievously injured. He dies in Veeru's arms later. Radha is on the scene, and once more she endures a romantic loss.

Veeru finds out the coin used in each one of the coin-tosses in the film (the duo uses these to make their joint decisions) is a double-headed coin. Jai had manipulated every incident to his favor, including his death. Veeru is touched and angered by his loss, and vows to avenge his friend's death. He does catch up to Gabbar, and beats him up, but just as he is about to kill him, the Thakur reminds him of his vow to hand him over alive.

The Thakur reveals steel spiked sandals, which he uses to stomp Gabbar to near-death (another later-released ending shows that he loses the use of his arms, thus the Thakur has leveled the field. He then shoves Gabbar into a pointy nail and kills him). The police arrive and take Gabbar away to be tried under law.

Jai's funeral pyre is shown, with Radha watching from inside the house in the shadows. Veeru is all set to leave the village alone by train but finds Basanti in the train with him. They leave together.

Sholay and the Natyashastra

The excerpt of the *Natyashastra* at the start of the previous chapter encapsulates the essence of the text. And it is clear that *Sholay* has much in common with it.

"In it sometimes there is a reference to duty, sometimes to game, sometimes to money, sometimes to peace, and sometimes laughter is found in it, sometimes fight, sometimes love-making and sometimes killing of people ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 14](#))"

There's something, or someone, for everyone within the film.

Dramatic Success, the *Natyashastra* and *Sholay*

One of the main criteria for dramatic success vis-a-vis the *Natyashastra* is that the dramatic performance appeal to as many people as possible. *Sholay* has clearly achieved this kind of success, given its indications of mass appeal, including its success at the box office, its place in contemporary popular culture, and even the attempts to remake the film.

Contrary to Desai's criticism of the film ([2015](#)), in *Sholay*, there is much about duty: the young man, Ahmed takes the job in the city at the insistence of his father, even as he is torn between staying and caring for him, and leaving to be able to earn more money to care for him better. There is Basanti's aunt, who takes her orphaned niece in, cares for her, and feels it her duty to find her a suitable husband. There is the motif of the coin toss woven through the film, signifying the games of chance that people play with their own lives. There is the motivation of money, which is the initial reason Jai and Veeru come to the village and decide to work for the Thakur. The money also shows the difference between Jai and Veeru, who are mere thieves and warrant a reward of ₹1000 per head, and Gabbar who has a reward of ₹50,000 on him – this underlines his cruelty and brutality. There is the mention of peace, which is what everyone wants in the village. There is laughter thanks to the comic devices of the small-time businessman Soorma Bhopali, the Hitler-parodying Jailer, and Veeru and Basanti's love story. There is a lot of fighting, some covert flirting between the couples in the film, a highly sexualized song (the famously sultry Helen who features in the song *Mehbooba, Mehbooba*), and death. Thus, while many of the themes are dealt with on an "individual level" ([S. Desai,](#)

[2015](#)), the individual characters may stand in for themes tethered to the larger issues that Indian films have dealt with.

A part of mass appeal, the *Natyashastra* says is in a dramatic piece appealing to people from many regions. There are many curious ways in which *Sholay* has managed this. Dacoits (armed robbers) are usually identified with the Chambal region, in central India. However, the landscape, which is almost its own character in the film, is actually located in South India in Tamil Nadu. While the actors Dharmendra, Amjad Khan, and Amitabh Bachchan are originally from Northern India, Hema Malini is from the South, Jaya Bachchan is Bengali, and Sanjeev Kumar is from Gujarat. Thus, the film's cast spans every major geographical direction. Hema Malini is in reality a trained *Bharatnatyam* dancer, and her movements are clearly indicative of her classical training.

Natya uses *Rasa*, which in turn is created using *abhinaya*, a combination of the body, speech, mind and scene, and accompanied by dance, song and instrumental music, in a playhouse (specifically designed for dramatic performances to be most effective). A large part of the film's success may also be attributed to its sound and music ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#); [M. Mukherjee, 2014](#)), and the overall cinematic experience of the film. It was a film before the time of home video, and the only way to experience a newly-released film was in the theatre. *Sholay* was the first film adapted to a 70 mm wide screen format with stereophonic sound. This created a whole new experience for audiences that saw the film in the theatre, positioned as they were to almost feel like they were part of the action, surrounded by the cinematic sound. In its time, *Sholay* was one of the most extravagantly produced films with its 70 mm prints, intensely choreographed fight and chase sequences, gun fights, stereophonic sound,

individualized sounds for each character, and sound designed specifically for the film (rather than stock sounds) ([Prasad, 1998](#)). The latter changed the way film sounds were done forever, and the sound of the coin being flipped and tossed, as well as Gabbar's "tune" became ubiquitous ([Prasad, 1998](#)). If this is considered in the context of the formula for success in which many things contribute to the overall communal dramatic experience of the audience, then it's clear that sound, music and video format were big factors in the film's success. Sound especially is used to create much of the impact within the film, including: introducing characters, depicting death and tragedy, and continually identifying characters.

Thus, in the larger question of whether there is a formula for success for cinema, *Sholay* at least, found its success through a combination of the familiar, presented in a unique format. The "spaghetti western," film made by a Japanese filmmaker, that inspired the making of the first "curry western" is incomparable, but *Sholay* resonated with audiences, who could identify with the characters, yet loved them for their eccentricities, danced to the music, and incorporated the dialogue into their daily lives. Audiences embraced the experience of watching the film on the big screen, gasping aloud when Thakur loses his arms, and crying together when Jai dies.

What all of this does in fact, is answer that first question: Is success the result of a formula? And the answer is yes. both yes, and no. In addition to the *Natyashastra* formula identified above, *Sholay's* success lies also in its mass appeal, and its use of the latest technologies in its making (widescreen format and Dolby sound). But, it also lies in its use of star power, the unique endeavor of combining a western with a masala Hindi film, and the unique appeal of its characterization.

Rasa and Sholay

Success may be the result of a formula, or it may lie in the creation of *Rasa* among spectators. Providing evidence of the existence of the creation of *Rasa* is not an easy task. Audiences are made up of individuals. When Ahmed's body is seen lifelessly bouncing on the horse, when Gabbar says "*Yeh Haath Mujhe De Thakur*" (Give me these hands, Thakur) and swings those swords; a chill runs down this researcher's spine. *Sholay*, as has been mentioned before, has been loved by mass audiences and has stood the test of time. And the reason, probably, for this is the evocation of emotion, or *Rasa* among these audiences.

In the opening sequence of the film, Ramlal guides the jailer to Thakur's house. Even as the two ride to the house, the landscape looms large in the background. This landscape plays a major role in the film, from the songs to the title credits, because it evokes the aridity, the heat, and the passion of those who live in these kinds of harsh landscapes. The sunlight in the scenes is blinding; the ground is dry (depicting the scarcity of water); and the ground looks golden, full of potential but hard to look at and work on. According to the *Natyashastra*, the color of gold/yellow creates wonder in the mind of the beholder. There is potential in that land, as any Indian farmer knows; but all victories are hard won.

Later in the film, the Thakur reminisces about the way he first encounters Jai and Veeru (*Sholay*, 0:07:00 – 0:17.35). Here, the landscape features again, alongside the Thakur (as a policeman) fighting bandits with Jai and Veeru on a train. Here, the landscape, and the glowing coals (*Sholay*) that Veeru flings into the furnace are in stark contrast. The red embers glow with a ferocity, a passion, that is matched by the Thakur and the two convicts with him, as they fight against the landscape and the bandits who emerge from it, trying to cow those who love the

land and work on it. Thakurs are traditionally landowners, and the irony of the Thakur being a landowner and policeman who fights against bandits is not lost. The Thakur's duty is to the people who work and live on the land, and they in turn provide for him and take care of him, all of which are shown in the film. The loyalties of the Thakur and the villagers are intertwined, as are their fortunes. Spectators of the film are aware of the bourgeois relationships that exist between the landed gentry and those who work for them. Thus, these depictions on screen resonate with spectators, and they in turn respond to and identify with the characters.

Rasa theory includes the depiction of love. And, three kinds of love are illustrated in three consecutive tableaux. First, the blind imam, his son, and Basanti have a conversation about Ahmed finding a job in the city. Ahmed refuses to leave his blind father, in a touching tribute to filial love. Ahmed sacrifices his own career and wants to be secondary to his father's needs (*Sholay*, 0:55:00 – 0:56:12). Then we see Basanti flirt with Veeru. Under the guise of teaching her how to shoot a gun, he manages to steal an embrace. Basanti is the picture of outrage and then accuses Veeru of thinking her a village simpleton who doesn't recognize an opportunist when she sees one and leaves. Their love affair is comic, and playful (0:56:12 – 1:01:30). Soon after, we see Jai and Radha at dusk. Radha is dousing the lamps for the night, as Jai sits on the stoop and plays a sorrowful dirge. The scene foreshadows the way their relationship ends (1:01:30 – 1:03:10). Even the names of the characters are significant, Basanti, who is effervescent and sprightly, gets her name from the season Spring; Radha, the widow gets her name from one of Hindu Mythology's most one-sided love couples: Radha-Krishna. In her actions with lighting the lamps, Radha epitomizes *Karuna*, which is the disinterestedness or indifference consequent to curses, misery, separation from loved persons, loss of wealth,

murder, imprisonment, etc. *Karuna Rasa* is produced by seeing dear ones die (or killed) and by hearing unpleasant things. It is to be acted out by weeping, fainting, lamenting, and crying and also by physical fatigue and hurt.

What we see in these instances is exactly the way *Rasa* is evoked. Through *Karuna* (compassion) for the Imam, Jai and Radha, we eventually feel *Shoka* (sorrow or sympathy) for the characters. Through *Śṛīṅāra* (passion) and *Hāsya* (comedy) in Basanti and Veeru's exchange, the audience feels delight and laughs at their playful flirtation. Jai's name, a metaphor for victory, is symbolic where, in his death, there is a victory of good over evil, the ultimate victory in all Hindu mythology.

Gabbar's anger and the way he treats his allies in anger, angers the audience with him. The horror of Ahmed's death makes the audience fearful for the fate of the other villagers. When the wind blows away the Thakur's shawl and it is seen he has no arms, there is disgust and horror in the audience. When Jai dies, the audience as one is inspired. The ending of the film brings resolution and justice. There is balance.

The film's box-office success may be also considered a measure of how it is effective in evoking emotion in the audience. Even the actors were not spared of these effects. When Jai dies, there is a scene where Radha looks at Thakur. Her expression is one of desolation, and she breaks down on his shoulder. While shooting the film, actor Sanjeev Kumar (who plays the Thakur) apparently came to the director Ramesh Sippy and said to him, "I can see in Radha's eyes that she is devastated...she was married to my son...and then I was marrying her off to Jai, and then this tragedy happens...I feel so bad for her...Can I take her in my arms and comfort

her?” ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). There was one problem with his request, and Ramesh is believed to have pointed it out. “What arms?” he asked. Sanjeev Kumar the actor, had spontaneously reacted to the scene, and forgotten that his character of the Thakur had no arms ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)).

Makers of the film and its actors were not confident of the success of the film when it was released. Critics had derided the film and the actors’ performances ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). One magazine in particular is believed to have voiced the opinion that *Sholay* was an example of all that filmmakers should not have done and a colossal waste of money in a technology like 70mm (widescreen). The producers refused to reshoot the ending to be happier. It turns out this was a good decision. In the first week of the film’s release, there were few ticket sales in advance, but the theatres running the film were full house. An actor (Macmohan) who went to see the film in a theatre was mobbed. And a theatre owner in Bombay told Ramesh Sippy, the director that his film was a hit. Sippy couldn’t believe it, and asked why the theatre owner thought so. To which the theatre owner replied that the sales at his snack counter had dropped ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). Audiences weren’t even leaving the halls to obtain refreshments!

Audiences felt a connection with this film. They adopted it, were awed by it, and made it their own. When Veeru throws the coin in the last scene, people in audiences dove to the ground to see if it had fallen by them instinctively ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). By the third week, people were quoting dialogue ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). The record company noticed and released a special edition record with selected dialogue with the recorded music. Prior to this,

music sales for the film weren't doing as well as hoped, but the addition of the dialogue changed all of this ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)).

An inference here could be that *Sholay's* commercial success is an indication of just how successful it was in creating *Rasa* among audiences. Audiences loved the film. And, the film is just as popular today, indicating that even in the absence of its historical context, it remains just as relevant in Indian culture. The nationwide success of *Sholay* was an indication of its universal appeal. India, like the United States is a melting pot, with every state maintaining its unique cultural identity, language(s) and dress. *Sholay* managed to cross these boundaries. It is rare that a Hindi film becomes popular in states like West Bengal for instance, where Hindi is not spoken by many locals. And yet, the longest run for any film on record at the Jyoti cinema hall in Kolkata (West Bengal), to this day remains *Sholay*, which released on August 15, 1975, and then had a run in the theatre for a week short of two years. In subsequent years, *Sholay* was re-released several times at the venue ([Bhattacharya, 2013](#)). This is especially significant given that Kolkata, in West Bengal is a state where Hindi is neither spoken, nor really heard or understood by everyone.

That the film spoke to audiences around India, and sales from the movie and its place in history and contemporary popular culture, are all indicators of this and the fact that *Rasa*, though not directly quantifiable, was definitely created, especially when considering how the film was initially poorly received.

***Sholay*, plot and the structure of drama**

Sholay cannot be categorized solely as a romance, a western, a comedy or a tragedy, instead, it is a composite of all of them. It's termed a "curry western," and any Indian cook knows that a curry is merely a mixture of spices. The term "potboiler" is also sometimes used in India to describe a "masala" film. *Sholay* is definitely a potboiler in the sense of the film being a stew consisting of different elements. *Sholay* is the epitome of that characteristic within the *Natyashastra* that states that Indian drama is dependent on dance (*nritya*), song (*gita*), and instrumental music (*vadya*). It is incomplete without its iconic songs, dance sequences and most of all its dialogue.

There are a number of plot devices from the *Natyashastra* that are used in *Sholay*. The *Sutradhar* (the narrator or indicator) is one that is used often. Gabbar has his own "tune," that serves as an indicator of his presence. There is no narrator, however, in the true sense of the word. Instead in bits and pieces, we have the Thakur acting as the *Sutradhar* or narrator as he tells the audience how he came to meet Jai and Veeru, and the story of how he lost his arms. The detailed preliminaries listed in the *Natyashastra* always include an invocation to the Gods at the beginning of the performance. Most Indian films pay homage to the Gods before the film through a small featured prayer by the production house. *Sholay* doesn't appear to follow this in the DVD version at least. The opening credits and titles are woven into the narrative, playing along with the iconic theme music that is evocative of being western, but still manages to sound Indian.

Specific *Bhāvas* or emotions are perceived to be more attractive to certain kinds of people ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Going by the *Natyashastra*, *Sholay* may be liked by young people for its

romantic pairings (both lead pairs went on to marry), and the man-on-the-street may be attracted to watching Jai and Veeru trying to make their way in the world (not always by playing by the rules). The film definitely has depictions of love, comedy, heroism, horror, and revulsion, and of the journey that young people undertake to make their fortunes in the world. Some of these stories end well, while others do not. And it is these elements that probably make the film so popular and successful. It's definitely not a stretch to say *Sholay's* appeal, based on the guidelines in the *Natyashastra*, is universal and timeless, holding up the hypothesis that the structure of drama is one that should appeal to as many people as possible.

A reading of any Indian epics is riddled with labyrinthine journeys through wormholes of space and time. The *Natyashastra* does not provide any guidelines for such meanderings, subtly granting for their existence. The film *Sholay* displays a similar disregard for strict chronological order. The Thakur goes back and forth as he reminisces, as do some of the other characters in the film. However, from the outset, the spectator is made aware that he/she is moving with the Thakur or another character in time and space, through memory.

The protagonists of the film are two morally ambiguous young jeans-wearing criminals, Jai and Veeru, who capture the zeitgeist of the seventies, when the idealism of the freedom struggle had faded, along with the optimism of a newly independent India. Politicians, police and authority figures had lost the people's respect, and Amitabh Bachchan's "Jai" on screen was the beginning of the period of the Angry Young Man. In many ways, Jai's character is like that of Robin Hood; "good" in such a way that the Thakur would marry his widowed daughter-in-law off to him, but a jailbird, a petty thief, and a killer when necessary. In terms of the *Natyashastra*, both Jai and Veeru would be seen as "middling" characters, who were good at

communication, good with their hands, somewhat educated in the values, displayed common sense, and had good manners. But, their characters came to define those in many of the films in those years, where good people did bad things, and the ends were often said to justify the means. Young people had come to believe it was better to be “effective” than “good” ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)), and *Sholay*’s characters reflected this sign of the times. And thus, *Sholay* was a film made with “grand passion for a madly passionate audience” ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). It upheld the old virtues, albeit with a modern or post-modern twist.

Symmetrical pairings of opposites dominate the film — Jai and Veeru, Thakur and Gabbar, Basanti and Radha ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). The call to action is provided by the *Thakur* (translated as upper caste feudal lord but used here as a respectful title indicating his standing in the small village) — a man of few words, who is principled, spotlessly clean (epitomized by his white kurta pyjama), and with a clipped style of speech. His nemesis is Gabbar, a *daku* (dacoit/bandit), who is amoral, sadistic, dirty, and gregarious. The Thakur’s call is answered by two petty criminals — Veeru, the flirtatious extrovert, and Jai, the sardonic introvert. There are two women — one, a colorful, uninhibited (but morally upright), vivacious chatterbox coquette; and the other a silent shadowy figure in ghostly widow-white. The two heroes wear light-colored denim, where Gabbar wears military fatigue colors. Gabbar is amoral, with no sense of right or wrong, juxtaposed against the shades of grey in the two convicts and the absolute white of the Thakur.

Gabbar’s entrance is dramatic. He is seen entering in parts — his boots first (standard military issue, setting him apart from the other “*dakus*” of his time, who wore leather moccasins), and slowly the camera tilts upwards to reveal his face. Similarly, he grows in stature

with each line as the film progresses. As a character, he is based on Sergio Leone's villains ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). But, Gabbar is different from other Hindi film villains: there had been other "dacoits," but they were depicted as looters of villages, clad in a rustic dhoti and turban, and sporting a big red tikka on their foreheads. They were largely shown as worshipping *Ma Bhāvani* (a warrior goddess), and as honorable "Robin Hood" types, who stole from the rich to feed the poor. Gabbar however, is shown as amoral, with no redeeming qualities. He has distinct mannerisms, a way of speaking that is unlike everyone else. He even has his own dialect, "a *Ganga-Jamuna*-inspired mix of *Khadi boli* (argot) with a flavor of Avadhi" ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). Combine this, and his expressions, and you have someone iconic, who gets quoted to this day striking terror into audiences the first time he is seen. He is a prime example of the "inferior" male character in the *Natyashastra* — harsh of speech, ill-mannered, criminally inclined, violent (a killer), mean, insolent and insulting, a thief, and fond of conflict. These characters possess all the traits that are contrary to *Dharma*.

Sholay's centerpiece – the scene sequence in which Gabbar obliterates the Thakur's family – was complicated to shoot, as it had several components and functions ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)). It established the parts of the family, Gabbar's arrival, the shootings, and then the Thakur's arrival and his reaction. Ramesh Sippy, the director reported later that half the scenes had been shot when the weather suddenly changed from sunny to overcast. Sippy apparently took that as a celestial signal: the overcast skies were perfect for the scene, underlining the tragedy and heightening the sense of dramatic doom. The skies also made the next sequence more plausible – where the wind starts to build up and dry leaves are blown over the dead bodies ([Anupama Chopra, 2000](#)).

Capturing the mood seemed important to the director of the film, when you see the small sequences of scenes that have no words but reveal the nuances of relationships between the characters. Take for instance the scenes of Radha extinguishing the lamps while Jai plays the harmonica and watches her. There is an intimacy to them, unspoken, candle-lit, and romantic. Radha clad in widow-white, and him in his light-blue denim, in shadows of light. Similarly, the tiny almost inconsequential scene showing Gabbar killing an ant, which immediately moves to the scene with Ahmed's horse carrying his corpse into the village. Nothing is said, but Ahmed's life, it is implied is like that of the ant — inconsequential and quickly snuffed out. Similarly, while action in the film is very vivid, there is very little gore in the film. There are no scenes streaked by blood. Even the scenes depicting the Thakur's dead family are punctuated by the staccato sound of gunshots, rather than shocking the audience with visual gore. This is in keeping with the tenet of the *Natyashastra* which also discourages the use of visual gore to "scare" audiences.

The *aadhikaarika*, the main plotline concerned with the hero, and the *prasangika* or the subplot are also distinct. The Thakur is clearly the Hero of the story. The seed of the story is planted in the earliest memory where the Thakur meets Jai and Veeru. The memory is significant enough to be narrated, and the spectator understands that these three characters are connected. As the plotline progresses, we have the two friends arriving at the village to undertake a mysterious task assigned by the Thakur. The various incidents with Gabbar and his men form the action in the film. The key memory of the Thakur losing first his family, and subsequently his arms, is the episode, or the principal incident, or the catalyst, if you will, of all the happenings in the film. And *karya* or the final action is that final climactic fight that is the

culmination of the entire story — Gabbar’s death or his arrest and the events that lead up to it, including Jai’s death.

The film has two main secondary characters, without whom the Hero would remain unsuccessful in his quest for revenge against Gabbar — Jai and Veeru. Their stories are the *prasangika* in the film. And their stories follow the structure of the development of the plot: *Arambha* (beginning), *Prayatna* (effort), *Praptsambhāva* (prospect of success), *Niyataphalaprapti* (removal of obstacles to attain success) and *Phalaprapti* (attainment of the desired goal) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). The film begins with an invocation to the gods, who are also mentioned, seen and “heard” in the film. Basanti invokes Shiva to find her a “good” husband, while the blind imam implores Allah to watch over his son.

The *Natyashastra* has sections specifically describing the various kinds of supporting scenes, specifically those connecting stories of secondary characters with the main plotline. For instance, the scene where Ramlal tells Radha’s story, about how she was a carefree loving girl before she married and lost her husband is an example of *Vishambaka*, a scene connecting the main plotline with those of secondary characters. With Ramlal’s description, Radha’s character goes from being one-dimensional to having a more rounded definition, and the audience sees her as how she used to be. In this way, Ramlal also manages to make the story jump between the dimensions of time and space. Creative camera techniques could also have made the jump between time and space, but by using the technique of a narrator or a *sutradhar*, the filmmakers harken back to an older form of storytelling. Another scene where a character’s background is explained more in detail is the scene where members of the row of convicts extrapolate on the jailer’s character in greater detail.

Bharata has specified several instances that may not be shown on stage, including acts of war, death, grief, mourning, anger, cursing, marriage, or the depiction of a miracle. Bharata also warns against killing off the hero, his flight (or acts of cowardice), or instances where the Hero makes pacts with the enemy. *Sholay* is a film where death features heavily in many scenes — Thakur’s family, Jai’s death at the end, the imam’s son, and Kaalia’s killing by Gabbar. All of these scenes of death however, are oddly bloodless. We do see some blood in the film as bullets fly around, and it is particularly poignant to listen to Veeru as he turns to his blood-spattered friend in the climactic end battle and asks, “*Jai, tu theek hai na?*” (Jai, are you alright?). The spectators know Jai has a bullet wound in his back. They’re shown it, and once again, the audience is reeled in, complicit in the deception that Jai creates for Veeru, to save his best friend.

The conclusion here is basically this: yes, *Sholay* does retain some plot elements from the *Natyashastra*, but disregards others. It deviates when it is convenient to do so. Scenes of death and destruction for instance, feature largely, but the audience is far from put off. The death of a major character mars the end of the film. There is no happy ending for all the couples and we see one of the secondary characters leave at the end of the film. While individual scenes in the film do not cover over a year’s time period, the entire film — flashbacks and all — spans more than the period of a year. Some of the main characters have no back story. We never learn what happens to the characters in the sub-plot, like Soorma Bhopali or the jailer, leaving us with several loose ends in the colossus that is *Sholay*.

Sholay is a complex film, covering a myriad of themes, characters and messages. It is layered. The film has several messages for the audiences, messages about doing your duty,

fulfilling your destiny, loving your friends and family, and about revenge, communal integration, maintaining societal hierarchies and, being courageous when faced by adversity and threats. All of these are familiar themes to Indian audiences who have grown up with Indian mythology and the epics. Jai and Veeru may be compared to Ram and Lakshmana, and Gabbar to the evil Ravana. Thus, the stories are familiar, but packaged to suit the times.

Indian dramatic performances are said to be of two main types: *Lokadharmi* (realistic, or depicting human behavior and objects in a naturalistic way), and *Natyadharmi* (a more stylized and symbolic version of reality). *Sholay* is both *lokadharmi* and *Natyadharmi*, making use of symbolic gestures and styles, including dance, and music, as well as showing realistic portrayals of human behavior in its depiction of its characters and their traits. *Lokadharmi* drama also features both male and female characters in distinct roles, portrayed realistically. From the outset, it is clear that the film deals with a universal story: the one between good and evil. Gabbar is larger-than-life, and the Thakur is every man who is trying to do the right thing (albeit with no arms). It commented on the plight of the people, who stood up to the government, metaphorically powerless with no arms. Jai and Veeru reveal the two sides of fate or karma — a theme that is understood by those growing up culturally Indian. You win some; you lose some: that is what Jai's death says. It's arbitrary who dies and who lives, and life doesn't have always have a happy ending. The *Natyashastra* only specifies that balance be restored at the end of a story, it does not specify mandatory happy endings.

Sholay uses the *Sattvati* (grand) style of production, in which there is substantial use of grand gestures and speeches. *Sholay's* dialogues were sold by record companies when they realized audiences quoted those more than they sang the songs. *Sattvati* productions also

emphasize passionate emotions and shows of strength. *Sholay* may also be classified as a “masculine” production for its portrayals of anger, vengeance, and violence and while verbal styles of production were known for their masculine qualities per the *Natyashastra*, these kinds of plays usually attempted to evoke *Adbutā* and *Karuna Rasas*. *Sholay* however attempts to (it appears) and manages to evoke *Raudra*, *Vira*, *Bhayanaka*, and *Adbutā Rasas*, with occasional breaks where comic characters to provoke *Hasya*. This leads this researcher to classify *Sholay* as being largely of the *Sattvati* style of production.

The *Natyashastra* specifies that all plays must be of two main types: *Aviddha* and *Sukumara*. *Sholay* falls under the former type and may be characterized as largely following the *Aviddha* type for its use of violence and conflict, as well as the featuring of primarily male characters as protagonists. However, *Aviddha* dramas also feature the use of magic and were stories of Gods, demons and *rakshasas*. In a translation of this into contemporary terms, it may be possible to see the use of the coin toss motif, as a kind of “magic” or chance. Jai and Veeru are not Gods, but they are comparable to mythical heroes who save the day.

The ten kinds of plays described in the *Natyashastra* overlap and cannot be used in their strictest sense in the examination of *Sholay*, for they are mainly determined by the number of acts within a play. *Dima*, *Samavakara*, *Vyayoga*, and *Ihamrga* are considered of the type *Aviddha*, while, *Nataka*, *Prakarana*, *Bhana*, *Vithi*, and *Anka* are said to be *Sukumara* (sensitive) type of drama. The *Nataka* ends with a resolution and restoration of balance. *Sholay* does end with a resolute climax, and the vanquishing of the evil character, and tells the tale of the nobility (the Thakur). The main purpose of the protagonists is not to reiterate the social structure within society. *Sholay*, it may be contended, is more in keeping with the definition of

the *Prakarana*, where characters are not from nobility or royalty, but are commoners. The plotlines are of revenge, theft and politics, with themes of money, legal issues, love, and honor. The plotlines and themes featuring in *Sholay* are most in keeping with this type of drama. However, the *Prakarana* is considered a drama in the *Sukumara* or sensitive type, which *Sholay* is not. In looking at the other types of plays however, it is clear *Sholay* does not fit into any one category. For instance, *Sholay* cannot be a *Samavakara*, for it does not feature a trinity, nor does it feature divine characters. It cannot be *Ihamrga* because the action does not revolve around a woman. *Sholay* is not the story of a well-known hero from mythology or history, and therefore cannot be called a dramatic performance of the *Dima* variety. It cannot be of the *Vyayoga* type because it features action taking place in a period over 24 hours, even though it does have scenes of fights and conflict, centers on one main character, and features other central characters who are not from royalty. There is no central story of female lamentation, and therefore *Sholay* cannot be an *Anka*.

Simply by a process of elimination, we can categorize what *Sholay* is not, but there is no neat category into which it truly fits. However, the *Natyashastra* allows for the possibility that a dramatic story can fit into multiple categories at once or can draw from multiple types of drama. The answer to the question as to whether typology of drama may be observed within Hindi cinema at least in the case of *Sholay* is that yes, multiple types of drama may be observed in the film.

Other things of note in *Sholay*

The creation of *Rasa* according to the *Natyashastra* is through a combination of the portrayal of specific emotions expressed using the body, face, speech, and costume.

Music. It is outside the scope of this dissertation to analyze the musical compositions within film per the *Natyashastra*, as the instructions for music are incredibly detailed, from the use of musical instruments, the composition of notes, pitch, and tenor. However, the sales of the dialogue in *Sholay* and the music are clear indicators of its success in attracting audiences.

Costume. Radha and Basanti, the film's leading ladies remain clothed in keeping with their characters. This in turn helps in creating the "mood" of each scene within which they are featured. Radha in ghostly white is the weeping widow. She is ethereal, but present. The *Natyashastra* is clear on the garb of widows, "The one who is separated from her husband should wear white clothes and no make-up" ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)). Basanti, loud, brash and a coquette, is dressed in what is a facsimile of rural costume evoking *Sringara*. Her garb is flirtatious and sexy, without being obvious. The *Natyashastra* states very clearly that the women in the performances must be clad in the garb of the region to which they belong. It is implied in the film that all the events take place in the Chambal area, and the characters are dressed accordingly. Helen's outfit in the song "*Mehbooba, Mehbooba*" is overtly sexy. The Thakur's omnipresent shawl, which shields his empty sleeves from view, is an indicator that he conceals something. In addition, the Thakur's white clothing is a juxtaposition against the dusty camouflage of Gabbar.

Overall, *Sholay* is very much an Indian film. Careful consideration and comparison with points within the *Natyashastra* indicate that it draws heavily on its Indian context, which is familiar to its audiences. This in turn appears to form a large part of the reason for its appeal among Indian cinemagoers. Through themes and technical strategy, *Sholay* is a film that manages to provide evidence that traditional forms of dramaturgy need not be considered

merely as historical and cultural artifacts. Instead, it shows that traditional forms of drama – and even non-indigenous forms of drama – can be adopted and adapted for contemporary audiences.

CHAPTER 6

DILWALE DULHANIYA LE JAYENGE (1995)

Overview

“Bade bade deshon mein aisi choti choti baatein ... hoti rehti hai” (Even in the biggest of the countries, the smallest of occurrences take place all the time) ([Aditya Chopra, 1995](#))

Filmmakers may have found the winning formula with *Sholay*, but it is the changing times that continue to dictate audience taste. Exactly twenty years after *Sholay*'s release, *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* (*DDLJ*) or The brave-hearted will take the bride ([1995](#)) came along to illustrate exactly how the times had changed in terms of Bollywood cinema. *DDLJ* was a turning point in how Indian cinema began to be perceived as a representation of the way Indians and the larger diaspora engaged with each other and the motherland. It showed that Bollywood could be (and perhaps had always been) a vehicle for articulating the changing Indian identity in all its forms — domestically and internationally ([Uberoi, 1998](#)).

The film took liberties with film convention, despite being a simple and typical Bollywood film featuring young love. Aditya Chopra, the director, remained faithful to the usual basic requirements of song and dance spectacles contained therein, and added beautiful locations, but changed some aspects of these for the film to be an invigorating experience. The expat national for instance — the NRI— was the main protagonist. Prior to this, the expat, the NRI and other members of the diaspora were largely depicted as being morally corrupt. These characters had hitherto only been shown drunk, smoking, gambling, and exhibiting lust, all of which have traditionally been considered negative habits adopted from the “corruptive” West.

A great example of this is in the film *Purab Aur Pachhim* ([1970](#)), where characters in the film who are seen as “western” are depicted as morally corrupt. *DDLJ* changed this perception of the expat. Both Simran and Raj, the protagonist lovers, are second-generation immigrants of Indian descent. The filmmaker emphasizes their distinctly “moralistic Indian” thinking and values, despite their upbringing in the West, and their Western clothing (the latter more applicable for Raj). There is no “villain” in the film, and certainly no one in “Gabbar’s” class as in *Sholay*. In fact, the most unlikeable character in the film is Simran’s Punjabi “fiancé,” who is depicted as being both chauvinistic and lecherous ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)).

Even though the diaspora was always known to consume Bollywood cinema, considering it a primary source of connection to contemporary India ([Bandyopadhyay, 2008](#)), Bollywood producers had hitherto not tapped into this potential audience. *DDLJ* was the first film that directly spoke to the diaspora. Chakravarty ([2011](#)) elucidates the relationship between the diaspora and India by stating that in many cases, Bollywood and all its accoutrements are directly seen as substitutions for India, and this is reflected in how the songs, fashion and the dance all feature prominently in diasporic gatherings. Past researchers have also pointed out that Indian cinema is tuned into, and speaks about a variety of concerns, anxieties and dilemmas of the everyday lives of Indians ([Chakravarty, 2011](#); [Nandy, 1998](#); [Prasad, 1998](#)). However, this was almost never depicted on screen, and it is important that the nostalgia felt by non-resident Indians be understood in its proper context. Most diasporic populations possess dual identities that dwell in the intersection between past and present, parent culture and adopted culture, belonging and exile, and nationality and naturalization ([Chakravarty, 2011](#)). And whether intentionally or not, *DDLJ* found a way to address and represent these

conflicts in a way that was meaningful and real to the diasporic community, and it also managed to capitalize on the sense of nostalgia that people of Indian descent felt for the motherland ([J. Desai, 2004](#)).

The dilemma of the Indian diaspora with regard to cultural identity, is primarily manifested in the indecision of what to accept from western practices and norms, and in what to abandon from Indian practices ([Rushdie, 2012](#)). This has led to what one researcher has called “new ethnicities” ([Hall, 1996](#)) and another has termed “In-between” cultures ([Bhabha, 1996](#)). The idea of these new ethnicities and the dilemma faced by those living in the cusp of two cultures — eastern and western — is explored in *DDLJ*, ensconced in the arranged marriage vs. “love marriage” debate, and in the trip taken by Simran and Raj through Europe, unaccompanied by their parents, and in the company of friends who are not blood relatives. And despite the film having a happy ending with a love marriage, *DDLJ* attempted to get one important message across: Indian values are portable, paramount, and inherited — and your parents apparently always know what’s best for you.

The release of *DDLJ* coincided with the rise in Indian liberalization, the policy of which was first laid out in 1991. India’s liberalization was a big step in eliminating the restrictions on imports and on foreign investment ([Sharpe, 2007](#)). Consumer goods and brands (including Coca Cola and Pepsi) that were hitherto unavailable or were brought in by visiting “aunties and uncles,” were now in the hands of the average Indian. Liberalization brought in cable TV, MTV, and American soap operas. Sex was now talked about, and seen, on television more openly than ever before. And this changed the Indian middle class forever, leaving it caught in a space

that was now shared by Indian traditional values and western permissiveness. *DDLJ* was a direct reflection of this intersection. Previously the Non-Resident Indian (NRI) lorded it over the Resident Indian. To Indians in India, the traditional outlook of Simran's father was an indication that Indians outside India were the same, if not in some ways more traditional than the Indian within India. And suddenly Indians in India felt equal. They found they shared problems with their brethren outside the country but no longer blindly aspired to be them. It was a revelation in more ways than one. For the NRIs, the film spoke to them on another level. They saw themselves as protagonists and portrayed in a positive way for the very first time on the big screen. Thus, *DDLJ* tuned into and spoke to the diaspora, and ultimately imported them back home to India. At its heart it spoke about two main concerns of the Indian diaspora — retention of the Indian identity while living outside the motherland, and marriage within the Indian community ([Uberoi, 1998](#)).

The latter — marriage within the Indian community, both within the country and in the diaspora is a font of much conflict and discussion. In India, marriages are believed to be made in heaven, to be enacted on earth — and “arranged” by one's parents. The institution of marriage is complicated by the conflict between individual desires and aspirations, societal expectations, and social standing (class and caste). This has been called the “animating logic of South Asian romance,” and is a dilemma that has been consistently solved by the phenomenon of “arranged marriages” ([Uberoi, 1998](#)). The subordination of individual desire to familial duty is one that is familiar to Indian culture, and females especially are relegated to traditional roles ([S. Chopra & Chanda, 2016](#)). Even before liberalization, some families who prided themselves as being “less conservative” but who still clung to aspects of class and caste began to adopt the “arranged

love marriage.” This researcher has had many friends who have had “arranged love marriages,” which have either entailed marrying someone of their own choice with parental consent, or conveniently falling in love with the person of their parents’ choice. Both phenomena are seen to an extent within *DDLJ*.

In his book, *Modern Romance* ([2017b](#)), Aziz Ansari, a second-generation Indian-American has written:

My parents had an arranged marriage. This always fascinated me. I am perpetually indecisive about even the most mundane things, and I couldn’t imagine navigating such a huge life decision so quickly.

I asked my dad about this experience, and here’s how he described it: he told his parents he was ready to get married, so his family arranged meetings with three neighboring families. The first girl, he said, was “a little too tall,” and the second girl was “a little too short.” Then he met my mom. He quickly deduced that she was the appropriate height (finally!), and they talked for about 30 minutes. They decided it would work. A week later, they were married.

And they still are, 35 years later. Happily so—and probably more so than most people I know who had nonarranged marriages. That’s how my dad decided on the person with whom he was going to spend the rest of his life. ([Ansari, 2017b, p. 187](#))

The researcher’s parents had a similarly arranged marriage and are still together. And therein lies the crux of the issue at the heart of *DDLJ*, once again unknowingly best

encapsulated by Ansari ([2017b](#)), who comments on the difference between how his parents made the decision to get married and how members of the next generation make their decisions: “*The stunning fact remained: it was quicker for my dad to find a wife than it is for me to decide where to eat dinner.*” ([Ansari, 2017a](#)). Similarly, in the film, the female protagonist Simran, agrees to marry someone she has never met, simply at the behest of her father.

Other films from the 1990s similarly reaffirmed the importance of the Indian familial unit. They featured upper-middle-class or affluent families as main characters and presented “endless rounds of parties, beach dances, wedding celebrations, and an all-around feeling of well-being” ([Kripalani, 2001](#)). The previous year, *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun* ([1994](#)), another Bollywood blockbuster, had shattered box office records. Both films dealt with young love and family, albeit in different ways. *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun* ([1994](#)) revolved around a wedding and was in essence a family drama, complete with parents, aunts, uncles, cousins, the family help, and even the household pets. *DDLJ*, on the other hand, was a story about young forbidden love with an Indian twist. These two young lovers agree to only be together with familial consent and acceptance, or not at all. Rebellion and young love were no longer synonymous, at least in Bollywood — And the angry young man of twenty years ago, was now a lover in love.

***DDLJ* Synopsis**

The film opens with a scene that immediately provides the context for the film. Baldev Singh (Amrish Puri) is standing in a square in London, where he tells his tale of being an immigrant in another land. He is feeding the pigeons, and his wistful memories take the audience to the yellow mustard fields in Punjab. A short traditional folk song and the title

credits roll at the same time, and Baldev Singh is seen walking through London (sometimes with an umbrella) to a store front, which he unlocks.

The titles end, and he is seen invoking the gods (with a stick of incense) to an idol of Lakshmi, the Goddess of Wealth. The phone rings, and we see his wife, Lajjo (Farida Jalal), at home, who calls him every day at the same time to know that he has got to the store safe. Chutki (Pooja Ruparel), his younger daughter, goes to school, and then his wife goes in search of their older daughter Simran (Kajol). A short scene with mother and daughter shows the two reading from Simran's diary, where she describes how she has begun having thoughts of romance with a yet-unknown man, who she knows must exist somewhere. A song ensues, in which this man is introduced.

In a football field somewhere, Raj (Shahrukh Khan) is playing soccer, and is then seen in many other locations doing the things that rich kids are supposed to do, partying, drinking, by a pool, and by an airplane. The song ends, Raj wakes up in bed, drives a luxury car, and appears late at his own graduation, where he finds out he has failed high school. His friends Rocky (Karan Johar) and Roby (Arjun Sablok) are with him in school. At home, his father Dharamveer Malhotra is celebrating Raj's non-graduation. Raj is a bit ashamed and says he will cancel his planned trip to Europe, but his father does not agree, explaining that he wants Raj to enjoy his youth. Dharamveer makes it clear that he wants to live vicariously through his son.

Meanwhile, a letter from India arrives at the Singh household in London that makes Baldev very happy. The letter is read out by Simran, who learns she has been betrothed to Ajit Singh's (Satish Shah) son, Kuljeet Singh (Parmeet Sethi) since they were both children. She runs

from the room abruptly, clearly upset, which her father mistakes for shyness — a quality he considers attractive in an Indian woman. Lajjo timidly asks Baldev to ask Simran for her consent to this betrothal, a consent he explains is a foregone conclusion because he knows his daughter will be happy. In a short subsequent scene, both Raj and Simran are found to be on the same street discussing trips to Europe. They do not know each other but serendipitously cross paths.

Baldev is seen closing up his shop for the night, when Rocky comes to ask him to let him buy some beer. Baldev refuses, saying it is too late and the store is closed for the day. Rocky leaves and tells Raj and Roby he could not buy beer. Raj goes inside, pretends to have a headache and asks to buy some aspirin. Baldev relents and sells him some aspirin, when Raj asks to buy beer as well. Raj insinuates he feels guilty for making Baldev reopen the store simply for a little aspirin. Baldev sees through the ruse and is enraged and tells Raj to leave. Raj makes to leave, but comes back, takes the beer from the counter, throws the cash at Baldev, and breaks his idol of Lakshmi in the process.

Later we see Baldev arrive at his home. Just prior to this, the women in his family are listening and dancing to western music, which they switch to Indian devotional music when the doorbell rings. Baldev tells his wife about the incident and asks her to be grateful that her daughters and she have escaped the curse of western values. He claims “Indians” who adopt western ways are “*Galli ka Kuttas, na ghar ka, na ghat ka*” (Stray street dogs, who belong neither at home, nor in a compound).

The following morning, we see Simran praying and then taking her father’s blessing. Her father sits down with her and reminisces about India and tells her how proud he is of her. She

takes the opportunity to ask him for permission to go with her friends to Europe for one month. In the exchange, she reminds him she will be moving to an unknown land that is not her home, to marry a complete stranger with no complaint. And so, she would like one month of her life to be her own. Baldev gives her permission for the trip.

Simran and Raj leave from the same station on their trip. Raj helps Simran onto the train, and they get shut into a luggage compartment. Raj attempts to charm Simran, but she rebuffs him. When they rejoin their respective friends, their accounts of the meeting are vastly different, with each projecting themselves positively (although Simran's appears closer to the truth, and Raj appears to insinuate that Simran threw herself at him). In Paris, the two groups of friends are at the same event, where Simran attempts to embarrass Raj, but he redeems himself, and we see a slow thaw in Simran's feelings toward him. The tour continues until they get to Switzerland, where the two miss the train onward, and after a series of events are in a car heading to Bern.

The car breaks down, they get drunk, and end up sleeping in the same room. In the morning Simran has no recollection of the previous night, and Raj lets her believe that they have had sex. He relents and tells her the truth when she gets hysterical, after a monologue about being Indian and understanding the value of an Indian woman's honor (her virginity). Simran makes a statement that insinuates self-harm if she had lost her "honor." In a church close by, the audience realizes that Raj is developing feelings for Simran, but he learns that she is engaged to be married to someone she's never met.

The two meet up with their friends in Bern. Raj declares his love for Simran, but on seeing her reaction, claims the confession was in jest. He wants to know whether Simran would give up her arranged match if she were to fall in love with someone else. She does not respond. They arrive in London, where they say their goodbyes, and Simran asks Raj for his address to invite him to her wedding. He states he wouldn't have come anyway. They part, and Simran realizes she is in love with Raj.

Back at home, she reveals her feeling to her mother, but her father hears her and feels betrayed. He declares they will leave for India forever in the morning. Meanwhile, Raj tells his father about his feelings for Simran, and his father encourages him to go find her and stop the wedding. In the morning, Raj arrives on her doorstep to find the entire family has moved to Punjab. This is the midpoint of the film and coincides with the interval.

After the interval, the Singh family is seen travelling by train in Punjab. The folk song plays out in the passing fields, Baldev is nostalgic, and the rest of the family are lost in thought. When they arrive, they are greeted by the family of Simran's betrothed and Baldev's mother, who is seeing her son after 20 years. The families reunite, and young and old are introduced. Simran is less than impressed by Kuljit, but at the request of her mother, agrees to give up on Raj and go ahead with the arranged wedding. However, the morning after this agreement, she runs out into the yellow mustard fields, and finds Raj. He has come looking for her. They declare their love for each other, and while she wants them to run away and get married, Raj asserts that he will slowly win over her family and thus, approval for her hand in marriage.

In the next scene Kuljit is found caught in a hunter's trap. Raj "saves" him, and befriends him, pretending he is a rich investor, looking for the right opportunity to invest. Ajit and Kuljit are instantly impressed and invite him to stay with them at their house. The daughter in the family, Preeti (Mandira Bedi) displays her shy interest in Raj.

Ajit Singh and his family, accompanied by Raj go over to Simran's house, where Raj proceeds to make himself at home, and endears himself to members of Simran's family, including her mother, sister, grandmother, and unmarried aunt. He realizes at the first meeting that Baldev Singh is the man from whom he had once "stolen" beer. Baldev appears also to recognize Raj. Raj attempts to bond with Baldev over feeding the pigeons every day, but it is an uphill battle. He covers up the real reason he is in Punjab and instead helps out in the wedding preparations at every turn, as if he is part of the bride's family. Slowly, even Baldev begins to thaw to him. Meanwhile, Lajjo and Chutki realize he is the boy from Europe.

Raj's father also arrives in Punjab, just in time to mistakenly agree to a match between Raj and Preeti. Raj updates him on the current situation, and the two conspire together to get Simran's family to accept him. Dharmveer tells Kuljit he doesn't think he has made a good match, and Kuljit reveals that he has no qualms about being unfaithful to Simran after they are married. Lajjo urges the young couple to run away, because she knows her husband will never agree to the match, but Raj insists that he and Simran will marry only with familial consent.

In another scene where Raj and Baldev are feeding the pigeons, Baldev describes the feeling of alienation when one is far from the homeland, but Raj convinces him this is a matter of perspective. He believes that home is what one carries within, it is not the external

accoutrements of a person, like dress and language. Baldev is lost in thought, when a pigeon falls from the sky, injured. Baldev is furious but resigned when he sees Kuljit hunting nearby. Raj “cures” the pigeon by applying a salve made from “the soil of the motherland.”

When they return home, Baldev finds his mother has collapsed and could be dying. She expresses a desire to see Simran wed before her death. The wedding is moved up, much to the panic of all those who know of Simran and Raj’s love for each other. Simran is seen surrounded by the paraphernalia of her wedding but gazing at a photograph of herself and Raj in Europe, when her mother calls away. Baldev finds the photograph soon after.

A confrontation takes place between Baldev and his family and friends on one side, and Raj on the other side. It turns violent, and Simran pleads her case. Raj refuses to defend himself and leaves. Baldev is unmoved. He continues to remain firm even when Dharamveer advocates on behalf of the couple.

Raj is then seen being attacked by Kuljit and some hired goons. He makes no move to defend himself. Dharamveer arrives and tries to defend his son but is hurt in the process. Seeing his father hurt enrages Raj, and he begins to defend and then attack Kuljit and the goons in turn. Someone tells Baldev and Ajit about the altercation, and they rush to the station in time to separate Raj from the others. Simran and her mother, along with some of the other women also arrive at the train station to see Raj and his father get on the train. Simran makes to go to Raj, who watches her impassively. But her father restrains her by holding on to her hand. Baldev continues to stare at Raj, even as the train begins to move. Simran continues to plead. Something in Raj’s face appears to change Baldev’s mind, and he lets Simran go, telling her to

go to Raj. He tells her to finally live her own life, for he knows now that Raj is the only man who will ever love her that much. Simran runs to Raj who holds out his hand, even as she runs alongside the train to reach him. She finally manages to hold on to his hand and gets onto the train into his arms. Raj gives Baldev the thumbs up sign, who returns the gesture. Simran finally looks back to her family who appear to her in a haze. She turns toward Raj and his father. The film ends with cut scenes from the romance between Simran and Raj.

DDLJ and the Natyashastra

“This teaches duty to those bent on doing their duty, love to those who are eager for its fulfillment, and it chastises those who are ill-bred or unruly, promotes self-restraint in those who are disciplined, gives courage to cowards, energy to heroic persons, enlightens men of poor intellect and gives wisdom to the learned.” ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 15](#))

One of the most salient messages of *DDLJ* is its overt emphasis on “Dharma,” the Hindu concept of the personal ethical code that must be followed by all. While “Kāma” or love or passion appears to be the theme of the film, represented by Simran and Raj, ultimately the film appears to say that adherence to “Dharma” supersedes everything else — including the realization of true young love. And its appeal to Indians everywhere lay in its speaking of a common tongue — the language of Indian (Hindu) values.

Dramatic Success, the *Natyashastra* and *DDLJ*

The first Indian migrants to North America arrived on the Pacific Coast to work on the railroads and the lumber mills in Washington State near Vancouver and subsequently to California. They were young Punjabi Sikhs, who had once served in the Indian army for the

British Raj, but who no longer wanted to stay in service ([Bhatia, 2007](#)). Similarly, the United Kingdom saw an influx of Indian migrants from Punjab both before and after Independence. A report published in Canada stated that approximately 50 percent of East Indian immigrants in Canada identified as being of Punjabi descent ([Bhargava, Sharma, & Salehi, 2008](#)). And, while exact figures of the demographic composition of the Indian diaspora are hard to find, it is not unreasonable to believe that a large part of the diaspora is of Punjabi descent.

Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge spoke directly to the diaspora that identifies as Punjabi and was a huge success in this community. The *Natyashastra* advocates first audience identification, and subsequently, tailoring content specifically to target this audience, as being important for a dramatic performance to be successful. In this aspect, *DDLJ* has proved extremely successful. The nostalgia by Baldev Singh in the film may be seen in two ways — as nostalgia for Punjab, and secondly as nostalgia for India. The setting of the film, language, dress, cultural references and folk music used in the film are all Punjabi as well.

This geographic affiliation may also have contributed to another reason for the success of the film — Pakistani audiences. By targeting Punjab and Punjabis, Aditya Chopra managed to target all of Punjab, a state that was divided by Partition in 1947. By casting Shahrukh Khan, a Muslim actor who self identifies as being of Pathan descent, he ensured that the film transcended domestic audiences into neighboring Pakistan and Afghanistan, where Hindi films remain popular to this day.

DDLJ broke *Sholay's* box office records, as well as the record for the longest theatre run. *Sholay* ([1975](#)) ran in Mumbai's Minerva theatre for 300 weeks. But *DDLJ* ran for over a

thousand weeks in Mumbai's Maratha Mandir theatre. Management at the theatre decided to stop screening the film on February 21, 2013, but caved to popular demand to bring it back the very next day ([Bhattacharya, 2013](#)). And there it has run ever since — house-full (sold-out attendance). The Reason? "It's a first-grade picture," said Kundan (a black marketeer), "that's why the public still comes," adding, "I've never seen such a craze for a film." ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). Inside the theatre, what may be described as an atmosphere of communal karaoke pervades the audience. The audience cheers, mouths dialogue, and sings the songs, clearly indicating that this is not their first time seeing this film. The researcher's friend in her last viewing of the film at a local theatre many years after the film's release reported that a man sitting next to her cried copiously and loudly as the film progressed towards its climactic end. There have been some who have cynically attributed the audience's repeat viewings to a desire to escape the Indian heat in an inexpensive way in an air-conditioned theatre ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). This researcher would disagree; after all, audience members can just as easily go watch newer films at other theatres closer by. Instead this repeated attendance at a theatre of the same film, may be attributed to a sense of nostalgia for a classic and much-loved film, much like the researcher's repeat attendance at the annual showing of the Broadway Musical *Mamma Mia*. Indeed some regular audiences saunter in even half an hour late for the film, and leave when their favorite scenes are over, indicating that the pleasure they take in the film now is more in the experience, rather than in the story ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)).

It has been estimated by music company HMV's executive director Harish Dayani that one out of every three households in India used to own the *DDLJ* soundtrack, that an estimated 25 million copies of its soundtrack have been sold worldwide, and that approximately half of

that number may be estimated as being pirated copies ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). The music was accompanied by the use of beautiful locations in both Europe and India. A lot of Indian films used foreign locations for song-and-dance sequences, but *DDLJ* made Indian locations look exotic to depict romance ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). The song “*Tujhe Dekha To Yeh Jana Sanam*” (As soon as I saw you, I knew), is a prime example of this. The video featured two immigrant Indian characters, clasped in a romantic embrace, placed among mustard fields in Punjab, one clad in Indian garb, and the other in Western garb. It was a great addition to the nascent music video industry in India, a country that had only recently discovered MTV.

Even though revenue figures in India are notoriously unreliable, it has been estimated that *DDLJ* has generated ₹302,00,00,000 in official box office revenues worldwide ([Malvania, 2014](#)). In fact, Komal Nahta, a Bollywood trade analyst, estimates that between 1994 and 1995, revenues for the box office for Hindi cinema went up by over 300 percent ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). This change began in 1994, when *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun* ([1994](#)) changed how films were released, as the video and theatre release were set for different dates. More importantly, its release marked a significant increase in ticket prices for Bollywood films, especially in certain theatres. Hitherto, cinema goers paid nominal sums to go see their favorite actors on-screen. But *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun*, and then *DDLJ* saw ticket prices go to as much as ₹150 in select theatres ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). And the higher prices changed the demographic of theatregoers. The 1980s for instance saw an increase in the number of people who had VCRs in their homes, and most people preferred to watch their films in the privacy of their own homes. Theatres were mostly frequented by men and women of the lower classes. The increase in prices in select theatres for these films was a gamble that paid off, attracting people of the

suddenly affluent middle class back to the theatres, featuring characters they either wanted to emulate, or could identify with already.

Aditya Chopra, director and writer of the film did his own research. Son of the famous Hindi film director Yash Chopra, he is believed to have an uncanny understanding of Indian audiences and is famous for his hands-on approach to the minutiae of filmmaking. For many years before turning filmmaker, Aditya Chopra would go to the theatre incognito and watch films with regular cinema goers. He experienced Bollywood with its real mass audiences ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). In making this film, Aditya Chopra knew he wanted to attract the NRI audience, and because of its appeal to this segment, *DDLJ* snared the overseas Bollywood audience market, and captured it. The film made over five million dollars in business worldwide in the first week alone, and 11,000 people watched the film in San Francisco's Naz theatre in the first week ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)). Similarly, the film ran in select theatres in the UK for over a year ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)).

Young people formed a large part of this audience. Producers and filmmakers had lost this segment of the audience as young "westernized" middle class audiences had begun to lose interest in Hindi films and considered them "uncool." As a teenager in the 1990s, this researcher knows and understands this attitude very well, and films like *DDLJ* and the later *Dil Chahta Hai* ([2001](#)) changed this perception. One of the reasons for these films' success was in their portrayal of younger actors and actresses who were seen as identifiable and "cool." Shahrukh Khan, who starred in *DDLJ* went on to be known as King Khan, with this film catapulting him to stardom. Today, nearly every film featuring Shahrukh Khan has some nod to

this film that launched him as a star. Perhaps this is nostalgia but more likely gratitude to that first film that helped launch him. Whatever the emotion, this self-referencing has turned him into an iconic brand that helps sell everything from fairness cream to Pepsi.

During the making of the film, film actress Kajol, who starred in the film, said to Aditya Chopra, the director of the film, "I thought your film was different." Chopra reportedly responded by saying, "My film is not different. I'm making the most commercial, clichéd, tapori (pedestrian) movie. I'm making the oldest story in the world" ([Anupama Chopra, 2002, p. 57](#)).

DDLJ on the surface is the quintessential Bollywood musical romance, the likes of which are churned out every year ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#)), but for some specific reasons it turned into a runaway box office hit.

The question arises then, why did this formulaic film become so iconic, where others like it have flopped? And the answer here at least, seems to have been the specific targeting of a section of the audience that had hitherto been ignored — the Indian diaspora. The characters in the film spoke to and about what was going on in the diaspora and within Indian borders at the same time — Indians everywhere were caught in the eye of the storm between East and West. *DDLJ* featured characters raised in the west who were not only struggling with defining their "Indian" side, but also featured Indians who were struggling to reconcile with the encroaching Western ideals in their lives. In focusing on national and communal identity, the filmmakers ignored established conventions of caste and class. In tweaking the formula of the popular musical, this Bollywood film redefined what it meant to be Indian in a globalized society. And with this emphasis on the context, it managed to be successful.

The reasons for the success of *DDLJ* likely lie more in its star appeal and in its attention to detail in appealing to Indians' emotions or values than in its story of young love, implying that this film was more successful in its creation of *Rasa* than *Sholay*.

Rasa and DDLJ

DDLJ opens with a scene set in London. Everything is grey: the buildings, the sky, and the streets. And in this, we see a man in subdued Indian clothing, but a deep red coat, feeding pigeons from a pouch in his hands. A voiceover plays in a somber tone. And as the voiceover continues, the tempo changes, and the audience is transported to Baldev's memories of vibrant Punjab, where the fields are yellow, and the people are colorfully clad. As the scene ends, the audience and Baldev return to England, where he has finished feeding the pigeons for the day.

The tone of the start and end of the scene is melancholic (*Karuna Rasa*). Baldev wears a deep red/maroon coat which is perhaps an indication of Baldev Singh's character, for this is a man prone to rage. But as he is transported to Punjab, he has a small smile on his face, an expression of wonder, and of joy (*Adbutā Rasa*). The yellow fields and the song and dance in Punjab, indicates to the audience that this is a place of his dreams, where he wants to be and isn't able to be. And at the end of the scene, he walks away, with the pigeons dispersing behind him, flying into the grey sky. Nostalgia, sadness, and memories, these are all tinged with the happiness of Baldev's yellow dreams.

The theory of *Rasa* explicitly states that the visual spectacle, including color, gesture, dance, and song all contribute to creating the intended *Rasa* within the audience. The visual

aspects of *DDLJ* clearly supersede the spoken effects. When speaking of *DDLJ*, viewers and researchers and viewers most often mention the yellow fields in Punjab, and it is evident that this is an iconic message, reinforced by several scenes in the film, as well as the film's poster ([Anupama Chopra, 2002](#); [Patel, 2015](#)). Clearly, the yellow fields evoke an emotional response within the viewers, enough that every viewer the researcher has ever spoken to about the film mentions them in their descriptions of the film.

In the *Natyashastra*, the color yellow is associated with the *Adbutā Rasa*, and the *Vismaya Bhāva*, both of which are connected with the emotional states of amazement and wonder. In *DDLJ*'s iconic reunion scene, Simran is in a dream state, when she runs outside into the fields and comes upon Raj in a yellow mustard field. It is a scene of wonder, and viewers rooting for the young lovers collectively sigh at the beauty around them and at the wonder that the two have been reunited despite the odds. The scene is still dream-like in its quality as the viewers realize that a happy ending is still not a sure thing but that the creator, Brahma (who is associated with this *Rasa*), has blessed the two.

The yellow mustard fields are a repeated visual image in the film, with Baldev seeing them in his memories, from the train as he arrives with his family from the UK, in Simran and Raj's reunion scene, and in subsequent scenes between Raj and Baldev feeding the pigeons, indicating that they are motifs. Another visual motif is the repeated action of Baldev feeding the pigeons, something he associates with his childhood, and with his memories of India, and the display of the Goddess Laxmi, the Goddess of Wealth and material abundance in the film. Baldev is first seen performing a little *puja* in his store, and we see the goddess displayed his

home in the UK and in India. This Goddess, as most Indian Hindus know, is not just the Goddess of Wealth but is also associated with the women in the house. A new bride is often referred to as the “*Ghar-ki-Lakshmi*” (the lady/Goddess of the house, who is traditionally believed to bring in good fortune and wealth to the house she enters). In the film, Simran, the new bride is to enter the house of Kuljit and Ajit Singh, who hope to be blessed with good fortune and prosperity. In that sense, we also see the two of them associate with Raj, whom they invite into their homes when they learn he is rich and looking for new investments. Yellow is also the color of the outfit in the scene where Simran walks away from Raj toward the train. Raj says to himself, “Raj, if this girl loves you, she will turn around.” As he mouths to himself, “turn,” The audience sees Simran walking away in a pale yellow haze. When she turns, around, the audience is amazed. And it appears as if a golden glow surrounds her. Overall, the color yellow is ubiquitous in *DDLJ*. And while this is convenient in this analysis of the film, the color itself was picked by Aditya Chopra, director of the film. Chopra knew he wanted his lead pair to reunite in a field of yellow “sarson” (mustard) flowers, and spent a long time scouting for the ideal location. Thus, the color dominating the film’s backdrops was not arbitrary or traditional, but a director’s creative vision that paid off.

While visual images are used as repeated motifs in the film, there is also another often-used motif used in many films: the theme song, a tune or ditty that is repeated and associated with a character. In *DDLJ*, Simran hears a ditty, the opening tune of the song “*Tujhe Dekha Toh Yeh Jaana Sanam*” (When I saw you I knew what love is) whenever she deeply misses or dreams of Raj. This is the *sutradhar* (the narrator or the indicator) in the film. The audience knows to listen for this tune and associates it with the two of them and their love. Little wonder that

when the song is finally played out, the audience feels a sense of relief, as they have been “primed” with anticipation when only the opening bars of the song have been played or a small ditty in another instance.

The creation of *Rasa* involves the use of gestures and the body. The use of the eyes is linked closely to the *Sringara Rasa*, which in turn is linked to the Rati (erotic) *bhāva*. There are several scenes in the film where Raj and Simran’s eyes are seen to do the talking. However, the most famous among these would be the scene where Simran wakes up wearing Raj’s shirt and is afraid she has slept with him. Raj teases her at first, but as she becomes agitated, tells her the truth. And as he realizes her agitation, he looks into her eyes, and tells her the truth, calming her down, and assuring her of his sincerity. The scene is rife with emotion. In addition to his gaze, and his gesture, Raj declares that he is a “Hindustani,” and that he knows what an Indian woman’s virtue means to her. The audience is impressed. It is one of the very first times in the film where Raj’s character evokes the *Vīra Rasa*, that of heroism.

The eyes do a lot of the talking in a number of scenes within the film. In the start of the song, *Tujhe Dekha To Yeh Jaana Sanam* (When I saw you I knew what love is), for instance, Raj and Simran embrace. Simran then moves away from Raj, her expressive eyes communicating her distress. She does not know whether Raj cares for her and moves away embarrassed at having initiated an embrace with a man. Raj, who is equally overcome with emotion, declares himself using song but begins only when her back is turned. And, finally at the end of the film, Baldev is seen holding on to Simran’s hand, preventing her from going to Raj. Meanwhile Baldev and Raj continue to hold each other’s gaze. In an instant, we realize Baldev has come to

some conclusion from this silent communication, and he lets Simran go to Raj, before clarifying it, to tell her to go to Raj and live her life. This last interchange remains enigmatic, however, and may be interpreted in a variety of ways.

Parciack (2016) has posited that popular Hindi films like *DDLJ* are primarily concerned with the intrinsic conflict between *Kāma* (love arising from passion and carnal pleasure) and *Dharma* (love arising from duty) and that most characters are caught between their individual desires and their dharmic obligations and norms. This position is supported by *DDLJ*, where Baldev clearly embodies the *dharmic* aspect, and Raj epitomizes the pursuit of *Kāma*. In addition, Parciack (2016) appears to assert that the focus on the pursuit of *Dharma*, and this inherent conflict between the pursuit of *Dharma* and *Kāma*, is a deterrent to the successful creation of *Rasa*, despite the causation of the *Vīra* (heroic *Rasa*) (Parciack, 2016). This researcher would venture to disagree with this stance, positing instead that this conflict lies at the heart of a great many others in Indian society and is bound together in the values of the primarily prevailing Hindu systems within the country. Thus, rather than detract from the creation of *Rasa*, the conflict between *Dharma* and *Kāma* and its inevitable resolution in *DDLJ*, actually adds to the creation of *Rasa*. And in addition, it gives rise to another hypothesis: Could it be that being immersed in Indian culture, Indian audiences are subliminally “aware” of *Rasas* and *Bhāvas*?

Thus, *Rasa* is caused in the audience in several ways by this film, where the audience cries with Raj and Simran, but understands Baldev’s *dharmic* attitude. The successful use of color, gesture, and music is a great example of the different *Bhāvas* that have led to *Rasa*. But,

the *Rasa* created in this film is culturally contextual. *DDLJ* is not a film that would have universal appeal, nor in fact, does it have timeless appeal. To a non-Indian, this film would fail to convey the same meaning. Instead what this film indicates is that *Rasa* for a performance is created in an audience only when the performers and the audience have a shared code and a shared context. Instead, Indians of a certain generation and background are far more likely to be able to appreciate the film than other people, or even contemporary audiences.

***DDLJ*, plot and the structure of drama**

At first glance, *DDLJ* appears to be a film about two young lovers, and how they manage to be together. But after a second look, it is contended that it is actually Baldev's journey to acceptance that his daughter's cultural identity and values may differ from his own. With Baldev considered as protagonist, *DDLJ* fits in best as a *Samavakara*, one of the ten kinds of plays laid out by the *Natyashastra*, in which the main character is most often an *Asura*, or a demon, and may contain as many as 12 main characters. The action in the play should revolve around the exploits of the gods and must focus on either the three kinds of deception, love, or excitement. It is, in short, a three-act play of a specific length. No ancient plays of this kind have survived today, and *DDLJ* does not satisfy all the requirements mentioned. Baldev, Raj, Simran and the other main characters are neither Gods nor *Asuras*, but people with means. And as Simran and Raj are portrayed as sympathetic characters, and Baldev Singh is portrayed as being obstinate and rigid, he may be seen as the protagonist *Asura*, who are generally known in mythology to be quick to anger, rigid, prone to stubbornness and serving as obstacles in the journey of lovers.

DDLJ is neither about deception nor excitement, but love. The description of the *Samavakara* states that three kinds of love must be featured in this kind of play. These would be love arising out of duty, love leading to material gain, and love arising out of passion. All three are clearly portrayed in the film. Baldev believes that he is doing his duty in getting Simran married to his friend's son. He has made a promise, and he intends to fulfil it. Ajit Singh and Kuljit Singh, together epitomize the love leading to material gain. Kuljit believes that marrying Simran is his ticket to get to the UK; while his father agrees to take Raj into their home to stay with them, and maneuvers to get Raj married to his daughter because he believes that Raj is a millionaire. And finally, Raj and Simran embody love arising out of passion.

DDLJ may be categorized as being a romantic film, and all its songs and dances are an integral part of the film's appeal. The *Natyashastra* states that young people are attracted to depictions of love, older people tend to favor stories of tradition and "tales of virtue," while children, women and those with less or no education prefer comedic depictions. As discussed earlier in this section, *DDLJ* was popular with young people and older people, for albeit different reasons. Young people watched the film for its romantic depictions and older people identified with Baldev Singh, sympathizing with him for his difficulty in finding his footing in a rapidly changing world, as well as trying to relate to his children while still doing what he thinks is best for them.

Plays of the style of the *Samavakara* need not — and in the case of *DDLJ* — do not have a distinct main plot and sub plot because of the limited cast of characters. Three main characters dominate the film, but the others act as a foil against them. Baldev's character is in

direct contrast to those of Ajit Singh and Dharamveer Malhotra, the other two fathers portrayed in the film. While the other two also appear patriarchal, they are more democratic in their dealings with their children. However, in this, it must be noted that this is in relation to their sons, and not their daughters. In the scenes in which they are introduced, the fathers' characters couldn't be more different. Baldev is sober and quiet, Dharamveer is vociferous and comic, while Ajith Singh is larger than life, and loud, but very little besides that. In his analysis on *DDLJ* and the *Natyashastra*, Parciack (2016) points out that there is very little character development in the protagonists in Bollywood, and asserts that the reason for this is that the plot is driven by the conflict between *Dharma* and *Kāma*. However, while it appears accurate that the plot is defined by this major conflict, this is the case with most, if not all narratives referred to by the *Natyashastra*. The lack of character development may instead be ascribed to the goal of *Natya*, which is to instruct and entertain. Thus, the characters are delineated as symbol of instructional concepts to illustrate, educate, and entertain, making them both predictable and less than three dimensional. This of course is a direct opposition of the composite figure who undergoes a journey of transformation who is the protagonist following the modern European literary tradition (Parciack, 2016). But even so, not all the characters in the film are one-dimensional. Baldev's character for instance, on the surface, is that of a dictatorial tyrant who seeks to maintain his patriarchal role and his cultural identity, to the exclusion of everything else. But on the other hand, he is also seen to be loving to his wife and children, and a good provider. A deleted scene from the film shows his wife Lajjo explaining why he seldom laughs. She explains that someone tricked them and took all their savings as they made the immigration journey, and the incident has embittered Baldev and robbed him of

his easy laughter. Raj, is also shown as similarly complex. He is the quintessential playboy rich kid, but he is also the honorable “Hindustani,” who won’t take advantage of a drunk girl. These are characters with inherent contradictions.

DDLJ is an easy film to watch and absorb. It does not meander through space and time, and the western notions of the unities are maintained. And while the songs are dream sequences or fantasies, the audience remains fully aware of this, and appears to care very little for the apparent lack in realism. The lack of realism in the film categorizes *DDLJ* as largely belonging to the *Natyadharmi* (the more stylized and symbolic version of reality) type of performance, with human behavior being more or less portrayed naturally like in the *Lokadharmi* type. The *Natyadharmi* type is particularly seen in scenes like those between Raj and his father in the beginning when Dharamveer Malhotra celebrates his son failing high school. However, the *Lokadharmi* type of production is stricter in its portrayal of gender roles. In *DDLJ*, gender roles are clearly defined, and even articulated. Simran’s mother tells her of the “woman’s lot in life” and how she must play the role society lays out for women. Indian society is also inherently patriarchal, and gender roles are more strictly enforced and performed. For instance, in the film, the head of Simran’s family is the strict Baldev Singh, whose wife Lajwanti is a housewife, and together with his two daughters, they uphold the Indian culture and values that Baldev Singh has deemed appropriate. Simran and her sister understand and conform to these values, with occasional outbursts of their Western upbringing only in the presence of their mother. This is seen in the scene where Simran and Chutki switch from dancing and listening to Western music to Indian classical music when their father comes home. The desires of the women are fulfilled only at the sanction of the men, and this is considered to be how

“Hindustani” women are meant to act and live. Thus, Simran accepts her father’s choice of groom but pleads for one month before the wedding to live her own life, on her own terms.

The film also centers on a real issue — that of non-resident Indians’ cultural identity and the conflict between *Dharma* and *Kāma* that a lot of Indians face when deciding to enter into matrimony. Ultimately, the film finds resolution in an acceptance of change, but with no resolution of that conflict between duty and love. Baldev appears to realize that a person’s appearance may have nothing to do with a person’s beliefs and values. And he lets go of some of his preconceived notions and gives his consent for Simran and Raj to be together. With its expressions of love and other emotions considered “feminine,” *DDLJ* may be considered a “*Sukumara*” production, but also has elements of the *Aviddha* style where there is emphasis on the creation of the *Vīra Rasa*. The *Samavakara* play is also generally considered to be under the *Aviddha* style. This only means that while *DDLJ* has predominant elements of the *Aviddha* but does not fit into neat boxes of any one category.

Similarly, *DDLJ* also refuses to follow the *Natyashastra* in its dictats on what may not be shown in a dramatic performance, including acts of war, death, grief, mourning, anger, cursing, marriage, or the depiction of a miracle. Even though Simran manages to avoid the ceremony of marriage and even an engagement, there are scenes of the pre-wedding ceremonies within the film. Baldev expresses his anger and commits violence in more than one scene, including when he finds out that Raj is the boy who Simran fell in love with in Europe. Kuljit brings hired thugs to beat Raj up in the scene at the station at the end of the film. This may be considered a scene depicting war.

The DVD edition of *DDLJ* does not begin with an invocation of the gods, merely an indication of the celebration of the twenty fifth anniversary of the production house, the title of the film, followed by the first scene, into which the opening credits are incorporated. The seed of the story or the call to action in the film is early in the film when Baldev receives his friend Ajit Singh's letter, reminding him of the promise made to get Simran married to Kuljit. Simran and Raj's trip and time in Europe is the drop (*bindu*) that takes the plot forward, introducing an obstacle to the call of action being achieved. The episode takes place when Baldev finds out about Simran's feelings for Raj and moves his family to India and extends until Raj himself gets there. Simran and Raj's story is the *prakari*, representing the theme of the entire film, the unification of two young lovers. And the final action in the film is the climactic scene at the end, where Baldev ultimately lets Simran go to be with Raj. And while these scenes fit in with the overall structure of a play as per the *Natyashastra*, each of the characters' journeys fits into the more well-known character arch format of the narrative journey: *Arambha* (beginning), *Prayatna* (effort), *Praptsambhāva* (prospect of success), *Niyataphalaprapti* (removal of obstacles to attain success) and *Phalaprapti* (attainment of the desired goal) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)).

Overall, *DDLJ* is a mélange of several styles and structures. It appears to be predominantly in the structure of a *Samavakara*, but has aspects of both the *Sukumara* and the *Aviddha*. It bears hallmarks of both the *Sattvika* style and the *Kaisiki* style of production, even as it attempts to, and evokes the *Adbutā*, *Śringāra*, *Hāsyā*, *Karuna*, *Raudra*, and *Vīra Rasas*. While it does not directly state it, all the action in the film appears to take place in the time period of within a year, as specified within the *Natyashastra*. Most of the characters featured

within the film, with the exception of the three main characters, may be treated as important characters and get equal screen time. All the characters are seen at the end of the film, with the exception of Raj's two friends, and Simran's friends who went with her on her trip. The film has several messages for the audiences, including listening to your parents; adhering to your *Dharma* (Ethics) and *Parampara* (Traditions); love; and that despite geographical borders, Indians are the same everywhere. The story of young lovers facing parental and familial objections is universal, with the story of *Heer-Ranjha*, and Romeo and Juliet being familiar to all. The only difference here is the twist at the end where Raj is prepared to walk away from Simran in the absence of parental consent. *DDLJ* is thus the retelling of a universal tale, with several subversions. These subversions, like the featuring of an NRI as protagonist and the idea of Raj leaving Simran at the end for the lack of parental consent, along with the emphasis on Indian value systems within the film, came at a time when Indians everywhere were struggling with their "Indian-ness." Perhaps then, a tried-and-true simple narrative and storyline, with some changes, released at the auspicious time is the winning formula for the success of some Bollywood films.

CHAPTER 7

YEH JAWAANI HAI DEEWANI (2013)

Overview

With *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* ([2013](#)), or *YJHD* being a relatively new film, there is very little, or no academic research available about it, making it untouched territory for academic analysis and conjecture. There is also the lack of historical perspective that comes from examining something that is contemporary, in a way that is akin to writing the biography of someone who is still alive. This makes examining this film both daunting and exciting.

Produced over 20 years after liberalization came to India, *YJHD* is produced in the “contemporary” age of cinema. Liberalization changed Bollywood production, and led to the internationalization of Indian production houses or studios, and more importantly, foreign production houses began investing in Indian cinema — perhaps smelling the profits to be had. The first film produced by a foreign production house was *Saawariya* ([2007](#)), a film directed by Sanjay Leela Bansali, and based on a Fyodor Dostoevsky short story. The film was produced by a subsidiary of Sony Pictures Entertainment and was the first to have a North American release by a Hollywood studio. And this was just the beginning. Today, there are many foreign media houses producing films in India include Viacom18, Sony Pictures India, Fox Star Studios, UTV Motion Pictures, Warner Bros. and Walt Disney Pictures ([N. Sharma, 2014](#)). *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani*, which means “This Youth is Madness” was produced by Dharma Productions (owned jointly by Karan Johar and Hiroo Yash Johar) and distributed domestically by UTV Motion Pictures (a subsidiary of Disney), directed by a relatively new director Ayan Mukherji (this was

his second film). The combination of director, producer/director and distribution companies, along with the star power in the film, indicated there was much investment in this film, perhaps indicating that it was destined for box office success.

Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani is from the genre termed the “coming-of-age” films; a genre that was spawned in the wake of the release of *Dil Chahta Hai* ([2001](#)), in the wake of a post-liberalized society. The genre is particularly interesting and is aimed at an audience, which appears to consist mainly of urban young Indians, including millennials and Gen X-ers, from the middle and upper middle class. Like *Dil Chahta Hai* ([2001](#)), *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* ([2013](#)), focuses on contemporary youth culture, represented by a group of friends who have to individually undergo their personal journeys before being brought together at the end of the film for a relationship resolution. The protagonists in the film, who are depicted as worldly, contemporary, and in a sense, global citizens live in the intersection where a lot of young people live today – between Indian traditional values and western liberalism. In a comment on the intersection of Jane Austen and Bollywood cinema, one researcher makes a valid point about how post-colonial citizens live in the intersection between Eastern and Western cultures and traditions ([García-Periago](#)). This is easily applicable to characters from films of this new genre, who are comfortable living in this duality.

Perhaps this comfort emerges from growing up in a country that is steeped in tradition, but in the past twenty years has opened up to global influences. Thus, if India took the first fifty years after independence to define its own cultural identity, it has taken the next twenty years to demonstrate that its global citizens — both from the diaspora and within its borders — are

increasingly at peace with being hybrid citizens. Films of this genre portray a version of the Indian young urban middle class that is real only to very few but is aspired to by many from this social stratum. Most characters in these films are portrayed as being wealthy and independent, in a way that much of young India is not, but aspires to be. The films also appear to portray some disregard for established conventions and traditions, in a way that is not outright rebellion, but indifference.

The “coming-of-age” genre is only one in a newly-fragmented Bollywood industry. For every film that is a hit from this coming-of-age genre, there is a film that reaffirms Indian patriotism, or the Indian cultural identity. In the same year as the release of *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* for instance, there were other hit films, including *Dhoom 3* ([2013](#)) — an action film, *Chennai Express* ([2013](#)) — an action love story between a North Indian and a South Indian, and *Bhaag Milkha Bhaag* ([2013](#)) — the story of Milkha Singh, the Indian Olympic runner who was deeply influenced by India’s partition. What may be understood from the variety of hits within the same year is perhaps a fragmentation of audiences, or perhaps is an indication of the wide variety of tastes within Indian audiences.

The characters in *YJHD* display definite character development. This is direct opposition to previous film characters, as stated by another researcher ([Parciack, 2016](#)). In this film, it is reflected in the devotion of more air time for the journey of the protagonist(s), and in their character development. The idea of individualism, a trait hitherto associated as being Western, is explored in the film. While all four main characters have families, there are only a few scenes in which they are even featured on screen. And yet, Naina and Kabir refer to them often,

making them unseen presences. This indicates that while individualism may be on the rise, the Indian family is still paramount to the definition of one's character, career, and life path.

The personal journey of the characters portrayed in this genre of films could be considered evidence of the global influences at play in Indian society. In both Kabir's family, and in Naina's family, there are parents and their children. There is no evidence of grandparents. In Kabir's family, there is a stepmother, indicating another kind of fracturing of the traditional Indian family unit. Kabir's dislike for his stepmother though is replaced in the end by appreciation, while her responses to him – even in the face of his rudeness – remain cordial, calm, and respectful. The portrayal reflects the increased commonality of the nuclear family and the disappearance of the traditional Indian joint family and the omnipresent extended large Indian family. The film's protagonists may also be seen as symbols of young Indians' increased focus on individuality, independence, and the satisfaction of personal desires and ambitions, as opposed to the previous emphasis on family and familial desires. In this film, this is reflected in the devotion of more air time for the journey of the protagonist(s), and in their character development, something that other researchers have pointed out has not been a part of traditional Indian cinema or drama ([Parciack, 2016](#)).

YJHD also reflects the growing consumerism within Indian society. Deshmukh ([2016](#)) points to the use of Make My Trip (an online travel company) as evidence of brand placement within contemporary Bollywood cinema, and evaluates how well these brands have been integrated into the film narrative. But Make My Trip is not the only brand to be displayed prominently in the film. Another brand that was mentioned many times by name — Roohafza, a

drink concentrate by Hamdard National Foundation — launched a case against the filmmakers, delaying the release of the film by a few weeks, alleging that the mentions contained within the film were negative, and would damage their reputation. Hamdard later won the case, and the filmmakers replaced the name “Roohafza” with “sherbet.”

YJHD Synopsis

The film opens with a collage of scenes of elaborate wedding invitations being dispersed, including one written out for Bunny, and changed to Kabir Thapar (Ranbir Kapoor). Avinash Arora or “Avi” (Aditya Roy Kapur) opens his invitation while having a drink, and Naina Talwar (Deepika Padukone) opens hers and begin to reminisce of times past, spent in the company of her three friends.

There is a flashback to eight years prior to the present, when Naina and her mother bump into Aditi at a supermarket. Aditi is brash, outspoken and free-spirited, and dressed in a short pair of shorts. Naina is a direct foil to her — quiet, reserved, and studious (denoted by her glasses). Naina’s mother disapproves of Aditi (indicating this in her expression and noises) and questions Aditi about her life, even as she provides an endless update on what Naina is doing — which is attending medical school. In the course of the conversation, she finds out Aditi is leaving on a trek to Manali, the details of which are in a brochure that Aditi leaves behind at the supermarket.

Meanwhile, Bunny is shooting a video in the local red-light district of some prostitutes with an international filmmaking team. This leads into the “item number” of the film. He gets

home late, to find his father (Farooque Shaikh) waiting up for him. His father has learned of his trip to Manali, and Bunny is annoyed that his father has snooped through his things. He had lied and said he is going to Lonavla for fear that he would worry his father. Bunny is also seen arguing with his stepmother (Tanvi Azmi), who cautions him against spending all his hard-earned money on frivolity and his friends. Back at their home, Naina's mother continues her tirade about Aditi's character at the dinner table. Naina expresses first her disapproval, then her frustration with her own planned existence in which she feels trapped. Later that night, she looks up, and then decides to go on the same trek as Aditi and her three friends. She leaves her mother a note to find in the morning. At the station the next day, Aditi (Kalki Koechlin) finds Avi watching a cricket match at the station with a bunch of people. As she urges him to get a move on; he says he will not go on the trek. Kabir who arrives then, realizes that Avi has lost all his money by betting on the game. He offers to pay Avi's share, which Avi promptly refuses. The three friends go off together.

On the train, Aditi offers Avi ham-and-cheese sandwiches, which she has made especially for him. He mocks her for having made them, but accepts them. Outside the train, Bunny meets Naina, whom he does not recognize, but attempts to flirt with. On realizing she's his former classmate — "Scholar Naina" — he first attempts to dissuade her from coming and then offers to share his bunk with her when the tour organizer tells her she cannot go because of her last-minute booking. When the train begins to leave, Naina stares into the distance on the platform, lost in thought. She is clearly experiencing some internal turmoil, which she tells Bunny has to do with the fact that she'd never been this spontaneous before. She's afraid. Bunny reassures her and helps her onto the train in a semblance of the train scene from *DDLJ*.

Inside the train, the four are joined by a duo of flirtatious and uninhibited girls — Lara (Evelyn Sharma) and her friend. Lara flirts openly with Bunny, making Naina acutely uncomfortable; while Lara’s friend flirts with Avi, which annoys and upsets Aditi. They begin playing the game, “Never have I ever,” accompanied by drinking. Naina quietly states she doesn’t drink.

In Manali, the two boys attempt to drag Aditi out of bed, accompanied by a loud and bawdy rendition of Jumma Chumma De De (Give me a kiss, it’s Friday) from *Hum* ([1991](#)) Hindi film, the words of which they forget part-way through the song. Naina completes the rendition, first with hesitation and then with confidence, as she feels their acceptance of her grow. She is now part of the group and goes off with them. While exploring, they come upon a temple where Naina says a prayer. As they stand there, a marriage procession goes by into the temple. Bunny announces his “allergy” to the institution of marriage. A series of events ensues for the day, including Naina praying at every temple she encounters, and the four getting into an altercation, from which they run. Quick thinking and skillful maneuvers from Naina help them evade their pursuers.

During the trek the following day, Bunny and Naina compete in a race to get to the campsite first. Naina is in the lead, but Bunny ties her shoelaces together and she is delayed. Later, at the campsite, everyone is invited to a party with some “foreign” trekkers at another campsite. As she leaves, Lara says something mean to Naina, who stays behind with her books. A while later, Bunny returns to the campsite, and finds Naina “studying.” He wants to know why she has not come with the others to the party. At first, she tells him she is not interested in “stupid parties,” but on further probing by him, she confesses that she is interested, but knows

she does not fit in, as she is considered “boring.” Bunny contradicts her belief of herself as boring, explaining he admires her instead for several reasons. They share a moment again, which leads into a song.

The group arrives at the last point in their trek. Bunny wants to climb another peak, but the guide tells them it’s haunted. That night Bunny climbs to the haunted peak, when he is surprised by a sound. It is Naina. The two climb together, with Naina leading the way. At a stop point, Naina asks for a sip of alcohol and gets it from the flask Bunny is carrying. He also tells her of his dreams of travelling the world and shows her his travel scrapbook of all the places he intends to visit. He asserts his need for staying unencumbered by a wife and kids. When they arrive at the peak, both are exhilarated. Naina narrates that that is the moment in which she falls in love. She says a prayer to the local deity and asks for just one thing: Bunny.

Back in the city center, everyone celebrates Holi, included a suddenly exuberant and uninhibited Naina. As the celebration winds down, Naina and Bunny are walking, and it is clear that Naina intends to confess her feelings for Bunny to him, when Avi interrupts them. He is holding an envelope in which there is an admission and scholarship letter for Bunny to attend Northwestern University to study Journalism. Avi is clearly disappointed, as he sees his dreams of opening a pub with his friend evaporate. But Aditi is supportive, adding that it is time they all grow up. Aditi and Avi walk on ahead, while Bunny and Naina follow, talking to each other. Bunny confesses some trepidation over his choice to move, but Naina reassures him, and then asks what Naina was about to say when they were interrupted. Naina says it was nothing. The voiceover by Naina states she knew she couldn’t tell him of her feelings because she realizes

how important his dreams were to him, and that even though she is hurt, she was grateful for the memories. In the present day, the voiceover continues saying that she didn't wait for him to follow her dreams, and that he didn't look back following his. She never saw him again.

In the present day, we see Bunny living his dream. He is a video journalist and travels countries all over the world. He is also shown chasing women, indicating he is still single and unencumbered by a family. He currently lives in Paris and is offered a new job by his boss to host a show where he will spend three months in some of the biggest cities in the world and document his experience. It is here he receives Aditi's wedding invitation.

Preparations for Aditi's destination wedding are in full swing. Aditi meets Avi in the palace hotel, where the wedding is to take place. She asks about his bar venture, and he confesses he is in debt. Aditi tells him not to drink so much, and he tells her not to marry Taran (Kunaal Roy Kapur) because Avi thinks Taran is weird — but concedes he is a good guy nonetheless. Taran meanwhile, takes a dive into the pool fully clothed to rescue his engagement ring, which has fallen in. When he climbs out, he hugs Avi and soaks him as well.

Naina is giving a speech at a cocktail party before the wedding. She provides context on Aditi's betrothal and arranged marriage. She also provides details of how she and Aditi remained friends unexpectedly, despite being very different. She praises Aditi for being a great friend, and as she winds up, Bunny makes a dramatic entrance, which is followed by a song.

Aditi reintroduces Bunny to Avi, who appears deliberately unimpressed. They have a drink and discuss Taran, whom Avi points out is rich. Aditi adds that in addition he is sweet and

loves her. They also touch upon Bunny's movements since he left. Avi and Bunny separate on clearly poor terms. Bunny meets up with Naina by a poolside, and flirts with her a little. Bunny and Naina attend a pre-wedding ceremony the following day, and Bunny takes possession of Naina's phone and finds out she is flirting with someone over text. He is curious, but then assumes it is someone they see near the lake. This person is clearly not "cool," and Bunny leaves Naina in peace. In practicing for and attending the following day's pre-wedding ceremony, they discover that Lara from their trip all those years ago is Taran's cousin.

Bunny and Avi have a big fight before the "Sangeet" — the song and dance pre-wedding event. Bunny never even returned for his father's funeral, and Avi believes that Bunny doesn't care for his friends or anyone else — just himself. Aditi makes them hug and apologize to one another. The three are at the Sangeet, where there is a light-hearted competition between the bride and groom's sides in song and dance. At the end, the friends all end up dancing with one another, and Avi and Bunny decide to let bygones be gone.

Naina and Bunny spend the following day together, exploring Udaipur. As they wander, Naina remarks that this must be like Bunny's life everyday (referring to his extensive travels), to which Bunny retorts that he could never stay tied to one place or one person. The two debate the merits of each lifestyle, with examples. They concede that neither is "right" but that the two outlooks are different. In the end, Naina urges him to live and enjoy the moment, and calls him out on his Fear of Missing Out (FOMO). They take a taxi to return to the hotel, and Bunny begins to talk about his father's death, and why he wasn't there. He was on a trek and had no

wireless signal, and when he returned, it was after the funeral. He expresses regret for missing the funeral and not returning to see his father before he passed on. Naina silently sympathizes.

Bunny returns to find Avi gambling. Through some conversation, he learns Avi's business is failing for lack of funds and offers Avi money. Avi refuses to take the money. Bunny and Aditi talk about her love for Taran and Avi. Her responses indicate that she has made her peace with this arranged match and has slowly begun caring for, and respecting Taran. Bunny goes in search of Naina and finds her next to a pool with Vikram (Rana Daggubati), who is the man sending her flirtatious texts. Bunny promptly behaves badly and jealously. Naina is annoyed. Vikram leaves, and Naina and Bunny are left to argue. Naina confesses that she cannot spend more time with Bunny because she knows she will fall in love with him again. They kiss, but Naina pulls away.

Later as the party winds down, Bunny comes up to Naina and confesses that he loves her, and Naina indicates she reciprocates his feelings. However, she points out that things cannot work for the two of them, not because they're not right for each other, but because their lives are different. She cannot leave her career and her parents behind, and she doesn't expect him to stay behind for her, giving up his dream job. He cannot promise her that either. They hug, and regretfully, Naina walks away, even though it is clear Bunny does not want to let her go. The wedding takes place soon after, and Bunny leaves as scheduled.

At the airport, in the waiting area, Bunny sees a past version of himself, full of dreams and hope. He appears to compare his present self to that past version. He misses the flight, and goes instead to his father's house, where he lets himself in. He sees his father's picture and

flashes back to the past, where he saw his father for the last time before leaving. Bunny knew his father was having a hard time letting him go, but his father still encourages him to pursue his dreams and to go to America. His memories and his father's selflessness make Bunny emotional, and his stepmother consoles him with a hug. The two then talk, and his stepmother reassures Bunny that his father was proud of Bunny for living by his convictions. She says that the best way for Bunny to continue honoring his father's memory is to continue living life on his own terms.

It is New Year's Eve, and Naina is alone in her home with her dog. The doorbell rings, and it is Bunny. He tells her he was worried some other guy would snatch her up, and he has cancelled his plans to return to Paris. He proposes, and Naina accepts. Later, the four friends are on the telephone with each other to ring in the New Year.

YJHD and the Natyashastra

"That which includes good instrumental music, good songs, good recitatives as well as co-ordination of all acts prescribed by the Śāstra, is called an [ideal] production." ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 526](#))

Despite its definition of the ideal performance, the *Natyashastra* acknowledges that in reality perfection or a flawless performance is impossible to achieve, for after all it is produced by human beings. As a contemporary film, in some ways *YJHD* is an ideal production, with a combination of great music and catchy lyrics, the dream team production company of Dharma Productions, the distribution by UTV Motion pictures domestically and Eros International outside India, and star power in the form of an established lead pair with a former romantic

history. But, the “ideal” production elements alone do not guarantee commercial success or acclaim for a film.

Dramatic Success, the *Natyashastra* and *YJHD*

Upon its release, film critic Anupama Chopra criticized *YJHD* for being repetitive, with its pairing of bookish, serious, virginal Naina, who has never smoked or drunk alcohol in her life; with Bunny, the playboy charmer, whose dreams are to travel the world ([Anupama Chopra, 2013](#)). Chopra likens the characters and the basic premise to earlier hit film *DDLJ* and rates the film poorly, indicating in her newspaper review that she does not expect the film to be a commercial success. And yet *YJHD* succeeded beyond the expectations of its writer/director. The question is, why was this film so successful?

The *Natyashastra* has stated that it is important first to identify that a performance appeal to as many people as possible in its various aspects and to tailor a performance to suit an audience. This latter is the factor that appears to have largely contributed to the success of this film. *YJHD* is a film that appeals to urban Indian Millennials (and GenY-ers) born between 1980 and 1995. It may be noted among contemporary Bollywood offerings that newer filmmakers have focused on identifying, and subsequently targeting their content to particular sections of the mass audience. These new offerings have not been immediately traditional or expected. Ayan Mukherji’s first film for instance, *Wake Up Sid* ([2009](#)) was about an older divorced woman and her friendship with a much younger man who has only just finished college and has no professional aspirations or means.

Research on Millennials and GenY in India remains largely confined to the areas of human relations and management. The characteristics described in the existing body of literature describing millennials makes it amply clear why this population was quick to identify with the characters in the film. Unlike the previous Baby Boomer generation, millennials are considered to be less likely to make long-term commitments, desire greater flexibility in their career, prefer to work in teams, and work in areas that matter to them individually ([Parthasarathy & Pingle, 2013](#)). Kabir's priorities and character traits reflect the generation's quest for individualism and greater flexibility in terms of career and choices. However, Kabir achieves this by rejecting several traditional Indian value systems, including that of a close family unit. This is in direct contrast to Naina, who reflects the more traditional Millennial Indian, who is intelligent, educated, and self-aware, but sticks closer to home and chooses a traditional field of study with a stable income. Thus, the characters in the film comprise the dichotomy within which the Indian urban Millennial often dwells and are a big part of the film's appeal, and ultimately to its success.

And certainly, *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* has been a huge success. It made approximately ₹296 crores worldwide at the box office in its lifetime, without taking into account video and audio sales ([Bestoftheyear.in, 2017](#)). And, at the end of 2013, it was said to be the fourth highest grossing Indian film of all time (this record has since been broken) ([Koimoi.com, 2013](#)). But most indicative of its popularity is that even four years after its release, in 2017, it is still described as a film to which Indian millennials have been able to relate ([Bestoftheyear.in, 2017](#)). The soundtrack of *YJHD*, which was released prior to the film, was also

well-received, with “Badtameez Dil” considered one of the top songs of the year. However, sales figures for the music are not available to evaluate separately.

The success of films in Bollywood tends to depend partially upon the “chemistry” between the lead pairing within the film. *DDLJ* for instance, was the second film to use the successful pairing of Shahrukh Khan and Kajol — a pairing that has been repeated since in subsequent box office hits including *Kuch Kuch Hota Hai* ([1998](#)), *Kabhi Khushi Kabhi Gham* ([2001](#)), *My Name is Khan* ([2010](#)) and *Dilwale* ([2015](#)), among others. Similarly, Deepika Padukone and Ranbir Kapoor were first well-received in *Bachna Ae Haseeno* ([2008](#)). The couple then went on to date in real life, and publicly break up, leading to much curiosity and speculation among their fans about the outcome of their relationship, something that was widely covered in the publicity for the film ([Cafe, 2013](#)) and may have brought some viewers to the theatres. The producer of the film, Karan Johar attributed at least part of the success to the great number of theater screens devoted to the release, the release of the film coinciding with several holidays, and the aggressive marketing campaigns that take place these days in the run up to a film’s release ([Indiatimes, 2013](#)). The director of the film, Ayan Mukherjee, stated that while he was thrilled by the film’s success, he was also surprised by the extent of its success and attributed part of the film’s success to it not being a typical narrative ([Choudhary, 2013](#)). He claimed that he did not intend it to have a classical plot structure, but that he focused more on creating emotions within the audience using certain characters and situations ([Choudhary, 2013](#)). Mukherjee has stated the film is based on the philosophy that people experience deep happiness when put in certain situations ([Choudhary, 2013](#)).

The factors attributed to the film's success by the director and the producer of the film makes one thing clear: the determinants of success of a performance are no longer just limited to the actors, the narrative, the music, etc. While these determinants are still factors for success, there are other economic considerations that have become admittedly more important. The timing of a film's release, the timeliness of its themes and characters, the nature of its release, and the size of its star appeal are all large parts of its success. Producer Karan Johar perhaps summed it up best when he asserted that the success of a film cannot ever be predicted because, sometimes, despite a hit pairing of actors, a large budget, costumes, and a great narrative, there is something ephemeral that a film lacks because of which the audience fails to make a connection with a film. And when there is no connection with the audience, a film may be considered a failure.

Rasa and YJHD

The failure to make the connection with the audience is reflected in whether or not a film is able to create *Rasa* in the audience. This researcher asserts that *YJHD* manages to create *Rasa* in its target audience. It is stated in the *Natyashastra* that *Rasa* is created through a combination of the psychological states (*Bhāvas*), the histrionic/physical representation, the practices (*Dharmi*), the styles (*Vritti*), local usage (*Pravritti*), success (*Siddhi*), the musical notes (*Swara*), instrumental music (*Ātodya*), songs, and the stage ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

In the very first scene where Naina is seen reminiscing about her friends and the trip they took together, she is seen in a gesture that is poignant; her eyes are downcast, she is seen concentrating on her box of mementos, and her head is slightly bent. It is a gesture indicating she is wistful, and yet her memories are happy ones. She displays the same look when she

hears Bunny's voice as he is first heard at Aditi's wedding, before he is seen on stage. She is a woman in love. Her eyes are wide, but she does not meet his eyes. The *Natyashastra* is incredibly detailed in describing how women in particular are supposed to act when in love, or in the throes of strong emotion, and these are just a few instances. In *YJHD*, these gestures, and facial expressions are particularly easy to note. The film tends to focus on the faces of the characters and to emphasize their emotions. There are plenty of close-up shots, including in the songs. These are emotional and poignant, and evoke rasas like *śṛṅgāra* (meaning "romance" or "passion"); *hāsya*, (meaning "comedy" or "laughter"); *karuṇa* (meaning "compassion"); and *adbutā* (meaning "amazement"). The scenes between Bunny and Naina evoke *śṛṅgāra* and *hāsya*. When Bunny and Naina first meet in the film at the station, the exchange provokes laughter, but quickly transitions to compassion as Naina finds it hard to get on the train because she has never done something outside her comfort zone before. This is repeated in the film when Bunny and Naina talk later before Aditi's wedding. At first, they are lightheartedly flirting, but this quickly transitions into seriousness and compassion for the pair. The audience is rooting for them to succeed but fears they won't, and thus compassion is evoked.

Aditi's dynamic with Avi evokes *karuṇa*, *raudra* and *bībhatsā*. Aditi's character clearly cares for, and is in love with Avi, but this is clearly a one-sided relationship. Aditi makes ham-and-cheese sandwiches for Avi, which he has no qualms about "sharing" with the two unknown girls that he picks up in the train. Later, we see him go off with another girl during the Holi celebrations. Hurt is clearly reflected on Aditi's face, and the audience feels her sadness, and responds with compassion for her, and anger and revulsion to Avi's blithe treatment of her.

The *Natyashastra* ascribes the color light green with depicting love and affection. However, for a generation raised with Hallmark hearts and Instagram filters, candlelight and orange/yellow filters are immediately synonymous with romance and love. Bunny and Naina are often seen in this kind of lighting, from the fireside at the campsite where Naina first realizes she has feelings for Bunny, to late in the film when he proposes to her. The lighting is low and reminiscent of candlelight and fire. The *vyabhicāribhāvas* that are associated with *śṛīṅāra* are evident in the scenes depicting the growth of affection between Naina and Bunny. Both faces appear softer, Naina's lips part, and she steals glances at Bunny as he speaks to her (48:40). The camera catches expressions on the characters' faces and their gestures and physical interactions with each other, all of which contributes to the audience being "intimately" acquainted with the characters and thus contributes to *Rasa*. The physical interactions among the four friends makes it apparent as well that these characters are close. It also makes it apparent that this generation is more comfortable with physical contact than previous ones.

The *Natyashastra* has asserted that a successful performance should appeal to as many audience members as possible. However, it also specifies that some sentiments are more appealing to certain segments of audiences; like young people liking romance and depictions of love, and "*common women, children and uncultured persons are always delighted with the comic sentiment and remarkable costumes and make-up*" ([Ghosh, 1967, p. 520](#)). In the case of *YJHD*, it appears that a part of its success lay in its targeting of millennials and young people, who formed the main viewership of the film.

The first part of the film is set in “Manali.” This setting contributes to the *Rasa* created by the film. The evidence for this is in the spike in visitors to Manali and other places shown in the film in the months after the film’s release, who were keen to recreate the experience ([Khader, 2017](#)). In fact, the spike in sales and the emulation of the characters’ clothing and other accoutrements are another indication of the film’s success in creating *Rasa*. For instance, “Naina glasses,” or the style of glasses worn by Deepika Padukone’s character in the film became ubiquitous in eyeglass stores as well.

Succinctly, when *YJHD* is reviewed for its creation of *Rasa*, it is clear that the film is successful. The creation of *Rasa* in this film is through the actors’ expressions and gestures and through lighting, as well as the relationship between the characters. The physical setting as well as the youthful appeal are also contributors to the creation of *Rasa*. The success of the product placement in the film is a tangible indication as well of the creation of *Rasa* in the audience, essentially opening up the possibility for future research in the area of “subliminal” messages and the *Natyashastra*.

***YJHD*, plot and the structure of drama**

Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani begins with an invocation to the gods, by both Eros International as well as Dharma Productions. The invocations are clearly to the Hindu gods. This is followed by the delivery of wedding invitations to the main characters. When Naina receives her invitation, she begins to reminisce about old times, and immediately is established as the narrator for the film. It is her voice we hear as the film progresses, reporting on the passage of time, as well as providing context and background. She is the *Sutradhar*, or the narrator, and she helps the audience navigate between the time and space paradigms within the film. This

film does not adhere to the Western notions of Time and Space, but in the manner of most Indian narratives moves between past and present with great alacrity.

As a contemporary film with a distinct lack of narrative, *YJHD* is not easy to categorize based on the *Natyashastra*. But, most Bollywood films contain elements of one or more kinds of performances, and *YJHD* is no exception. *YJHD* may loosely be categorized as a *Nāṭaka*.

“[The play] which has for its subject-matter a well-known story, for its Hero a celebrated person of exalted nature and which describes the character of a person born in the line of royal seers, divine protection [for him], his many superhuman powers, and exploits such as, success [in different undertakings], and amorous pastimes, and which has suitable number of Acts (aṅka) and Introductory Scenes (prāveśaka) is called a Nāṭaka.”

[\(Ghosh, 1967, p. 356\)](#)

Bunny, or Kabir, is the Hero of the film. The Hero of a *Nāṭaka* is supposed to be of the royal family, or from a long line of seers. Bunny’s name — Kabir — indicates he is named after the seer Kabir, a 15th century seer and poet, who bridged Hinduism and Islam. Kabir and other mystics like him are seen in India as symbols of religious secularism in the way that they have brought multiple faiths together, while rejecting more extreme tenets of any faith. Many of them descended from royalty, much like the Gautama Buddha. Over time, their followers have ascribed miracles and other superhuman powers to them, making them canonical saints. They are well known in popular culture. Bunny’s name is just one of many indicators that he is the Hero of this *Nāṭaka*. Other indicators are how his life appears charmed even as he follows the

path to realize the vision he has for his own life and ambitions. He is successful, good-looking, and is shown as having “amorous pastimes.”

Other indicators that the film is a *Nāṭaka* are in how the film is divided up into a series of incidents, each of which is seen to advance the plot, even if they are not depicted in chronological order. These may correspond to the *Aṅka* (acts) within a play. But it is the presence of the various *Prāveśaka* that truly distinguishes *YJHD* as a *Nāṭaka*. The narrative moves smoothly from scene to scene, with most scenes having either Naina or Bunny in them. But there are a few scenes without these two. For instance, the scene with Aditi and Avi at the railway station establishes their dynamic and reveals that Avi has a problem with gambling (00:18:50 – 00:19:30). A later scene in the film between Aditi and Avi establishes her romantic nature and hope for a “love marriage,” where Avi is more cynical and smooth, which moves into establishing Bunny’s contempt for the institution (00:33:00 – 00:33:50).

Short explanatory scenes between the other main characters, as well as between Bunny (and sometimes Naina) with other tertiary characters like their parents and those around them, are instrumental in moving not just the narrative ahead, but also in creating *Rasa*, which is the ultimate goal of any performance. Bunny’s scene with his father (2:22:00 – 2:24:36) is particularly poignant to this researcher. Bunny watches his father clearly upset at the thought of his son leaving for the USA. His subsequent exchange with his father clearly illustrates the push and pull of a lot of Indian parents and their children, as they leave for higher studies. There is a resistance, sacrifice, and guilt in both parties. And if the goodbyes are permanent, as in Bunny’s case, the guilt is mixed with shame ([A. Mukherjee, 2013](#)).

There is no “bad” guy in the film. This is not a film where good triumphs over evil, and the hero fights off bad guys to win the hand of the fair maiden. Rather, it is the story of the Hero. There is no distinct main plot (*aadhikarika*) or sub-plot (*prasangika*) in the classical sense. Instead, Kabir and Naina comprise the main plot, while Aditi and Avi comprise the sub-plot. The progression of the narrative is not as described in the *Natyashastra*, with the *beej* (seed), *bindu* (drop), *pataka* (action), *prakari* (episode), and *karya* (final action). However, it is possible to see the narrative in terms of the *Arambha* (beginning), *Prayatna* (effort), *Praptsambhāva* (prospect of success), *Niyataphalaprapti* (removal of obstacles to attain success), and the *Phalaprapti* (attainment of the desired goal) ([Rangacharya, 2014](#)), if the meandering through time is ignored. The narrative can then be taken to begin with the trip to Manali by the four friends, followed by the realization that Bunny is to leave and go to the USA. The four friends attempt to follow their individual destinies, until they are reunited by Aditi’s wedding. Bunny has just found out that he is to host his own travel show, which is one of his ultimate career goals. The obstacle now is that he realizes he is in love with Naina, who won’t and cannot leave her work and life to be with him. In the end, he gives up his travel show to be with her, indicating he prioritizes being with her over his career goals. He also makes peace with his guilt and his past, regarding Avi and his father. The film does appear to follow the *Natyashastra* in one aspect — all of the action takes place in the course of a year (especially if the flashback scenes are all taken to be memories).

In terms of style, *YJHD* combines the *Natyadharmi* and the *Lokadharmi* styles, with artistic license being taken in some respects. Only one of the forbidden phenomena described in the *Natyashastra* is depicted in the film: a marriage. Other than that, all deaths and

catastrophes are not portrayed on-screen. There is liberal use of dance and music in the film, with all the songs appearing naturally as a part of the narrative. Overall, *YJHD* is a tightly edited film, with a weak narrative, but strong characters. It is also a distinctly Hindu film, despite Bunny's real name. Naina is shown as being religious, at least in the beginning. But the film, its success, and its appeal are all indicators of the changing tastes of Indian audiences, the fragmented nature of Indian audiences, and the increased cosmopolitan/global outlook of most young Indians.

The fragmentation of Indian audiences and the success of films such as *YJHD* makes it apparent that there is a fragmentation of Indian society as well. If some Indian youth are comfortable dwelling in the dichotomy between Indian tradition and western permissiveness, others have difficulty straddling this divide. This is seen in the success of films reaffirming Indian traditional values and religion. This also results in smaller audiences for each hit film, reflected in lower box office earnings. It appears that no more is any film an unqualified success or "hit."

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSION

An exploratory study may not include any definitive or generalizable conclusions, but this critical analysis provides initial insight into the investigation of Bollywood cinema as a significant body of media that requires further investigation. Popular Indian cinema clearly holds elements of its origins, even these elements are decreasingly obvious.

Dramatic Success and the *Natyashastra*

The diversity of the Indian population and its diaspora has increasingly contributed to the variety and the quantity of films released by Bollywood. It was estimated that the Indian film industry would grow from \$2.32 billion to \$2.89 billion in 2017 (only within India) in terms of profit. Of this, theatrical runs were estimated to account for 74 percent, which was estimated at \$1.78 billion in 2016 and \$2.13 billion in 2017. While this amount is not as big as Hollywood figures, Bollywood cinema is clearly thriving in terms of theatre-going audiences ([Frater, 2016](#)).

This is because the *Natyashastra* emphasizes that the communal experience is important for viewing dramatic performances. It is possible that *Rasa* may be experienced differently when people are together. It also appears that the collective experience intensifies the effects of *Rasa*. Viewing films in a quasi-public space in a group may affect the experience of a spectator, encouraging certain kinds of meaning-making, and suppressing others ([Banaji, 2006](#)). It was found that the collective experience of anger, amusement, pity, patriotism, etc., reaffirmed group identities, values and beliefs ([Banaji, 2006](#)). Bollywood audiences have been

reaffirming their Indian identities through the consumption of Hindi films. Past studies have even confirmed how the performance, viewing and experience of watching Bollywood films helps expatriate Indians reaffirm their cultural roots and feel connected to their identities and values. *DDLJ*, a film that repatriated the NRI, was one of the first films to portray the expatriate Indian in a positive sense. The film is a clear indication of how both Bollywood filmmakers and audiences have used the medium to reinforce and reiterate values and beliefs.

Movie theatres, as mentioned before, are areas of communal gathering to watch films, and it has been observed that audiences are united in their experience as they consume the medium of film. This has especially been reported in screenings of the cult movie classics, including *Sholay* ([1975](#)) and *DDLJ* ([1995](#)). In 2017, with the release of *Baahubali 2* ([2017](#)), Indian cinema goers showed their devotion for the theatre experience once again, with every single show being sold out for a film that was in fact a sequel ([Mirror, 2017](#)). This idea of the dramatic performance helping to create a feeling of unification in the audience is unique to the *Natyashastra* and warrants more scrutiny in a separate study in the future.

The success of drama in the *Natyashastra* is said to depend on the performance elements appealing to as many people as possible, and can be of two kinds: divine (*daivikī*) and mortal (*mānusi*) ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Of these, the divine appears to be placed in higher regard, and relates to the deeper aspects of dramatic structure, and to those spectators from a higher order, i.e. those who were educated and considered cultured ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Meanwhile, the mortal success of drama was more concerned with the superficial aspects of drama, and more

“average joe” type spectators. Both kinds of success are important. Thus, appeal to a diverse mass audience is important.

Indian cinema has somehow managed to straddle that fine line between love for the kitschy over-the-top musical like *DDLJ* ([1995](#)), the curry western like *Sholay* ([1975](#)), the millennial-appealing *YJHD* ([2013](#)) and the later hit film *PK* ([2014](#)). The same audiences appear to enjoy all the genres of films that Bollywood produces. While the *Natyashastra* states that performances must be designed to appeal to mass disparate audiences, it may also be that over time, Indian audiences have become conditioned to be able to enjoy all the different kinds of films that are produced by Bollywood. Very few researchers have analyzed Bollywood from the perspectives of its audiences ([Srinivas, 2002](#)), and the limited research in this area needs to be updated, taking the changing Bollywood landscape into consideration.

On the basis of this critical analysis, this researcher would say that Bollywood films likely appeal to different aspects of an individual spectator — some films may appeal for their setting (*Chennai Express* ([2013](#)) for its South Indian setting, and *DDLJ* ([1995](#)) for its depiction of Punjab), others for the emotions portrayed, and still others for the characters (*Sholay* ([1975](#))). Certainly, Indian audiences have repeatedly indicated their liking for different kinds of films. For instance, the other hit film in the same year as *Sholay* ([1975](#)) — *Jai Santoshi Ma* ([1975](#)) was a religion-themed fantastical film. *Bharata* has stated that the various types of spectators would indicate their responses to a film in different ways; but a deeper investigation could indicate whether disparate audiences — for instance, those more educated and those less educated — would actually comprehend the films in different ways, taking away entirely separate media messages. This could be examined in a future quantitative study.

The idea of a formula in Bollywood film may emerge from the theory of success articulated within the *Natyashastra*. It has been stated that a performance has the best chance for success if a certain set of criteria are met. This coupled with positive audience reception to a performance, which in turn indicates the creation of *Rasa*, makes it clear when a performance is successful. Indian films often speak of and to a specific societal need of the times or connect with the collective contemporary psyches of the audience ([S. Desai, 2015](#)), tending to focus more on the “unconsciously perceived fantasy, rather than the consciously perceived story” says Sudhir Kakar ([in S. Desai, 2015](#)). Many Indian films portray urban middle-class life in such a way that it is an aspiration for some, a fantasy for others, and a reality for very few. A film like *YJHD* illustrates this concept.

The Bollywood ecological system encompasses the people, practices, values, and technologies involved in its production all within the larger local environment ([Nardi & O'Day, 1999](#)). Similarly, the *Natyashastra* indicates the various parts of a dramatic performance all contribute to its success. This includes the actors, the characters they play, the emotions they convey, their gestures, the music and the stage, the preliminaries, the plot and structure of the play, and the producers. In addition, today, factors like release date, film distribution, and star power also play a role in determining the success of a film. Banaji ([2006](#)) points out that context is important in the experience of Hindi films. The films produced by the Bollywood ecosystem continue to emerge fast and furious.

An early scholar of the *Natyashastra*, Sylvain Levi stated that one of the main ways in which *Natya* differed from the western notion of drama was in the way it treated the ideas of “spectacle” and “action,” stating that there was no clear demarcation between these two

components in Indian drama, unlike in Western drama ([in Ghosh, 1967](#)). This is consistent with certain expressions contained within the *Natyashastra*, which translate to “they danced a play.” In Aristotle’s notion of drama, the plot and action were considered vastly superior to “spectacle.” *“Terror and pity may be raised by the decoration “the mere spectacle; but they may also arise from the circumstances of the action itself; which is far preferable, and shews a superior poet”* ([Donaldson & von Schlegel, 1860, p. 170](#)). One of the reasons for the prioritization of spectacle over plot and action is the emphasis on emotional experience and the need to appeal to a wide variety of audiences, some of whom may not speak the language in the film. Many of the audience members of Bollywood films in the diaspora may not speak the language, but manage to, and indicate their enjoyment of the films. The appeal of these films may lie more in the visual spectacle, the emotional experience, and being part of the cultural context. What would be interesting at a future date, would be to examine the degree and quality of differences between the experience of someone in-culture versus someone outside the culture. Through the course of this study, it is found that those raised within the Indian culture tend to absorb and understand those aspects of the film that have culture-specific meaning or values more easily. This was found to be true when the researcher watched films with a mixed group; those who had experience and understanding of Indian culture tended to understand more of the film’s nuances than someone who remained wholly unfamiliar with it. Thus, cultural context tends to influence understanding, positive reception, and perhaps the intent to consume the films in general. This is consistent with a finding that ecological contextual factors tend to contribute to use and adoption of technology as a whole ([Williamson, 2005](#)). In the future, a study to examine the factors most likely to influence

understanding and intent to consume Bollywood films may be carried out. For instance, while it is noted that having familiarity with Indian culture contributes to understanding and appreciation, it may be equally interesting to note the other demographics of the average Bollywood film audience member in terms of age, education, religion and socio-economic levels. This kind of large-scale study has never been undertaken but is important for understanding the reach of these films.

***Rasa* in Bollywood Film**

The Bollywood film industry provides ample evidence of the use of *Rasa* technique. An examination of a sample of Bollywood films has shown that they blend a range of emotions into the film's plot, including, love, passion, fear, worry, ecstasy, bravery, and levity – complete with grand stories set against scenic backdrops ([Gulzar & Chatterjee, 2003](#)). The use of this technique of “all-in-one” is one that has precluded the formation of clear genres within Bollywood film. Most Bollywood films cannot be categorized as strictly tragedy or comedy; they may be dominantly a comedy or a tragedy, but most are a glorious hodge-podge of many elements – and the reason seems apparent. The *Natyashastra* states that dramatic success lies primarily in mass appeal ([Ghosh, 1967](#)).

The notion that a play or a dramatic piece as having mass appeal in the time of the *Natyashastra* is certainly unique. The backbone of success in the *Natyashastra* lies in the creation of *Rasa* within an audience. Despite the formulaic product offerings, complete with song-and-dance sequences, theatres showing Bollywood films are still mostly full. The formula, thus is successful. *Rasa*, though difficult to qualify and quantify is clearly indicated in audiences going back to the theatres to watch films with which they feel a connection. It also lies in

audience adoption of the contents of the films, music sales, copying of fashion within the films, or increased sales of products placed within the films. Srinivas ([2002](#)) has found that Indian audiences are unique in their theatre-going habits, with repeat viewing of a film being considered a normal indication of appreciation for a film, as well as active vocal and physical responses during viewing being perfectly acceptable.

Some researchers have found that audiences had a high emotional response (as reflected by brain activity) as they watched a Bollywood film, specifically scenes of violence, romance, and sex ([Schaefer, Pathakamuri, Sammut, & Karan, 2013](#)). While the researchers made no attempt to qualify the emotions aroused, instead labeling them as positive or negative, they did quantify the intensity of the responses. This was seen to be highest among those who watched the violent scenes. The scenes used in the study did not come from any of the films used in this study, but the researchers found the results to be consistent in their sample ([Schaefer et al., 2013](#)). Similarly, the *Natyashastra* states that specific *Bhāvas* or emotions are perceived to be more attractive to certain kinds of people ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). This is also in line with media studies using social identification theory, where it has been postulated that users of media tended to favor genres and messages that were in line with the way they identified themselves. Thus, women tended to favor romances and comedies, men tended to like action/adventure type films, and older people tended to favor a wider range of films, but tended to mark as favorites films they tended to identify with at different times in their lives ([Fischoff, Antonio, & Lewis, 1998](#)). With their something-in-it-for-everyone approach, Bollywood films are designed to appeal to a wide variety of Indian audiences.

In terms of *Rasa* and the three films in this study, it was found that all three films evoked responses within the viewing audiences. Repeat audiences, box office success and their longevity are indicators of the connection that Indian audiences felt with the films. This idea of *Rasa* is unique to the *Natyashastra*, and in this dissertation has been used to evaluate Bollywood film. However, the theory of *Rasa* may be expanded and used to understand why some films are bigger successes than others. The ephemeral, tenuous connection between audience and performer must be deep enough to sustain interest for the duration of the film, and if the connection is deep and impactful enough, will bring a viewer back for a repeat experience. Thus, it would be interesting to apply, compare, and quantify the elements that attract and/or repel audiences in terms of films. This may even yield that elusive “formula” that predicts success and would provide a new perspective through which to evaluate film and television offerings.

The theory of *Rasa* provides a foundation for a new affective theory in film criticism. It is recommended that the theory should be further examined and developed for a new perspective in evaluating film and television offerings. This researcher believes that *Rasa*, along with the factors for success identified in the *Natyashastra*, could provide better insight into evaluating cinema in general.

On Plot and the Structure of Drama

Indian cinema is heavily dependent on dance (*nritya*), song (*gita*), and instrumental music (*vadya*). The *Natyashastra* has specified that there are different kinds of dance, music, and song to indicate the different *Bhāvas*, to create *Rasa*. In the three films in this dissertation, there are various modalities in the song, music, and dance within each film, and across all three

films. Some of the songs are sad, others are happy, and others are romantic; they intend to create a certain mood, and use gestures, colors, settings, and expressions to express and create the mood intended. And while the number of songs may have decreased in newer films, there are few films that leave them out altogether, which confirms to this researcher that performance in the Indian context is still intrinsically bound with song, dance, and music.

Similarly, the traditional motifs used in Indian performances continue to be used in cinema. The *sutradar* (the “indicator” or narrator, if this is a person) sets the tone of a scene or indicates the arrival of a specific character. The arrival of Gabbar (in *Sholay*) is indicated by his distinctive ditty, and Simran (in *DDLJ*) indicates the direction of her thoughts about Raj with a small ditty. The title of *YJHD* derives from an older film song title featuring Ranbir Kapoor’s uncle, and as the ditty of this song plays in the film, the audience recognizes it and remembers the familial connection.

This kind of conscious viewing is unique to Bollywood. It is part of the structure of performance described in the *Natyashastra*, where it is stated that the audience, while enjoying the experience, is still always conscious of, understands, and accepts that what is before them is not reality, but a performance. This awareness or conscious viewing does not appear to detract from the audience’s enjoyment, but adds to it, making the audience a part of the story. This is rarely the case with Western audiences, where the idea of watching a film is an individual experience, akin to reading a book. In the instance mentioned above with Ranbir Kapoor, it indicates the audience not only appears to appreciate having knowledge of the history of the song, and the actor’s familial history with it, but is also conscious that the actor is playing a part and is referring on-screen to his real identity. It would appear that there is a

shared enjoyment of this complicit deception that contributes to *Rasa* overall, and thus to the success of the film. Audiences were not as quick for instance to accept the remake of *Sholay* ([Sippy, 1975](#)), which was released in 2007. The film, which was known as *Ram Gopal Varma ki Aag* (Ram Gopal Varma's Flames), was not received well by audiences who felt the remake was a mockery of the original, especially in terms of other actors replacing the originals in the new version ([Masand, 2007](#)).

As mentioned previously, the importance of the Indian context is crucial for complete understanding and appreciation of the films. It is also more than likely that this shared context has created a shared code that provides the audience with a deeper understanding of the content, plot, and structure. The disregard for the unities of time and space does not detract from the enjoyment, or faze the Indian audience, who are well-acquainted with Indian storytelling and the maze of tangential subplots that are all somehow bound to the main plot.

Sholay, *DDLJ*, and *YJHD* all have a main plot (*aadhikarika*) and something resembling a sub-plot (*prasangika*). The sub-plot may not always be well-developed, but sometimes may be integral to the main plot. In the case of *Sholay*, the sub-plot with Soorma Bhopali is poorly developed and abandoned midway through the film. In *YJHD*, the sub plot consists of interactions between the two secondary characters: Aditi and Avi, who are also part of the main plot. The subplot in *DDLJ*, consisting of Baldev's story, is part of the main storyline between Simran and Raj. However, *DDLJ* also makes liberal use of the *Vishkambaka* (the supporting scene which acts as an interlude scene signaling what is about to take place or explains what has just taken place and is essentially a part of the beginning of the play), as well as the *Praveshaka* (scene between two acts of a *nataka* or a *prakarana* that provides

information on the action from the end of the preceding act to the beginning of the following act). In the first scene, Baldev is walking the streets of London, feeding the pigeons at Trafalgar Square and is suddenly transported to the yellow mustard fields of Punjab. These fields are a symbolic *sutradar*, and a later interaction with Raj is an example of a *Vishkambaka*, indicating that his relationship with Raj is likely to be acrimonious.

There are three elements that characterize the movement of the plot: *beej* (seed), *bindu* (drop), *pataka* (action), *prakari* (episode) and *karya* (final action). Similarly, there are five stages (*Arasthas*) in plot development: *Arambha* (beginning), *Prayatna* (effort), *Praptsambhāva* (prospect of success), *Niyataphalaprapti* (removal of obstacles to attain success) and *Phalaprapti* (attainment of the desired goal). An Indian dramatic performance begins with *Purvaranga* (preliminaries) followed by the opening (*Mukha*), the progression (*pratimukha*), the development (*garbha*), the pause (*vinarsa*) and the conclusion (*nirvahana*). The differences between these are too subtle to be really distinguishable, but it would appear that the plotlines in all three films loosely have elements corresponding to these stages. The story arc in all three focuses on the primary characters.

There are certain situations that may not be represented on stage in a performance. These situations have however been depicted on screen, including representation of battle, loss of a kingdom, death, and the siege of a city on stage; as well as the killing of the hero, his flight or capture, or him making a treaty with the enemy, a marriage ceremony, and the occurrence of a miracle. Perhaps the nature of the medium makes these situations easier to depict. There is also no reason provided for this ban on the depiction of these situations, and this researcher

would think that the reason for the rule was for the lack of resources to show events of this magnitude on a stage. Also, given the variety of audience members, it was perhaps considered that the depiction of some of these events would be distressing for some. This rule does not seem relevant anymore.

Plot construction and structure has always been considered audience-specific and audience tailored. Thus, plotlines, content, and structure of Bollywood cinema are concurrent with contemporary tastes, ideologies and styles. In this, it is impossible to maintain strict adherence to the tenets laid down by the *Natyashastra*. Thus, it is the case that only certain elements continue to be visible and relevant, while others are ignored.

Bollywood Cinema, the *Natyashastra*, Song and Dance

While the Indian film industry is largely modeled after the Hollywood film industry in its adoption of the technologies, the studio, celebrity systems, and some of its plot devices, its creators imbued it with something that is uniquely Indian ([Gulzar & Chatterjee, 2003](#)). Today this is perhaps more clearly evident in watching early Indian cinematic products, which borrowed heavily from Sanskrit classical theatre and folk theatre – *raslila*, *nautanki*, and *tamasha* – and always featured the ubiquitous songs, dances, and comic interpolations from traditional Indian drama ([Gulzar & Chatterjee, 2003](#)). The *Natyashastra* confirms that both song and dance are intrinsic to the success of drama. The success of the three films in this study relied on the music and dance contained therein. But it is also immediately apparent that the styles of dance and music borrow from several traditions that make them applicable to a contemporary audience. Similarly, with changes in audience preferences, contemporary

Bollywood films tend to have fewer individual songs in comparison with older films.

Contemporary films have also begun to weave these songs into the credits and tend to focus more attention on the visual aspects of the song. This began with the introduction of cable television and the increasing popularity of music channels in India that are solely devoted to playing Indian cinematic offerings.

The analysis of music and songs in Indian cinema is incredibly complex, given that musical notes, instruments and their combination are all imbued with traditional meaning within the *Natyashastra*. Given the breadth of the musical offerings even within this tiny sample of three films in the case studies herein, it is clear that popular Indian music has developed and absorbed more than the *Natyashastra* has specified, especially in terms of style and instruments used. There is some nascent research, and more recently a comprehensive study on the development of Indian film music ([Morcom, 2017](#)), but nothing which examines its development in terms of musical traditions.

The same is also true of dance in Indian cinema. The *Natyashastra* is detailed in its description of gestures, expressions, makeup, dance, and costume. *Nritta* and *Nritya* are the two classifications of how the body may be used to express oneself in *Natya*. The former is intended not to convey specific messages or emotions to spectators, but to add beauty through the use of patterned delicate gestures. Helen's movements in the song "*Mehbooba Mehbooba*" in *Sholay*, or Deepika Padukone and Ranbir Kapoor's gestures in "*Diliwale Girlfriend*" in *YJHD*, for instance, are clear examples of *Nritta*. However, another song in *Sholay*, "*Jab Tak Hai Jaan*," featuring Hema Malini, is woven with the narrative, and Malini, a classically trained *Bharatnatyam* dancer uses purposeful hand and feet gestures to convey her distress at dancing

for Gabbar. On one hand, contemporary life makes much of the tenets on dance in the *Natyashastra* obsolete, at least when it comes to incorporating them in popular film, on the other hand, traditional Indian dance forms have survived, and are appreciated, practiced and studied on their own in India and among Indians in general. But, they have not translated well insofar as their being incorporated into popular culture is concerned.

Bollywood Cinema and Religion

The three films appear distinct when viewed separately, but there are common elements between them, which can only derive from the literary tradition that inspired them. This is because the historical contextual development of a community evidently contributes to the way in which it represents itself in its own mass media. What this also indicates through the films examined is that India may be a constitutional country, but its films espouse a distinctly Hindu philosophy. The portrayal of the values represented by the characters for instance are reiterated within the *Natyashastra*, including those of duty, love, attachment, respect, and guilt. In other words, the messages of the films are similar: good things happen to good people, and bad fortune goes hand in hand with evil. This is coupled with the notion of Karma, or fate. When Jai dies, the audience is sad, but they understand that his future would have been blighted by his marriage to a widow. Similarly, when Aditi and Avi do not get together in *YJHD*, the audience is wistful, but understanding. There are open displays of worship of the Hindu Gods, and characters following other religions are secondary or minor characters. Perhaps this trait always existed, but it is increasingly apparent, and in the years since 1992 (the demolition of the Babri Masjid by Hindutva activists), it is jarring to note that minority characters are often portrayed negatively or in a comedic sense. In *Sholay*, the blind imam, his son and Soorma

Bhopali all appear to be Muslim characters. In *DDLJ*, Baldev Singh's family is overtly religious and Hindu, with him flying into a rage when his idol of Laxmi is damaged by Raj. In *YJHD*, the studious Naina carries with her a small idol of *Ganesh* and enters virtually every temple. The *Natyashastra* is strongly Hindu, and this is evident, given its origins and its status as the Fifth Veda ([Massey, 1992](#)). In the years since, however, other religions and faiths have developed and spread in the country, but it is clear that at least in the domain of film, Hinduism is still the primary religion. Questions that arise from this are to ascertain whether Bollywood cinema may be also acting as an evangelical agent for Hinduism, promoting the idea of India as Hindu.

All three of the films under study revolve around relationships, rather than action. This is in keeping once again with Hindu tenets stating that while fate or destiny is predetermined, relationships are a matter of choice (except marriages, which are made in heaven). The changing value systems regarding filial relationships and romantic relationships are evident foci for the films. In *Sholay*, filial relationships between the imam and his son, and the common Indian notion of "adopted" family members, including the brotherly relationship between Jai and Veeru, and the relationship between Basanti and her "mausi" (aunt) are brought into focus. The romantic relationships in the film are indicative of the acceptable norms as well. In *DDLJ*, the filial relationships are clearly evident in Raj's relationship with his father, and Simran's relationship with her father. In *YJHD*, the filial relationship that is most evident is the one between Kabir and his father, and to a lesser degree between Naina and her mother. The changes in acceptable romantic relationships are far more significant in their portrayal. Simran is heartbroken to think she may have disgraced her family when she imagines she may have had sex with Raj in *DDLJ*, while in *YJHD*, the notion of premarital sex is deemed more

acceptable. In *Sholay* however, sex is very lightly implied in Veeru's suggestion of impropriety with Basanti. Jai and Veeru's attitudes are especially revealing in prevailing attitudes to sex, caste, inter-class relationships, and the anger towards the establishment.

Sex, Women, Film and the *Natyashastra*

While this study did not specifically examine the depiction of sex and women in Bollywood and the *Natyashastra*, they are impossible to ignore. The *Natyashastra* makes it clear that women play a subordinate role to men in performances. There is no play described as having a female protagonist, even though the *Īhāmṛga* is a play where the action in the play is caused by the anger of a woman ([Ghosh, 1967](#)). Chapter XXV describes the various types of male and female characters making up a population of "courtesans" who may be in the Hero's circle or be a part of his journey in the performance. Chapters VIII-XIII detail the gestures used to create *Rasa* and communicate the *Bhavas* within a performance. All of the films in this dissertation are male-centric, with female subordinate characters. In *Sholay*, Basanti is a woman who has to work for a living, but Radha's relationship with Jai is fixed by her father-in-law and her father. She is not independent enough to make her own decisions. In *DDLJ*, Simran's father Baldev makes it very clear that he makes the decisions for the women in his family. It is a traditional form of thought, and in *DDLJ* there are no strong independent women. Right to the end of the film, Simran remains under her father's will, only to be with Raj in the end, and only because her father grants her permission to leave. Naina in *YJHD* is a doctor. She is financially independent, fulfils her parents' dreams, but retains her own identity. However, in one aspect, she remains a traditional Indian young woman — her romantic entanglements (other than with Kabir) are never visually depicted in the way Kabir's are shown on screen.

Women are keepers of a family's "izzat" (honor), and audiences would not be accepting of watching a young woman's romantic dalliances.

The depiction of sex in Bollywood is problematic. Most films have few or no direct references to sex and seldom have nudity. This is in line with the *Natyashastra*, as it states that sex is not meant to be shown on stage. However, in Indian cinema, traditionally the sexual act on the screen is closely tied to violence and shame, with women as victims, and the Hero of the film as the savior. On occasion, there are instances where women have been depicted as incarnations of the vengeful goddess Kali or Durga. The idea of a woman as mythical Goddess, delicate flower lover, or long-suffering or dutiful mother are the positive depictions of women. The common negative connotations are the neglectful wife/mother, who prioritizes her career over her family or who lives beyond her means, and the evil mother-in-law. Women are not sexual beings in Indian cinema. This is in line with beliefs in Indian society. A woman must be seen as virtuous and pure. Only then is she seen as worthy of respect.

In recent years, this mentality is changing, with more films portraying issues like pre-marital sex and homosexuality, indicating that these have become more commonplace, and perhaps more acceptable. This change has corresponded with the rise of the Hindu nationalist movement, which seeks to suppress these ideas and often takes extreme action to prevent young people from acting on what they see as Western permissiveness. Thus, sex and women continue to be problematic in terms of Bollywood cinema.

This dissertation, though exploratory has revealed that contemporary Bollywood film has a foundation that lies in the *Natyashastra* but is heavily influenced by other cultures,

media, religion, social mores, and values that have come after the *Natyashastra*. While it is apparent that the *Natyashastra* continues to inform contemporary film, at least in terms of Bollywood cinema, it is also clear that it is not its only influence. The connection between the *Natyashastra* and Bollywood, though not always readily apparent, may be derived through an interpretation of the *Natyashastra* that is in touch with the contemporary cultural and social contexts. In some cases, as in the case of the *Rasa* theory, evidence of support may be found through deeper quantitative and qualitative analysis. Similar evidence can also be found for the theory of success, and this theory could perhaps be used to evaluate the success or lack of it in other forms of contemporary performance and cinematic studies. Future research therefore is greatly needed in this field to yield new perspectives and theories.

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APPENDIX

Phir Bhi Dil Hai Hindustani: Bollywood is India

“...[M]ost readers of this review have never seen a Bollywood movie and don’t want to start now. That will be their loss. It is nothing like [Americans] have seen before, with its startling landscapes, architecture and locations, its exuberant colors, its sudden and joyous musical numbers right in the middle of dramatic scenes, and its melodramatic acting (teeth gnash, tears well, lips tremble bosoms heave, fists clench). At the same time, it’s a memory of the films we all grew up on, with clearly defined villains and heroes, a romantic triangle, and even a comic character who saves the day. “Lagaan” is a well-crafted, hugely entertaining epic that has the spice of a foreign culture.” ([Ebert, 2002](#))

The cinema existed in India before the birth of “Bollywood.” The birth of moving pictures is said to have taken place on December 26, 1895, when the Lumière brothers aired their short program at the *Salon Indien* in Paris ([Bose, 2006](#)). And not even a year later, their show was seen in Bombay on July 7, 1896, by delighted audiences ([Bose, 2006](#)). But if the technology for cinema came from outside of India, the cultural possibilities and the creativity to realize the potential came from within, complete with Indian images and narrative, making it hard to classify or dismiss Bollywood cinema as either real or illusive ([Prasad, 2003](#)).

It has been said that watching Indian films in general helps in relieving the tensions of its mass audiences (psychological catharsis), through the over-the-top melodramatic emotional scenes, and may be considered an “addictive defense” against the hardships of life in India ([S. Akhtar & Choksi, 2005](#)). In doing so, the deeper agenda of Bollywood cinema appears to include elucidating and healing the intra-psychic conflicts of their audience ([S. Akhtar & Choksi, 2005](#)).

Bollywood is India. Kaur ([2002](#)) points to how Indian cinema has always closely mirrored developments in Indian society and culture. But what distinguishes Bollywood from other film industries is its inherent nationalism – the way that it gives India a common voice, a common stage with apparently no regard for religion, language, geographical area or even caste. One of its main distinguishing qualities is its choice to use Hindi as the language of Bollywood ([Bose, 2006](#)). While Bollywood is centered in Mumbai; Hindi is the language spoken mainly in North India, making it a curious choice. Initially Hindi was chosen because it was a language of trade and because most people could understand some or all of it. However, in the years following independence, Hindi was chosen as the national language ([Bose, 2006](#)), a move that was calculated to further the cause of nationalist sentiment through cinema in the wake of the death of colonialism.

The coming of sound, especially music, in Indian cinema changed things forever, with *Alam Ara* being released March 14, 1931 ([Bose, 2006](#)). Music and sound managed to distinguish Indian cinema from any other cinematic universe ([Bose, 2006](#)). For one, music used in Bollywood came from various Indian traditions – both North and South Indian classical music, religious *bhajans* (religious songs, similar to the Christian hymn), and folk music. As time passed, music also was “borrowed” from Hollywood, and from other international sources, including Latino, Chinese, and reggae ([Bose, 2006](#)). Once again though, in incorporating all these musical styles, Bollywood distinguished itself but also became a melting pot of music styles, while still evoking a unified Indian nationalist sentiment.

Booth ([2008](#)) classified the Hindi cinema into three distinct eras: the studio era, which ended with the 1950s; the music director era (roughly from the 1960s to the mid-1970s), and

the transition era, which runs to today. Whatever the era however, Bollywood is credited with creating “brand India,” a vision of secular India, by projecting values that promote inclusion, patriotism, and a sense of “retro-nostalgia” that many find attractive, for its simplicity ([Rajadhyaksha, 2003](#)). Notably, Indian cinema can be credited with an accurate portrayal of the Indian nationalist sentiment.

Bollywood and the Nation(alist)

Three genres of Indian cinema dominated in the decades between 1913 and Independence (1947): the mythological film depicting stories from Indian mythology, the devotional films which tell the stories of poets and saints, and finally, the stunt films with strong female characters ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#); [Gyan, 2010](#)). Any cinema with nationalist sentiments was noticeably absent, mainly due to stringent censorship by the British Raj. Unlike later cinema, these early films were appealing to all audiences, with no regional divides and transcending linguistic boundaries ([Bose, 2006](#); [Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#); [Jaikumar, 2003](#)). While early Indian cinema from the pre-independence era centered on historical and mythological themes, these themes did not carry over predominantly to the period after Indian independence in 1947 ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#)). Instead Indian cinema after independence intentionally propagated a strong nationalist agenda, as if filmmakers and audiences alike were looking toward film to create a sense of identity with a cultural heritage that had to some extent become diluted with subsequent invaders and colonizers.

Immediately post-independence cinema intentionally propagated a strong nationalist agenda, seeking to ease the excessive regional, religious and communal friction that existed in the wake of Independence from the British. Thus, films from this era portrayed secular cultural

value systems, strong family structures, and community spirit ([Rajadhyaksha, 1993](#)). This was further confirmed by the existence of the S. K. Patil Film Enquiry Committee, set up in 1951, as India's first freelance investment sector institution that would provide filmmakers with the funds they required for production. This sector hoped to help in the production of films with a strong pan-nationalist agenda, to instill values of brotherhood and solidarity into the masses. Filmmakers wanting funding from the organization specifically inscribed these values into their films to secure funding ([Rajadhyaksha, 1993](#)). Early Indian films like *Do Bigha Zameen* ([1953](#)) told the story of rural displacement, of losing a home, and of trying to make a new life, echoing the story of so many Indians who had been displaced by Partition ([Kaur, 2002](#)).

The period between the late 1940s (following Independence) and the 1960s is often referred to as the "Golden Age of Bollywood cinema" with some of the most critically acclaimed Hindi Films being produced during this period including, *Awaara* ([1951](#)), *Shree 420* ([1955](#)), *Mother India* ([1957](#)), *Madhumati* ([1958](#)), and *Mughal-e-Azam* ([1960](#)). While *Mother India* was nominated for an Academy Award for Best Foreign Film, the film is notable for many things, not the least of which is that it has been termed all-time classic Hindi film, with its imagery, its stance on Indian values, and its dialogue ([Thomas, 1989](#)). It is also important for its spotlight on the mother in Indian cinema, a symbolic character instantly recognizable to Bollywood audiences ([Rajamani, 2012](#)). *Mother India* ([1957](#)) and other films of this time have come to symbolize how Bollywood clearly distinguished itself from its western counterpart, from whom its name has been derived. Instead, these films come to show Bollywood as more than a genre of film, but instead as a cultural product(ion), which emerges from an inherently defined

cultural value system, and symbolizes the then recent struggle against oppression, and the struggle for freedom ([Rajadhyaksha, 1993](#)).

The portrayal of the mother figure in *Mother India* ([1957](#)) has been held up as a prime example of the deification of the “mother” in Indian culture and society. Mishra ([2002](#)) talks about how the character of *Mother India* ([1957](#)) epitomizes “*Bharat Mata*” or the idea of the nation as the beneficent sacrificing mother figure to all of its citizen, and how this ties in with the Mother Goddess figure of Indian mythology. More recently some critics have noted the differences in treatment of female figures in Bollywood cinema, saying how female characters have been “Indianised” even in remakes of Hollywood films ([Fábics, 2013](#)), others have noted how homoeroticism has been dealt with in some Indian films ([R. R. Rao, 2000](#)). In viewing films such as *Dostana* ([2008](#)) and *Yeh Jawaani Hai Deewani* ([2013](#)), it is immediately apparent how themes of feminism and homosexuality are “Indianized” for national audiences in ways that are unobjectionable to censors and viewers alike. But if “*Mother India*” took care of her sons, films featuring the “Angry Young Man” showed the sons of India trying (and sometimes failing) to take care of Mother India. Rootlessness and a longing for security and belonging may be seen in these characters, as a way to define themselves in relation to home, region, nation and society, especially in a rapidly changing national environment. Major films from this genre include, *Zanjeer* ([1973](#)), *Deewaar* ([1975](#)), *Sholay* ([1975](#)), *Don* ([1978](#)), *Shakti* ([1982](#)) and *Coolie* ([1983](#)) and *Qurbani* ([1980](#)).

While the 1970s and 1980s were devoted to the Angry Young Man, there were other themes being explored by Indian filmmakers: pre-marital sex in *Qurbani* ([1980](#)), illegitimacy in *Masoom* ([1983](#)), and disco in *Disco Dancer* ([1982](#)), and the hippy and drug movement in *Hare*

Rama Hare Krishna (1971). However, curiously even as the filmmakers explored these “non-Indian” themes, the themes were customized to be seen and accepted by Indian audiences, to suit their sensibilities, and were often portrayed in keeping with traditional values. For instance, the main two characters in *Qurbani* (1980) may have been a club dancer and a criminal, who were not married to each other, but they emphasized loyalty, sacrifice and family. *Masoom* (1983) may have been about a woman’s struggle to accept the fruit of her husband’s infidelity, but in the end, family comes first, and she accepts the child. Both films essentially addressed issues previously-considered “un-Indian” or Western societal problems and addressed them in a uniquely Indian context. Skillman (1986) points out something similar in his study on Indian film music – that Indian music directors may have incorporated western music elements in their creations such as rhythmic patterns, melodic figures and instruments, but they combined all of these elements with traditional Indian musical styles to create something distinctively Indian.

An overview of some of the themes that have emerged and been studied in Bollywood was useful in the context of this study, as they elucidated that Bollywood cinema mainly focuses on themes, styles, and social structures that most directly pertain to Indian society. Bollywood reflects Indian sensibilities, and it would not be a stretch to say that it is based on Indian narrative traditions. Some of the common themes in Bollywood remain love, family, marriage, and political conflict. But some periods reflect larger Indian concerns, and it is these that are discussed in the following sub-sections.

1970-1990: Bollywood’s Angry Years

In 1971, Bollywood surpassed all other film centers to become the world’s largest producer of films. Thus, Bollywood cinema had arrived, so to speak. Film as a medium came to

India from its colonial roots but was adopted and transformed in terms of content from within India's borders, infused with Indian images and narratives ([Kaur, 2002](#); [Malik, Trimzi, & Galluci, 2011](#)). And while music directors may have called the shots in the 1960s, the 1970s, it is agreed, this era belonged to the "Angry Young Man" and was characterized as Bollywood's angry years, a time when India, a young democracy, saw rapid urbanization, uneven economic growth, and political instability that led to a general feeling of frustration among "middle class" youth ([Bose, 2006](#); [Kazmi, 1996](#); [Rajamani, 2012](#)). The angry young man era is unique to Bollywood cinema and must be mentioned as comprising a set of successful popular culture films that came to represent the sentiments of a nation. This genre of films, featuring the "Angry young man" character is unique in Indian film history and spanned a period of roughly 15 years. It had a great impact on the male urban population of the lower and upper middle classes, and films of this genre have come to be read as a form of societal mirroring ([Rajamani, 2012](#)). Kazmi ([1996](#)) describes the Angry Young Man as embodying a "fiercely independent Promethean version of a person" and goes on to point out that despite him having a superhero aura, he is a victim of bad luck, fate, religion, mother and country.

The origins of the "Angry Young Man" can be traced back to a theatrical movement beginning in the 1950s with dramatists like John Osborne, Harold Pinter and Kingsley Amis ([Moble, 1992](#)). The movement consisted of several dramatists who railed against the proliferation of upper class characters in drama, characters who were consumed with social norms and conventions of the time, rather than the less-than-desirable reality that lay outside theirs. The "angry young men" dramatists targeted their ire at the dramatists who created

these characters, but more importantly railed at the failure of the present to live up to the past ([Rebellato, 2002](#)).

The “Angry Young Man” in Indian cinema was often synonymous with Amitabh Bachchan, who played him first in *Zanjeer* ([1973](#)). *Zanjeer* ([1973](#)) tells the story of Vijay, an honest policeman, wrongfully accused and framed for a crime he did not commit. After a period of incarceration, Vijay comes out of prison focused on revenge, and the desire to right the wrongs done to him. Other movies saw Bachchan playing a similar character in similar situations.

The period in history when these films came to be made was one of the most profound times of change in Indian society, and events in national politics, and economics affected the middle class deeply ([Nandy, 1998](#)). This began with Indira Gandhi’s election to the post of Prime Minister, and included the period between 1975 and 1977, which is known as the Emergency period. Beginning in the late 1960s was a period that saw an increase in political and communal violence and upheaval, which was further marked by tensions due to poverty, unemployment, and unionized strikes in many industrial sectors ([Rajamani, 2012](#)).

The “Angry Young Man” may be seen as a result of the decline in political stability and subversion of the judicial system, law enforcement agencies and even the system itself, but more likely the emergence of the concept of the Angry Young Man may be seen as a reaction to the fragmentation of the community system in India ([Nandy, 1998](#)). It also may be seen as the voice and experience of the urban poor in India at the time, screaming for change in the system ([Rajamani, 2012](#)). The audiovisual perceptions of the Angry Young Man in Indian cinema have even been seen as a form of public anger management ([Rajamani, 2012](#)) and as a reflection of

violent change from old traditional systems in Indian society to a new, more westernized, industrialized society with a powerful middle class ([Nandy, 1998](#)).

Bollywood: Cable TV and Beyond

On July 24, 1991, then finance minister Of India Manmohan Singh announced the arrival of economic liberalization in India with a quote by French writer Victor Hugo, “No power on earth can stop an idea whose time has come” ([A. Rao & Kadam, 2016](#)). Liberalization opened the floodgates to Indian businesses to foreign investors and brought global exposure to the masses within India. However, liberalization was not without its detractors. While the move was aimed at ending state and local monopolies, and decreasing government intervention in the private sector, it drew the wrath of those who had much to lose in the process. It was met with wide opposition even in the then ruling party (The Congress) but was taken ahead despite the opposition as the only way out of an economic crisis that left India unable to pay its bills to the World Bank ([A. Rao & Kadam, 2016](#)). And in 2016, India marked 25 years post-liberalization, and was labelled the fastest growing economy in the world ([A. Rao & Kadam, 2016](#)). The economy was booming, as was the population, with the country set to surpass China in terms of population by 2025 ([A. Rao & Kadam, 2016](#)).

Cable television came to India in 1991. This changed Bollywood cinema forever, as directors began to fear for their profits from this new trend, which first stemmed from the increasing numbers of VCRs in homes (to watch pirated copies of films), and then from the “cable” channel on television, which illegally showed films in houses ([Dwyer, 2002](#)). The 1990s saw a marked change in India’s economy, with the unveiling of free market reforms, namely the

economic liberalization. These measures by the government created a new strong middle class with more money. India saw more foreign visitors, but also saw more Indians leaving the country to travel abroad. There was a new middle class, with more money for conspicuous capitalist consumption, growing up in an India that had finally managed to gain a platform in the new global economic order ([Kaur, 2002](#)). The middle class of the 1970s and 80s was supplanted by this new middle class, with a new value system. These nouveau riche technocrats, who gained prosperity thanks to the dotcom boom, found it easy to switch from the earlier Nehruvian socialist economy to consumer capitalism, partly because, with the 1998 nuclear tests in India, they now felt more on par with more advanced economies ([Kaur, 2002](#)).

There is little surprise then that Bollywood cinema reflected these new concerns; and old concerns like caste, oppression, worker strikes, and corruption were shelved ([Kaur, 2002](#)). Instead main characters in film were from the upper middle classes and lived in palatial houses ([Kaur, 2002](#)). Themes of repatriation and emigration were more common, with films like *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* ([1995](#)) and *Pardes* ([1997](#)). The most notable film of the decade was the extravagant family melodrama *Hum Aapke Hain Kaun* ([1994](#)).

Some researchers have seen the popularity of a film like *Hum Aapke Hai Kaun* ([1994](#)) as problematic ([S. Malhotra & Alagh, 2004](#)). They have tended to see hit films from the 1990s like *Hum Aapke Hai Kaun* ([1994](#)), *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* ([1995](#)) and *Pardes* ([1997](#)) as symbols of the growing Hindutva trend in India at the time, pointing to the monolithic Indian identity presented herein as Hindu, wealthy, and patriarchal in nature ([S. Malhotra & Alagh, 2004](#)), and reiterate that this image excludes Muslims, Christians, and underprivileged communities, which in turn portrays them as being “non-Indian.” But most researchers have viewed films of this

genre portraying the Indian diaspora as a way to attract new audiences with a picture of a globalized India ([Dwyer, 2002](#); [Rajadhyaksha, 2003](#); [Uberoi, 2001](#)). One thing was certain, the Indian government took no efforts to try for a more accurate portrayal of India, one with a more “Indian” Indian. Instead, in its silence it was complicit in branding India as more global in outlook, but still traditional ([Vasudevan, 2011](#)). These films were seen as a means to repatriate the expatriate, via the medium of popular cinema.

The 1990s also saw the entry of the conscientious filmmaker. Filmmakers like Mani Ratnam who made *Roja* ([1992](#)) and *Bombay*, ([1995](#)), Vidhu Vinod Chopra with *1942: A Love Story* ([1994](#)) and Ram Gopal Varma with *Satya* ([1998](#)) came out with films with strong nationalist themes, based on real historical events and issues. And if films like *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* ([1995](#)), and *Pardes* ([1997](#)), spoke directly to Indians who had migrated to other shores – the expatriate Indian – films with a nationalist message spoke to those who lived within Indian borders, informing them that there were still problems in utopic India that would have to be surmounted.

If the early 1990s reached out to the expat Indian, later 90s-00s films refused to be classified into neat genres. There was something for everyone. The films mostly spoke to urban Indians, but spoke of rural India, of issues concerning the Indian youth. In 2001, the Indian government finally gave Bollywood the legitimacy of being termed a legal industry ([Jones, Arora, Mishra, & Lefort, 2004](#)). This further changed how films were financed, made, and distributed. The 2000s also saw the rise of the multiplex theatre in urban areas, which attracted more theatregoers of the new urban middle class. This new urban middle class steadily became the new theatregoer, and suddenly, the face of the new contemporary India. Educated,

employed, and geographically mobile, this was the face that Indian politicians wanted the world to see as being Indian. While earlier cinema focused on rural subjects and characters, defining them as “quintessentially Indian,” the focus on urban youth suddenly made Indian filmmakers aware that here was a new focus for Indian filmmaking.

In 2001, a little film called *Dil Chahta Hai* ([2001](#)) was released and was a runaway success. It followed the lives of three male best friends from the upper middle class in Mumbai, all of whom were educated, as well as upwardly and geographically mobile. Each character was distinct, with his own parallel story, with one, a financier, being in love with his female best friend, another, an artist in love with an alcoholic older woman, and the third working in his family business and resisting his family’s attempts for an arranged marriage. And even over 15 years later, the characters in the film remain cool, undated, and fresh. A Bollywood blogger who waxed eloquent about the film and its director Farhan Akhtar is spot-on on just why this film remains important: it made the grand ideals of contemporary Indian young people appear real ([Sreehari Nair, 2016](#)). But more importantly, it trivialized what other Hindi films so far had deemed important, and emphasized what had been deemed trivial by filmmakers ([Sreehari Nair, 2016](#)). It emphasized the everyday lives and concerns of Indians who were not at war with themselves, or society, or the religious or political systems in the country. In doing so, it spawned a new genre of Bollywood cinema.

This researcher would call this genre of cinema, the “Cinema of Journeys.” Films of this genre have been very popular in the last ten years, and examples of this genre would be *Dil Chahta Hai* ([2001](#)), *Zindagi Na Milegi Dobara* ([2011](#)), *My Name is Khan* ([2010](#)), *PK* ([2014](#)) and 3

Idiots ([2009](#)). But along with this, there were also box office hits with religious overtones like *Bajrangi Bhaijaan* ([2015](#)), and *Agneepath* ([2012](#)); sports-oriented films like *Lagaan* ([2001](#)), and *Bhaag Milkha Bhaag* ([2013](#)); as well as other films with themes of love triangles, romance, large action romances, and films about Indian history. In this, it may be said that there is a film to suit every taste, but this may also imply the gradual fracturing and fragmenting of audiences.

Films like *Lagaan* ([2001](#)), a film about cricket and fighting imperialism, but contemporarily seen a synonym for fighting the big corporations, drew large diverse audiences, and took India to the Oscars. The newly powerful middle class now travelled more, increasingly frequented movie theatres, and had grown similar to its Western counterparts in its patterns of consumption. Kaur ([2002](#)) feels evidence of this new thinking is best seen in the sudden appearance of weekly celebrity chat/high society columns in newspapers and popular magazines that celebrated the international lifestyle of the newly rich, urban Indians.

Indians were inundated by films and media from America and other places around the world from before independence, but with the advent of cable television, the broadcast medium exploded; this was not just limited to cinema, but also television. At first censorship was lower, and the amount of programming made in India was also low. But what cable television gave to the Indian middle class was a taste of the West. And this researcher contends that this taste only whetted its appetites for more and changed its taste from the traditional to a more hybrid Indo-western outlook.

In the nearly 20 years since *DDLJ* had been made, India has changed. And Bollywood has changed along with it. Cable television was firmly entrenched in every household. The Internet, the super information highway has made its way into virtually every hand. But Indian audiences

have perhaps become pickier than before. One of the reasons for this may be that they are now more spoiled for choice than ever before. Before cable television, viewers had the choice of state-run television, video, and the cinema theatre — none of which were available 24/7. Cable television meant access to shows from America and the UK, all day, every day. But, the problem was, most people didn't speak English. Many cable networks realized this early on, and dubbed American shows were broadcast and consumed with great alacrity. The researcher has watched several American shows only in Hindi, including *I Dream of Jeannie*, *Bewitched*, and *Dennis the Menace*. American soap operas like *The Bold and the Beautiful* were consumed with relish by English speaking housewives, and later dissected over tea and biscuits (the researcher has been present at such discussions). Indian producers saw opportunities and created soaps specifically for the Indian Market; soaps such as *Kyunki Saas Bhi Kabhi Bahu Thi* (Because the Mother-in-Law was also a Daughter-in-Law at some point), and *Kahaani Ghar Ghar Ki* (The story of every household). MTV began its initial broadcasts with American and British Pop music videos but transformed to a Hindi music channel. Indian pop stars began to slowly emerge. There was more experimentation in all forms of media than ever before. But why this is important, is to understand that the film industry has always been a part of the much larger media ecosystem within India; a more complex cultural conglomeration that involves a multitude of players, and factors, from fashion, to fairness creams, to music, food, and media. And liberalization changed Bollywood in all its permutations. For Hindi film fans, foreign investment and partnerships in Bollywood meant more — more variety, more big-budget films, more stars, more sophistication and technology. Overall, it may be contended that Bollywood cinema became glossier and more

professional because of liberalization. Bollywood was now a serious contender on the world stage and had finally come of age.

The journey of Bollywood from its beginnings to the present day has been long and arduous. However, all the literature on Bollywood reveals that no matter what the theme, the format or the storyline, there is something innately Indian about Bollywood. Bollywood is India. And, it is this one aspect of this essential “Indian-ness” that is at the heart of this study.

Bollywood’s Parallel Movement

Bollywood is the intersection of popular culture, where the classical and traditional do not supersede the modern and global, but instead create a happy medium that is not homogenized or unilinear ([Nandy, 1998](#)). Instead, Bollywood is free to challenge itself and create sometimes strange but always creative new forms of media, and in doing so, it has managed to retain its element of “magic,” despite the increasing use of technology in the films ([Nandy, 1998](#)). Nandy ([1998](#)) contends that this is due to Bollywood not yet forming a mass culture, but this seems unlikely, considering its pervasive existence in Indian life. Taking this argument further, Bollywood’s struggle against massification may also be seen as a struggle between the globalized Indian, and the culturally self-confident but multi-culturally low-brow Indian ([Nandy, 1998](#)). This too appears far-fetched, especially taking into account the varied nature of Bollywood films being churned out, designed to appeal to as many sections of society as may exist.

The art cinema movement is one such movement. Usually the focus of film aficionados, these are the films designed to appeal to the high-brow intellectual Indian. The parallel cinema movement has largely closely mirrored global literary and art movements, and originated in the

1930s, but was said to be in its Golden Age between the 1940s and 1960s ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#)). The pioneers of the movement were Satyajit Ray, Ritwik Ghatak, Bimal Roy, Mrinal Sen, Khwaja Ahmad Abbas, Chetan Anand, Guru Dutt and V. Shantaram ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#)). Parallel cinema drew inspiration from Italian Neo-Realism and French New Wave and poetic realism ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#)).

The earliest example of parallel cinema is said to be V. Shantaram's silent film *Sawkari Pash* (Indian Shylock) in (1925) ([Bose, 2006](#)). Another film, *Achhut Kannya*, 1936 is an early realism-based film that won its share of acclaim. The film portrayed the social condition of 'Dalit' girls. However, many critics point to Satyajit Ray's *Apu* Trilogy, which begins with *Pather Panchali* ([1955](#)); as the real beginning of parallel cinema in India ([Dissanayake & Gokulsing, 2004](#)). The trilogy, consisting of *Pather Panchali* ([1955](#)), *Aparajito* ([1956](#)) and *Apur Sansar* ([1959](#)), was produced on a budget of ₹ 150,000 (less than \$3000); won prizes at the Cannes, Berlin and Venice Film Festivals; and is today frequently listed among the greatest films of all time ([Cooper, 2000](#)).

While parallel cinema won accolades and prizes at international film festivals, it remains notable that with very few exceptions from its early days, it failed to attract the masses to the theatres. An excellent illustration of this is the delayed international success and recognition of *Pyasa* ([1957](#)), and *Kaagaz ke Phool* ([1959](#)), both made by Guru Dutt. While *Pyasa* ([1957](#)) saw commercial success in India after a slow start in the year it was released, *Kagaz ke Phool* ([1959](#)) saw success only in the 1980s, much after Guru Dutt's untimely demise in 1964.

It must be noted in the context of this study and in any study of Indian cinema that while Indian parallel cinema directly drew its influences from western art movements, it

remains Indian in origin by way of its creators and for its treatment of Indian characters and their stories.

The Effects of Parsi Cinema on Bollywood

There are many influences at play in Bollywood cinema. There are those who strongly support the idea that Parsi theatre contributed heavily to the growth of Indian cinematic genres ([Bose, 2006](#); [Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#)). The Parsis, a successful, yet very tiny community in India, have contributed greatly to India's industrial growth ([Hansen, 2003](#)). With the growth of the mass media came the rise of urban entertainment for the westernized masses in big cities. This genre of urban entertainment came to be known as Parsi theatre, which was a mix of Western drama, opera, and other Indian elements ([Hansen, 2003](#)). The Parsis were a community who were English-literate, had social interaction with the colonial elites, and were known for their entrepreneurship skills, leading them to undertake some of the first hybrid theatre forms in India ([Hansen, 2003](#)). This led to Parsi drama being inherently "syncretic" in nature, a composite of Indian and western elements, but uniquely emergent from the society where it dwelt ([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#); [Hansen, 2003, 2009](#))([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#); [Hansen, 2009](#); [Hansen, 2003](#)). It is worth noting here that while these Parsi theatre companies remained Parsi-owned well into the 20th century, they drew their members from all communities within Indian society, including Muslims, Christians, Hindus and others ([Hansen, 2003](#)). They also rarely featured Parsi themes or stories but instead drew from all cultures in a bid for mass appeal and a desire to profit from all audiences ([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#); [Hansen, 2003](#)). This remains an inherent trait and theme in Bollywood cinema.

Parsi theatre offerings included emphasis on spectacle and colorful backdrops, with the staging area being divided into front and back for the staging of main and subsidiary action ([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#)). Music was always part of Parsi theatre, and actors sang as part of all performances and played their roles with melodramatic gusto ([Bose, 2006](#); [Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#)). Themes for storylines came from diverse sources: including well-known popular mythological stories, folklore and contemporary life. Shakespeare was an especial favorite, and perhaps Parsi theatre is to be credited for the proliferation of Shakespearean themes within Indian cinema ([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#)).

While advocates of the Hindutva movement have downplayed or rejected the Parsi and Islamic influences in Indian cinema, it is impossible to deny both elements exist in various aspects of Indian cinema, not the least of which is visible in its music ([Hansen, 2009](#); [A. G. Roy, 2010](#)). Needless to say, Parsi theatre was very popular among the urban masses, and the actors were as revered as later film actors and actresses, with many of them joining Bollywood cinema ([Craig & Kapadia, 2014](#)). And it is especially important to note how Parsi characters and motifs continue to remain popular in Indian cinema.